

DELIVERABLE 3.2

SYNTHESIS OF PLANS OF THE EIGHT LIVING LABS WITH PORTFOLIOS OF REAL-LIFE INTERVENTIONS

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GLOSSARY

FoodCLIC – The acronym FoodCLIC stands for 'integrated urban **FOOD** policies – developing sustainability **Co**-benefits, spatial **L**inkages, social **I**nclusion and sectoral **C**onnections to transform food systems in city-regions'.

City Regional Food System (CRFS) – Within a geographical region, which includes the urban centre and surrounding peri-urban and rural hinterland, “all elements and activities that relate to the production, processing, distribution, preparation and consumption of food, as well as its disposal, [including] the environment, people, processes, infrastructure, institutions and the effects of their activities on our society, economy, landscape and climate”¹.

Food Policy Networks (FPNs) – Networks that represent multiple stakeholders and that may be either sanctioned by a government body or exist independently of government, and address food-related issues and needs within a city, county, state, tribal, multi-county or other designated region.²

Living Lab (LL) – “User-centred, open innovation ecosystems based on systematic user co-creation approaches, integrating research and innovation processes in real-life communities and settings. They focus on co-creation, rapid prototyping & testing and scaling-up innovations & businesses, providing (different types of) joint-value to the involved stakeholders. In this context, living labs operate as intermediaries/orchestrators among citizens, research organisations, companies and government agencies/levels. Within a wide variety of living labs, they all have common characteristics, but multiple different implementations.”³

Real-life interventions (RLIs) – Actions implemented by FoodCLIC that aim to produce changes in food environments that enhance co-benefits, spatial linkages, social inclusion and sectoral connections. RLIs may involve either first-time trials of a particular intervention in a city-region or the scaling-out of an on-going initiative to other locations in the city-region. The RLIs that FoodCLIC seeks to implement and scale aim to help city-regions to reduce knowledge gaps and

¹ EC FOOD 2030 Expert Group (2018) *Recipe for Change: An Agenda for a Climate-Smart and Sustainable Food System for a Healthy Europe*. Brussels: EC, Directorate General for R&I

² Cf. Santo, R., Misiaszek, C., Bassarab, K., Harris, D., & Palmer, A. (2021). Pivoting policy, programs, and partnerships: Food Policy councils' responses to the crises of 2020. Johns Hopkins, Center for a livable future. Retrieved from https://assets.jhsph.edu/clf/mod_clfResource/doc/FPC%202020%20Census%20Report_updated.pdf, last visited 21 April 2024.

³ European Network of Living Labs (no date): What are Living Labs?, <https://enoll.org/about-us/what-are-living-labs/>, last visited 21 April 2024.

improve the evidence base for policy making and food-sensitive planning to contribute to sustainable and inclusive food system transformation.

Food-deprived and vulnerable groups – People whose diets are lacking in quantity or nutritional quality (resulting in food safety risks and undernutrition) on account of limited access because of spatiality (e.g., living in ‘food deserts’), living on low income and/or personal circumstances (e.g., institutionalized persons).

1. INTRODUCTION

Context: The FoodCLIC project

Europe's urban areas face significant challenges to ensure the availability and consumption of healthy, affordable, safe and sustainably produced food. Such challenges converge within local food environments, but are often neglected by public planners. Promising initiatives taken by municipalities to change the architecture of food choice often fail to become embedded in the wider policy context and to reach deprived and vulnerable groups. Key factors responsible for this are: (1) siloed ways of working and (2) fragmentation of knowledge on facilitators and barriers related to food system transformation. These factors hinder the development and implementation of integrated urban food policies. **The FoodCLIC project aims to create strong science-policy-practice interfaces across eight European city-regions**, which together comprise 45 towns and cities. The backbone of such interfaces is provided by **Food Policy Networks (FPNs)**, which manage real-world experimental **Living Labs (LLs)** to build a policy-relevant evidence-base through learning-in-action. In each of the eight city-regions, an academic partner and a practice partner form a LL team.

Activities in the LLs are informed by an innovative **conceptual framework (the CLIC)**, which emphasizes four desired outcomes of food system integration (sustainability co-benefits, spatial linkages, social inclusion and sectoral connectivities). Capacity-building and direct support for intensive multi-stakeholder engagement (including deprived and vulnerable groups) enable policy actors and urban planners across partner city-regions to develop continuously evolving integrated urban food policies and render planning frameworks food-sensitive. Results are communicated and disseminated amongst others by extending the novel policy practices to another eight city-regions in Europe and Africa, an online Knowledge Hub, a high-level Think Tank and partners' networks. In these ways, FoodCLIC aims to contribute to **urban food environments that make healthy and sustainable food available, affordable and attractive to all citizens** (including food deprived and vulnerable groups).

Co-design methodology

This report presents the first results of **Task 3.4: Co-design and implementation of real-life interventions through action-learning cycles**. This task aims to co-design and implement portfolios of real-life interventions and learn from these interventions to inform policy processes. **This report presents the initial selection and design of portfolios of real-life interventions in the eight LLs**. In each LL, stakeholders were invited to co-design real-life interventions in local food

environments and interrelated supply chains based on the CLIC framework. For this purpose, a **co-design methodology** was developed that centred around three **co-design workshops** per LL, one dedicated to interventions at the level of the city-region and two focused on interventions in selected neighbourhoods (co-design guidelines are included in the methodological toolkit, see FoodCLIC Deliverable D1.6). The strategy for the co-design process was adapted in various ways by the LLs to accommodate specific needs, barriers and circumstances. The overarching aim was to foster the active involvement of citizens, in particular food deprived and vulnerable groups, local entrepreneurs (retail, hospitality, start-ups), urban designers, policy-makers and scientists. Where suitable, “city food walks” were organized where local inhabitants showed the strengths and weaknesses of their food environments to entrepreneurs, policy-makers, urban designers, and scientists to engage with local realities and opportunities. These processes resulted in **eight plans with portfolios of real-life interventions**, including objectives, activities, responsibility and a monitoring and evaluation framework.

The co-design processes described in this report built on an extensive visioning and strategizing process. During autumn and early winter 2023/24, the LL teams had organized numerous collaborative activities to identify key problems that are responsible for unhealthy urban food environments (also involving policy-makers, urban planners, city ecologists, designers, researchers). Based on these joint sense-making activities, multi-actor visioning workshops had been organized in each LL to create a **shared vision** for the city-regional food system (exploring “where are we now and where do we want to go”). A second workshop on strategic planning (“and how may we get there”) had created building blocks of an **integrated city-regional food strategy** for each of the eight city-regions. The visioning and strategy workshops in turn built on an analysis of each city-region’s food systems and the challenges they face (mapping and gapping). The results of visioning and strategizing workshops were summarized in FoodCLIC Deliverable 3.1.

To maximize the **coherence and compatibility of the approach** across the eight city-regions, the project coordination (VU Amsterdam) and work package (WP) leadership (Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin and Area Metropolitana de Barcelona (AMB)) provided guidance documents, feedback and training sessions to all LL teams. Within this framework, LL teams developed their own place-based strategies to adopt to the case-specific needs and circumstance and to harness upcoming opportunities.

Structure of the case study reports

The reports for each case (section 2 of this document) have been written by the respective LL teams and edited by the WP leaders. They follow a **shared protocol** which was developed by the WP leaders and refined through iterative discussions with all LL teams. For each of the eight city-regions, we first provide background information on the city-region and the selected neighbourhoods and the most important results of the visioning and strategy workshops and explain the specific aims of each of three co-design workshops. We then describe the scene

setting, planning and participants of the co-design workshops, with a particular focus on how local stakeholders were invited. We then explain the methods used for co-design and why they were selected. An overview table lists the participants in the do-design workshops and other activities. We then summarize the key results of each workshop and the co-design workshops overall. This section closes with a reflection by the respective LL team on lessons learned and a brief outlook on the next steps. The second section in each city-regional case contains a list of the real-life interventions (RLI) which have been selected and devised during the co-design process. For each RLI, we provide the identified target level (neighbourhood or city-region), a brief description, summarise the objectives and the envisaged activities, define the responsibilities, estimate the required resources and make suggestions for monitoring and evaluation. Finally, we reflect on how each intervention meets key project and local criteria (engaging food deprived and vulnerable communities; engaging innovative business models; contributing to the CLIC dimensions; which food environments are addressed; alignment with vision/strategic planning; any other criteria developed with co-design partners).

Based on the preliminary intervention plans and proposals presented in this report, the strategic plans will be implemented and further refined through an iterative process of reflexive action and learning cycles. Guided by the LL team, the FPNs in each case study city-region will **implement their portfolios of real-life interventions**. The implementation of the real-life interventions will take place over a period of 24 months (spring 2024 until spring 2026), under the coordination of the practice partners, while research partners will be responsible for stimulating collective reflection, monitoring the process and identifying intermediate outcomes (Task 3.5 of the FoodCLIC project). Over this period, four six-monthly multi-stakeholder reflexive learning sessions will be organized in each LL to (1) discuss progress with respect to the activities and their intermediary outcomes, with a particular focus on translating (intermediate) outcomes into lessons/evidence to inform the policy process (Task 3.3 of the project); (2) identify what goes well and what needs to be improved; (3) understand barriers and make the necessary adjustments; (4) work towards required changes in local and higher-level policy and planning to remove persistent barriers to change; (5) identify innovative business models for broadening and scaling up. These processes and results will be presented in FoodCLIC Deliverable D3.3 at the end of the fourth year of the project in autumn 2026.

2. REPORTS FROM THE LIVING LABS

2.1 AARHUS

2.1.1 SUMMARY OF THE CO-DESIGN PROCESS IN AARHUS

Background and aims of the co-design workshops

Leading up to the co-design of RLIs, the visioning and strategizing workshops held during October and November 2023 in Aarhus city-region included diverse stakeholders from across sectors who displayed a variety of interests, perspectives and preferred approaches when identifying key issues and pathways for sustainable food system transformation of the Aarhus urban food environment. Results indicated that key understandings of major problems in the city-region food system (CRFS) differ, but there are common concerns: the distances to food origins and food production, lack of food literacy, dominance of large retails in local markets and narrow available food choices and consumption culture, as well as poor alignment among different actors on a common systemic vision for the local food system.

The multi-stakeholder workshops led to the successful formation of four strategic visions for the Aarhus city -region reflected by the four themes presented in Fig. 1. These strategic visions were informed by, and well aligned with, the current national and local discussions around the future of the food system, e.g., promoting more sustainable consumption patterns. Beyond implementation of the Climate Political Food Strategy, the Aarhus City Council adopted a “Climate Action Plan (2021-2024)” that supported a comprehensive green transition in the city region. Through FoodCLIC support, the significant efforts of the Aarhus Living Lab (LL) have been instrumental in bolstering and promoting the inclusion of food to a greater extent in the current revision of the “Climate Action Plan 2025-2030” of Aarhus Municipality. This revision is currently ongoing and is expected to be finalized by August 2024.

Figure 1: The 4 strategic themes generated from the visioning and strategizing workshops: “common direction”, “food literacy”, “where does the food come from” and “plant-based plate of the future”, utilized during as a starting point for the RLIs co-design process

Another important background aspect to co-design of RLIs in Aarhus is the internal framework developed by the LL, which recognizes co-design activities as the opportunity to begin a “defining” phase of the overall FoodCLIC process in the city-region (Fig. 2). The “defining” phase aims primarily to define the overall concept and activities of the targeted RLIs and to identify appropriate stakeholders to recruit as part of the co-design groups for “refining” the RLIs during spring 2024.

Scene setting and planning

To achieve a broad representation of the Aarhus food system stakeholders and draft interventions that foster meaningful change, two “defining” workshops (see Figure 2) were organized in different locations of the city. These two co-design venues were selected to capture the different perspectives of two very different demographics of the residents in these areas: older professionals versus a younger and more activist demographic.

Figure 2: Schematic showing the current stage of ongoing RLI co-design process

Co-design workshop at Agro Food Park 26 (AFP 26) - An ecosystem for agri-food businesses

The first workshop was held on 7th March 2024 in the [Agro Food Park](#) from 9.30-12:00 AM (incl. lunch). [Agro Food Park](#) is an industry-specific ecosystem for agricultural and food businesses and was utilized as a professional venue to organize the workshop to attract relevant actors. The event was held in Danish. Approximately 60 people were invited through direct e-mailing, using contact information from networks that the LL has developed through preparing and hosting previous FoodCLIC activities, with invitees including farmers, chefs, researchers, policy makers, food banks, and several business and industry stakeholders. Furthermore, to achieve a broad participatory list, the event was promoted through flyers and several key networks and professional channels

through Aarhus University, i.e., [AU-FOOD Department's LinkedIn page](#), the [Agro Food Park](#) newsletter, the [AU Citizen Science](#) network, the [AIAS](#) network, and the [Kitchen Hub](#) entrepreneurial network.

Co-design at Café Mellemfolk (Cafe of Action Aid Denmark)

The second workshop was held on 14th March 2024 at [Café Mellemfolk](#) which is a key institution at the heart of the activist community in Aarhus. Located in the city centre, this evening workshop and dinner was organized by Aarhus Municipality in collaboration with the Food Justice group from Mellemfolkeligt Samvirke (Action Aid Denmark). The event was promoted on the Facebook page of the Café. Holding an event in this venue gave the opportunity to interact and hear the opinions of a very different demographic, fostering greater inclusivity and diverse participation. Moreover, the time (afternoon outside of working hours) and location (easy access in Aarhus Centre) increased the accessibility of the event. Unlike the other co-design workshop at AFP 26, participants attending this event did not represent particular affiliations, but rather were individuals with strong interests in climate and food.

Co-design methodologies

Both co-design workshops followed a similar methodological procedure, which included:

- a) an opening presentation
- b) 1st round of brainstorming – RLI conceptualization (definition)
- c) 2nd round of brainstorming – RLI conceptualization (enrichment; only used in the AFP 26 workshop due to time constraints)
- d) Voting – dotmocracy, and
- e) 3rd round of brainstorming – RLI conceptualization (focusing on add-on elements for the most popular RLIs).

First, an (a) opening presentation provided information about the project background, relevant terms, definitions and concepts for designing the RLIs (i.e. CLIC pillars, food environments, strategic themes, etc.). During the first round of brainstorming (b.), participants were divided into groups of approximately 4-5 people and a

The image shows a digital form titled 'RLI template' used for brainstorming. It features the logos of Aarhus University and Aarhus Kommune at the top left, and the 'food clic' logo at the top right. The form is divided into several sections:

- Title:** A blank space for entering the title.
- Description:** A section with the prompt: 'What is this intervention about? Which strategic themes does it cover?'
- Objective:** A section with the prompts: 'What are we trying to achieve?' and 'What are we going to observe if it is successful?'
- Activities:** A section with the prompt: 'What actions & processes we need in place to get there?'. Below this prompt are three circular icons labeled I, II, and III.
- Where, When, Who & How?:** A section with the prompts: 'Where do it take place? food environments, urban rural', 'When does it happen? How long, how often, timeline elements', 'Who? is involved, does it concern, is responsible', and 'How? resources required & what is available'.

At the bottom of the form, there is a footer containing the text 'Funded by the European Union', the email 'foodclic.beta@aal', and the website 'www.foodclic.eu'.

Figure 3: RLI template utilized during the brainstorming sessions of the co-design workshops

facilitator led a structured discussion to fill in a structured RLI planning template (Fig. 3). Participants were not asked to assess issues like CLIC-pillars, Food Environments or Strategic themes directly, but rather to keep them in mind while brainstorming. During the second round (c.), all participants except one (the “narrator”) had a chance to switch tables to contribute to another group’s RLI concepts. Once seated, the narrator’s role was to present the RLIs developed by their respective group, and newcomers at the table were instructed to discuss, enrich and/or raise concerns to the RLI content presented, ultimately strengthening the ideas (due to the time restrictions step c was only included at the AFP 26 workshop).

Next, voting (step d.), using dotmocracy for **application of consent-based decision-making**, was performed. Participants were instructed to vote for the RLIs they found to be the best for transforming the Aarhus food system according to the common vision presented. Each participant was handed 3 green dots for positive votes and 1 red dot to visualize points of divergence. The red sticker needed to be accompanied by a post-it with a short explanation for the LL team to be able to understand the reasoning behind the divergence. After the dotmocracy exercise, during the **AFP 26 workshop** the four to five interventions that received the highest number of green dots were chosen and placed at separate tables and participants were called to choose the intervention they found the most promising to work on, and further develop/refine. Due to time restrictions, this last step was modified at **Café Mellemfolk**, where the templates were organized thematically on the wall and then participants were called to populate the RLI themes they found more appealing to work with. A QR-code leading to a brief questionnaire was shared with participants to give feedback on the activity to improve for future activities in the FoodCLIC project.

Figure 4: Pictures of the Agro Food Park 26 (left) and Café Mellemfolk (right) co-design workshops for “defining” the RLIs, held at the 7th and 14th of March, respectively. Photo credits: Konstantina Sfyrá, AU.

Table 1: List of participants in the co-design activities in Aarhus Metropolitan Area

ORGANISATION	SECTOR
CITY-REGION WORKSHOP AT AGRO PARK 26	
Aarhus University (3)	Research and education
Simons kogeskole	Business and industry
Mellemfolkeligt Samvirke (Action Aid Denmark)	Civil society
Erhvervshus Midtjylland	Business and industry
Kontekst Kommunikation	Business and industry
Chef	Business and industry
Farmer, Høsteriet	Civil society
Food bank, Fødevarebanken	Civil society
Aarhus Municipality (2)	Government and public sector
SEGES (2)	Business and industry
Agro Food Park	Business and industry
Arla Foods	Business and industry
Food and Bio Cluster	Business and industry
CITY-REGION WORKSHOP AT CAFÉ MELLEMFOLK	
Dyrenes Alliance (2)	Civil society
Student	Civil society
Happy Food Forest	Business and industry
Aarhus University	Research and education
Mellemfolkeligt Samvirke (7)	Civil society

Description of co-design results

Though these co-design workshops took place in two different areas, there was consistent prioritization of RLIs selected for transformation of the Aarhus city food system, demonstrating the overall salience and validity of these intervention approaches (see Table 2 description). Moreover, it constituted a concrete step towards cultivating a shared sense of ownership and commitment and a shared vision for the designed RLIs amongst very different actors of the Aarhus food landscape. A summary of the key results in terms of RLIs concepts generated at each workshop is included in Table 2. These concepts were then analysed according to content and votes to synthesize the RLIs included in section 2.1.2.

Table 1: Summary of RLI concepts (given as title and number of votes) generated at the two co-design workshops. G and R stand for green and red dots received during the voting, respectively. Each participant was given one red and three green optional votes (dots).

AFP 26 (17 PARTICIPANTS)	CAFÉ MELLEMFOLK (12 PARTICIPANTS)
Suburban food production (12 Gs)	Agro-schools (6 Gs)
Green “festuge”: making the local food week greener (9 Gs)	A green school-gardening for kids (5 Gs)
Local food literacy (7 Gs)	Go local market (4 Gs)
Food Council (5 Gs)	Bio region Aarhus: Platform for citizens – local farmers (4 Gs)
Training of personnel working with food (2 Gs)	Fruit & Berry – alley cropping community (4 Gs)
Surplus food for vulnerable population (2 Gs)	Educating institutional actors to buy better food (3 Gs)
“Actual” give families and young adults engaging info on the entire food chain (2 Gs)	Reconnecting kids to the food origin (3 Gs)
School kitchens and gardens (0 Gs)	FOOD SHARING to reduce food waste (3 Gs)
	Community supported agriculture (2 Gs)
	Communal dinners for students (2 Gs + 1 R)
	Strengthening link btw consumer + producer (1 Gs)
	Local-connected food system (0 GS)

Co-design workshop at Agro Food Park 26

The quality of inputs from participants as well as the number and diversity of attendees were substantial achievements, as has been increasing with the progression of the FoodCLIC project in Aarhus. Participants had a good initial understanding of what the objective of the current workshop was, underlining the success of previous workshops. Results from the workshop (namely the RLIs) align with the established strategic themes, CLIC pillars and food environments presented and fall in line with what would be expected based on the visioning sessions in the fall of 2023. What stood out as an RLI concept when compared to Café Mellemfolk was the creation of a local Food Council, which can be partly explained by the background of participants attending this workshop. This forum of participants can be described as more inclined towards institutionalized approaches to address food system challenges as well as to create opportunities for themselves to have more direct impact (and voice) on policy-making processes and governance structures within the food system and community. Moreover, the apparent networking and collaboration opportunities initiated for and between participants of the workshop seemed to form valuable connections as an additional output. This not only enhances the potential of the FoodCLIC project but may also foster a community of like-minded professionals committed to advancing their respective fields and across the Aarhus city-region food system.

Co-design workshop at Café Mellemfolk

With a more activist-minded demographic, the general focus at Café Mellemfolk, while touching upon local production and food education, also addressed the needs of vulnerable and food-deprived populations (communal dinners) and food waste (food sharing) which were mentioned to a lesser extent at the AFP 26 workshop. The RLI concepts proposed to strengthen the link between rural producers and urban consumers of the city-region, for example via community supported agriculture or creating more local markets. Proposals demonstrated that participants had a good understanding of the challenges that these communities face, crafting potential solutions to enhance access to nutritious food, advocate for sustainable agricultural practices (for example by addressing biodiversity in farmlands and improving soil), and implementing initiatives to minimize food waste through food sharing.

Selection of neighbourhoods

Based on the synergistic nature of priorities in both workshops to improve urban food literacy and bolster local sustainable food producers, two neighbourhoods are being explored as potential areas to connect through RLIs: (1) the Hjortschø neighbourhood on the rural outskirts of Aarhus, home to working farmers in search of viable business models and new local markets, and (2) the neighbourhood of Gellerup, a more urbanized, multi-cultural setting with a new school being developed and a local "Bazar Vest" food market as a potential point of entry to engage with residents and youth from a diverse background.

Lessons Learned

The workshops provided valuable inputs and ideas for activities and interventions in the future phases of the project. While we consider the outputs of the workshops a success, the progression of the co-design was also made achievable from the overall agreement on the direction of the food system (from the visioning) which seemed clear and apparent to the participants. This was particularly due to the efficient introduction to the workshops as well as some participants' prior involvement in the visioning process and familiarity with the methods, which were clear and effective. However, to ensure this clear and accessible entry point for participants, it was important to avoid in-depth and excessive background and overly academic language. Our goal was to foster an inclusive environment where every individual could contribute meaningfully to the creation of interventions.

For the future, it is crucial to exercise caution when presenting the project, for example, when discussing potentially sensitive issues like addressing vulnerability within communities. Certain terms or language choices from the project description can carry negative connotations to the participants. Some participants raised valid concerns regarding the use of the term "vulnerable". While the term was used with the intention of highlighting the need for support and assistance to these community groups, this term can lead to misunderstanding or reinforce marginalization of

certain groups. We also saw a clear example of a participant from a potentially vulnerable group (a young farmer) using the workshop to voice a concern regarding specific planning decisions in Aarhus Municipality, which will affect her farm. Here, the workshop was utilized as a platform for direct mobilization around an urgent issue, in this case urging attendance at an upcoming public hearing.

Outlook

Following the first round of “defining” workshops, next steps will focus on synthesizing the outcomes to gain an understanding of the exact step-by-step content of the RLIs via “refining” activities, utilized both for gaining insights but also recruiting interesting co-creating parties. This process will entail further interpreting the details of the interventions in terms of their objectives, activities, and specific components to examine feasibility within the context of existing time and resources. These processes will be accompanied with additional events concentrated on refining the RLIs (including neighbourhood walks and site visits) to both generate additional input but also local commitment to the RLIs. In our upcoming co-design event agenda, is the presentation of FoodCLIC and RLIs at “[Fritidsforsker for en dag](#)”, a public science fair in Aarhus, where visitors will have the chance to immerse themselves in the project and come with ideas for refinement of the RLIs created in the co-design workshops. It is also important to mention that the Aarhus Living Lab is currently navigating the national political agenda where the debate regarding the implementation of a CO₂ tax on agriculture is high on the agenda. This practically means that the local initiatives and actions we propose in the Aarhus LL to some extent can play into and inform the national agenda.

2.1.2 PORTFOLIO OF REAL-LIFE INTERVENTIONS

The table below provides an overview of the tentative real-life interventions planned during the co-design workshops in Aarhus, subject to the next steps to refine these plans in further.

INTERVENTION 1 – SUPPORT LOCAL FARMING & CONSUMPTION CULTURE	
Level	City-region
Brief Description	Support local farming through provision of tools, resources and opportunities for “young” farmers, to initiate or create sustainable local businesses in the area of Aarhus that can “feed” the city.
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase sustainable local farming practices • Increase the number of local farmers / businesses • Development of novel & improved business models

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase local procurement of goods
Activities envisaged	
1.	Development of network/platform mapping & registering interested “young” farmers – small local farms through which they can showcase their profile/business/practices/produce to support communication, network and attract customers (Initial development in first 6 months, and updates thereafter).
2.	Farmers’ workshop organization for knowledge exchange, i.e. practices between farmers, but also between research and farmers, i.e. alley cropping, or between businesses and farmers, i.e. wishes for local ingredients (annually or bi-annually).
3.	Piloting local farmers market, a concept not existing currently in Aarhus. Using the network created in activity #1, to invite and organize a local farmers’ market which will be advertised and open to citizens. These pilot events will be used to evaluate the success of such a concept in the Aarhus city-region and will also act as an opportunity for citizens to get introduced to local production and taste their produce (bi-annually, in spring / summer months due to weather conditions).
4.	Farmers expo for networking with local hospitality businesses/retailers. An occasion for other food professionals to meet and taste what is produced locally at the Aarhus municipality, including a “Meet your farmer” session (annually, in spring / summer months due to weather conditions).
Responsibilities	TBD
Resources	TBD
Monitoring & Evaluation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase in the number of “young” farmers following the network • Increase in the number of farmers’ markets in Aarhus • Increase in local procurement of goods (municipal or private – business or citizen level) • Increase in self-reported perceived economic security of “young” farmers
Criteria: How does this intervention meet key project and local criteria?	
Engaging food deprived & vulnerable communities	“Young” is used as a classification of the professional level, not the age of the individual, describing a vulnerable professional community attempting to establish themselves in a non-optimal and highly competitive context (e.g., vegetables can be procured at lower prices from abroad) or through non-traditional/novel business models.

Engaging innovative business models	Sustainable small farmer practices addressing procurement at a city-region level is an innovative novel business model in the Danish context, especially when addressing the production of organic and plant-based food
CLIC dimensions	<p>Co- benefits: local production – synergistic outcomes for environment, economy and society</p> <p>Linkages: rural production to urban consumption</p> <p>Inclusion: of young farmers, researchers, food-businesses, citizens</p> <p>Connectivities: addressing the need of changing the local procurement societal culture and/or policies</p>
Food environments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agrifood: Urban agriculture establishment; Digital: Platform connecting farmers and showcasing their business • Retail: Farmers’ market/ Expo piloting • Hospitality: only if the connection is established through Expo or networking • Institutional: only if the connection is established through Expo or networking
Alignment with vision/strategic plan	<p>Aligned with the following strategic themes defined in the visioning/strategizing workshops</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Food literacy: addressed through the workshops with focus on exchanging knowledge between and amongst practitioners (farmers) and researchers • Where does the food come from: Increase citizens’ (and retailers’) knowledge of local production/opportunities • Plant-based plate of the future: Activities focus and support local and sustainable food production and practices
Other important information	RLI concept draws from proposals generated in both co-design events acquiring in total ~29 votes

INTERVENTION 2 – IMPROVE FOOD LITERACY AND SKILLS IN SCHOOLS

Level	Neighbourhood
Brief Description	Including lesson plans and activities in schools providing knowledge and skills around food, healthy diets and sustainable eating behaviours.
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase food literacy amongst students • Increase the investment and skills of students in food production and cooking • Increase awareness of environmental impact of food consumption

Activities envisaged	<i>Activities will be placed around the school year – specifics on frequency and timeline need to be agreed with the participating schools</i>
1.	Training the educators. Increasing the food literacy of teachers in order to impact the everyday life of students through workshops targeted at the staff in the respective schools.
2.	Communal gardens establishment at schools or visits. Give opportunities to students to grow their own food ingredients/vegetables and learn more about their growing cultivation needs (incl. time), production and usage.
3.	Communal/neighbourhood meals. Give opportunities to students and their families to cook plant based healthy meals, using the outcomes of their cultivation activities as well as locally produced ingredients for sharing amongst the community (either at neighbourhood or school level). The use of surplus foods from retail or other sources can be included in these activities to increase awareness on food waste and reduction strategies.
4.	Cooking with professionals/chefs easy, healthy, plant-based recipes. Inspiring and giving the skills to students to become self-sufficient and learn about healthy and sustainable eating through practice.
Responsibilities	TBD
Resources	TBD
Monitoring & Evaluation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase in student/family participation in organized activities • Increase in self-reported share of plant-based and/or healthy meals amongst students at schools • Increase knowledge, knowledge sharing, and interest connected to healthy and locally produced food (monitored through questionnaires or activities)
Criteria: How does this intervention meet key project and local criteria?	
Engaging food deprived & vulnerable communities	We consider children as a vulnerable target group, whose choices are highly affected by their surrounding environment (family, school, peers) and thus we want to engage with children by organizing activities addressing their whole environment. We consider recruiting schools in neighbourhoods located in the centre of Aarhus that are more remote from “nature” settings and/or ostracized neighbourhoods where food insecurity can have a higher incidence rate.

CLIC dimensions	<p>Co-benefits: better – sustainable/ healthy – food choices amongst students – synergistic outcomes for environment (sustainability aspects) and society (health aspects)</p> <p>Linkages: urban schools connected to rural setting (communal vegetable gardens)</p> <p>Inclusion: of families, students, teachers, chefs</p> <p>Connectivities: with the political health agenda in Aarhus and the political focus on children and young people’s health and well being</p>
Food environments (and digital aspects if applicable)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agrifood: communal/ school gardens • Retail: only if supermarkets provide surplus food for activities • Institutional: meals at schools
Alignment with vision/strategic plan	<p>Aligned with the following strategic themes defined in the visioning/strategizing workshops:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Food literacy: addressed through “training the educators” • Where does the food come from: addressed through “communal – school gardens” • Plant-based plate of the future: addressed through “communal neighbourhood meals” and “cooking with professionals”
Other important information	RLI concept draws from proposals generated in both co-design events acquiring in total ~18 votes

INTERVENTION 3 – RECONNECT CHILDREN TO FOOD ORIGINS THROUGH LOCAL PRODUCTION

Level	City (farms) to neighbourhood level (schools)
Brief Description	Connecting schools and local farms in the Aarhus area via visits, interactive activities, talks, etc. This can include visits of students to local farms to reconnect with food production and train their “farming skills”, but also visits of farmers to school grounds to help with communal/school vegetable garden and to share their knowledge with children.
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Connectivities between schools and farms on a knowledge sharing level • Increase interest/investment of students and families in local farming and use of local food sources in the preparation of their meals • Increase knowledge on the origin of food amongst students

Activities envisaged	<i>Activities will be placed around the school year – specifics on frequency and timeline need to be agreed with the participating schools</i>
1.	School visits in local farms. Students can visit the local farms, meet the farmers, learn about local food production and assist – engage in tasks around the farm to gain skills. Visits can be accompanied by researcher talks addressing other parts of “green” food production and environmental impact of locally produced goods vs. imports/exports.
2.	Farmers’ visits to communal gardens. Farmers visits to assist setting up the communal (neighbourhood or school) gardens and engage with students on introducing them and help them sharpen their skills in food production via hands on activities.
3.	Common cooking events. Farmers introduce how their ingredients can be used in different healthy recipes in cooking events amongst staff, students and families.
4.	Piloting inclusion of locally procured ingredients in school meals. Addressing how to incorporate local ingredients in school meals, including seasonality, production number, recipes, etc.
Responsibilities	TBD
Resources	TBD
Monitoring & Evaluation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More local procurement on a school or institute level • More knowledge amongst students/families • New business models
Criteria: How does this intervention meet key project and local criteria?	
Engaging food deprived & vulnerable communities	This intervention engages with both “young farmers” and “children” which are both considered vulnerable communities in our local context
Engaging innovative business models	Turning local production into local procurement pathways. Increase of competitiveness of locally produced food
CLIC dimensions	<p>Co-benefits: Local sustainable , local farmer businesses (economy), healthy student meals (society)</p> <p>Linkages: urban schools connected to rural agriculture</p> <p>Inclusion: of families, students, teachers, chefs, farmers</p> <p>Connectivities: with the political sustainability and health agenda of Aarhus</p>

Food environments (and digital aspects if applicable)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agrifood: communal/school gardens & farms • Institutional: meals at schools • Retail: (if business is established between farmers and institutions/individuals)
Alignment with vision/strategic plan	<p>Aligned with the following strategic themes defined in the visioning/strategizing workshops</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Food literacy: addressed through knowledge sharing during cultivation/cooking activities • Where does the food come from: addressed through “communal – school gardens” & farm visits <p>Plant-based plate of the future: addressed through “common cooking events” and “piloting of ingredients”</p>
Other important information	This is an intervention connecting with Interventions 1 & 2
INTERVENTION 4 – LOCAL FOOD COUNCIL	
Level	City-region
Brief Description	Community that creates a common direction through sharing of information
Objectives	Creating a forum that creates a common direction for the food system of Aarhus, to all, from all
Activities envisaged	
1.	Create knowledge communities
2.	Start up and facilitate common projects (how to best help each other)
3.	Pave the way for new projects and activities: “Stepping stone”, from food idea to sustainable company
4.	Rediscover the cooperative way of thinking
5.	Promote the plant-based agenda; create demand (green energy, green food, green business models)
Responsibilities	TBD
Resources	TBD
Monitoring & Evaluation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Shared vision amongst food stakeholders • Local new business (sustainable) • Spin-off projects • Promotion of green agendas

Criteria: How does this intervention meet key project and local criteria?	
Engaging food deprived & vulnerable communities	Inclusivity in the food council engaging with schools, citizens and vulnerable communities (to all, from all)
Engaging innovative business models	Facilitation of local common projects and businesses
CLIC dimensions	<p>Co-benefits: amongst all Aarhus stakeholders</p> <p>Linkages: between professionals in rural and urban settings</p> <p>Inclusion: of all stakeholder representatives</p> <p>Connectivities: aspiring to affect & inform local food policies</p>
Food environments (and digital aspects if applicable)	A local food council will interact and affect all food environments including: Agrifood, retail, institutional and hospitality
Alignment with vision/strategic plan	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Food literacy: knowledge sharing communities • Where does the food come from: local food focus • Plant-based plate of the future: focus on plant-based • Common food system direction
Other important information	RLI concept draws from one proposal generated in the AFP 26 event, acquiring in total 5 votes. However, it is the only RLI clearly addressing the strategic theme for a common vision across the Aarhus food system

INTERVENTION 5 – BUY BETTER FOOD, EDUCATING FOOD PROFESSIONALS & INSTITUTIONS

Level	City-region
Brief Description	Increased focus on facilitation of local procurement and training and development of competencies of personnel working with food to use local raw materials and avoid food waste.
Objectives	Increased knowledge in the usage of seasonal produce in professional kitchens and avoidance of food waste
Activities envisaged	
1.	Facilitation of local procurement
2.	Training of food professionals on how to use local ingredients and adapt recipes
3.	Training of food professionals how to avoid/lower food waste - Food waste hacks
Responsibilities	TBD
Resources	TBD
Monitoring & Evaluation	TBD

Criteria: How does this intervention meet key project and local criteria?	
Engaging innovative business models	Local procurement – businesses
CLIC dimensions	<p>Co-benefits: for food professionals and local producers/farmers</p> <p>Linkages: of urban food professionals and rural producers/farmers</p> <p>Connectivities: aspiring to affect institutional procurement policies</p>
Food environments (and digital aspects if applicable)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agrifood: farmers • Institutional: Professional kitchens • Hospitality: (in case this model is further extended)
Alignment with vision/strategic plan	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Food literacy: through trainings • Where does the food come from: through knowledge of local raw materials • Plant-based plate of the future: focus on plant-based
Other important information	RLI concept draws from proposals generated in both co-design events acquiring in total ~5-12 votes (depending on the conceptualization)
INTERVENTION 6 – LESS FOOD WASTE, MORE FOOD SHARING	
Level	From city-region (surplus) to neighbourhood level (community)
Brief Description	Use surplus foods from production to food literacy projects – food schools to increase the wellbeing of vulnerable (elderly, homeless, ethnic groups) population through food preparation, sharing and communal eating
Objectives	Lower food waste, broaden the mind, inform dietary habits
Activities envisaged	
1.	Food waste curriculum with hacks and knowledge
2.	Workshops tailored to the target groups' needs
3.	Food waste competitions for the “festuge” in Aarhus
Responsibilities	Use of Social Media campaigns for public engagement
Resources	TBD
Monitoring & Evaluation	TBD
Criteria: How does this intervention meet key project and local criteria?	
Engaging food deprived & vulnerable communities	Surplus food sharing with vulnerable communities and groups through communal dinners

Engaging innovative business models	Valorisation of food waste locally – creatively
CLIC dimensions	<p>Co-benefits: for food professionals/retailers and communities</p> <p>Linkages: Vulnerable communities and broader population through communal dinners</p> <p>Inclusion: of vulnerable groups</p> <p>Connectivities: To local and national food waste initiatives and strategies.</p>
Food environments (and digital aspects if applicable)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Institutional: institutions engaging with vulnerable populations • Retail: providing the surplus • Hospitality: in case this model is further extended
Alignment with vision/strategic plan	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Food literacy: Reduction of food waste • Where does the food come from: appreciation of food resources
Other important information	RLI concept draws from proposals generated in both co-design events acquiring in total ~5-7 votes
INTERVENTION 7 – MAKE AARHUS GREENER	
Level	City-region
Brief Description	Redefining the City of Aarhus as a green consumption city with local food production and culture, through citizen events, activities and food tourism (food city tours) to support local food growers and professionals
Objectives	To redefine the Aarhus food scene, production and consumption culture throughout the city via different “green activities”
Activities envisaged	
1.	Make the festive “festuge” week more green → sustainable festive week: Green transport; Green packaging; Green meals
2.	Marketing-free urban zone (and city busses) – avoid commercials for unhealthy/unsustainable products; help with decisions to eat healthy; avoid serving/selling unhealthy meals/products
3.	Promote local production and plant-based – healthy products. Organize food city tours to promote local businesses
4.	Create local food education/cooking schools like food camps for schools
Responsibilities	TBD
Resources	TBD
Monitoring & Evaluation	TBD

Criteria: How does this intervention meet key project and local criteria?	
Engaging innovative business models	Plant-based, local production, local consumption
CLIC dimensions	<p>Co-benefits: for different food professionals and producers (economic) and citizens through the enhancement of green/healthy consumption choices (social)</p> <p>Linkages: of urban food professionals and rural producers/farmers</p>
Food environments (and digital aspects if applicable)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agrifood: farmers • Hospitality: food businesses
Alignment with vision/strategic plan	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Food literacy: Better food choices • Where does the food come from: Promotion of local food • Plant-based plate of the future: focus on plant-based food
Other important information	RLI concept draws from proposals generated in the Mellemfolk event acquiring in total 9-11 votes. Lack of vulnerable group focus so far.

2.2 AMSTERDAM

2.2.1 SUMMARY OF THE CO-DESIGN PROCESS IN AMSTERDAM

Background and aims of the co-design workshops

Development of the co-design process in the Amsterdam Metropolitan Area (AMA) was significantly influenced by the outcomes of FoodCLIC “mapping and gapping” in the first half of 2023, and multi-stakeholder visioning and strategy sessions held in November 2023 and January 2024, respectively. Mapping and gapping identified local pathways that require transformation, including access to land, the right to food and the inclusion of relatively food-deprived and vulnerable groups in food and spatial policymaking.

The initial visioning session played a pivotal role in gathering insights from a diverse range of stakeholders, enhancing our understanding of the values driving the project stakeholders. This session identified twelve core values essential to the food system transformation in AMA: health, sustainability, accessibility, affordability, honesty, locality, commons, neighbourhood focus, city-hinterland relations, health as the norm, community engagement, and circularity. These values, along with co-created visions of six FoodCLIC food environments, laid a foundation for the co-design process.

The subsequent strategy session marked a critical juncture in decision-making, engaging strategic partners and various initiatives in a collaborative effort to refine ideas and determine the most promising interventions for the FoodCLIC project, narrowing a long list of ideas to five key interventions to pursue. This process not only highlighted the dynamic energy within AMA's current food system but also underscored the commitment to driving meaningful change through the project.

The co-design workshops were aimed not only at generating actionable insights to develop interventions, but also to strengthen the fabric of community collaboration across various locales within the AMA. Specifically, three neighbourhoods were identified for project interventions:

- **Amsterdam Noord** - the only city-district of Amsterdam on the other side of the river IJ. The area inhabits almost 100.000 citizens and is characterised by remnants of heavy industry and a housing style resembling a 'garden city'. The district is one of three 'attention areas' for city development. The population is generally less affluent than the average for Amsterdam. The area is relatively close to farmland and along the edge, there are many old allotment gardens.
- **Amsterdam Zuidoost** – a large city district on the outskirts of Amsterdam which is among the most diverse areas in the city in terms of its population. The area is less affluent than

the average for Amsterdam. In Zuidoost, many urban development projects are planned, governed by the Masterplan 2040. Food retail is concentrated in a few central hubs which are accessible by metro, bus, bike and car. The district is also characterised by strong activity in (often informal) food catering. Moreover, there are informal food banks that largely focus on providing undocumented residents of the city with food.

- **Haarlem Schalkwijk** – the largest district in Haarlem. Built around the 1960s to solve a shortage of housing, it is now characterised as a green district with higher cultural diversity than the rest of the city. There is one large shopping mall, located in the centre of the district. Compared to Haarlem, Schalkwijk has a higher percentage of households living in poverty and relying on social benefits.

The primary objectives for the co-design process in these neighbourhoods and at city-regional level are to foster action and tangible outcomes, build trust among stakeholders, define the scope of collaborative activities, and facilitate the formation of alliances and working groups.

Scene setting and planning

Recognizing the impracticality of convening large-scale workshops for an expansive and highly diverse network, we adopted a more focused approach. Instead of three general workshops, six intervention-specific co-design sessions were organized as of the time of reporting, with plans for another four workshops and further follow-up sessions.

Co-design sessions were convened in different settings for each intervention:

- Amsterdam Noord neighbourhood: The Living Lab's involvement over the past year has aimed to further integrate the FoodCLIC project within a well-established network (active for 2.5 years) between informal food initiatives in this neighbourhood, the city-district municipality, supporting institutions, and the local church community. This local church community, in a coalition coordinator role, invited participants to the session, and the municipality provided a welcoming venue and catering.
- In Amsterdam Zuidoost, two co-design workshops have taken place for our neighbourhood-focused intervention, with another scheduled. Here, efforts diverge significantly from those in Noord, reflecting the distinct dynamics of Zuidoost. Unlike Noord, Zuidoost lacks a unified meeting platform and municipal involvement is minimal. We partnered with GroenplatVorm Zuidoost, a neighbourhood initiative, to reach out to a diverse array of local food initiatives to bridge gaps among various stakeholders (cooks, green initiatives, and other institutions).
- One session was held in the Haarlem Schalkwijk neighbourhood, collaborating with the civil society network Haarlem Food Future and a collective of social entrepreneurs to invite stakeholders not previously involved in our initial mapping activities.

- At city-region level we initiated an intervention focusing on the public procurement practices of Amsterdam's municipal employers. So far, one co-design session has been held in collaboration with the municipality, which plays a leading role in this process. The session brought together representatives from universities, the green business sector, and community wealth building initiatives.
- At city-region level, the last intervention addresses cooperative food production, aiming to craft a narrative around land access through cooperatives. Utilizing our extensive network of CSA farmers and affiliated organizations, we hosted an online co-design session, with plans for a subsequent physical gathering.

Co-design methodologies

Each co-design session followed similar methodological steps: 1) getting acquainted; 2) alignment between the project's intention and the goals/needs of stakeholders and participants, i.e.: creating common ground; 3) content elaboration: thinking together about an action plan; 4) discussion on the form, e.g.: how do we allocate finances, how do we take decisions together, what values are beneath our actions?

For getting acquainted and building trust, a method was adopted from an existing initiative in Amsterdam Noord. In this exercise, all participants form a circle and are asked to share who they are, what their initiative is about and what barriers they face at this point.

To create alignment between the project's intention and the goals of local stakeholders, a document template was used in a facilitated discussion to explore local goals, key barriers and needs. Participants' inputs were clustered into an overview of common barriers and objectives. In Amsterdam Zuidoost, a 'World Café' methodology was used to generate actions based upon the common objectives and concrete actions within the project timeline.

Throughout these co-design processes, the CLIC framework served as a foundational guide, though its application varied across the different contexts. We observed that the relevance of the CLIC elements to current stakeholder challenges can vary, indicating a need for flexible integration strategies.

Pictures 1 & 2: Co-design workshops in Amsterdam Noord & Schalkwijk. Source: R. Smolder

Pictures 3 & 4: Discussions over soup & co-design brainstorming in Amsterdam Zuidoost, Source: R. Smolders

Table 1: List of participants in the co-design activities in AMA

ORGANISATION	SECTOR
NEIGHBORHOOD WORKSHOP AMSTERDAM NOORD	
Gezond Noord	Civil society/government
Neighbourhood centres Amsterdam Noord – Municipality of Amsterdam	Government
Boeren voor Buren	Business & entrepreneurs
Noordoogst	Business & entrepreneurs
Stichting Weggeefwinkel	Civil society
Dock	Social work – government/society
Dreamsisters	Civil society

Voor Pek en Bonen	Civil society
Neighbourhood team Amsterdam Noord – Municipality of Amsterdam	Government
Adopteer een Peer	Civil society
Municipality of Amsterdam	Government
Diaconia Amsterdam	Faith based organisation
Helen's Free Food Market	Civil society
Stichting Flora Buurthulp	Civil society
NEIGHBORHOOD WORKSHOP AMSTERDAM ZUIDOOST - 1	
Groenplatform Zuidoost	Civil society
Neighbourhood cooks from Amsterdam Zuidoost	Civil society (12)
Men4BetterLife	Civil society
Green Meal Initiative	Civil society
Boeren voor Buren	Business
Veni Cultura	Civil society
ProFor	Civil society
2Ping	Civil society
Ons Groenteboer	Business
Boeren van Amstel	Business

NEIGHBORHOOD WORKSHOP AMSTERDAMZUIDOOST - 2	
Groenplatform Zuidoost	Civil society
Neighbourhood cooks from Amsterdam Zuidoost	Civil society (18)
Men4BetterLife	Civil society
Green Meal Initiative	Civil society
Municipality of Amsterdam – Team Food Strategy	Government
Mijn Stadsgroenteboer	Farmer – Business & Entrepreneur
Venzo	Civil society
Profor	Civil society
Boeren voor Buren	Business
NEIGHBORHOOD WORKSHOP HAARLEM SCHALKWIJK- 1	
Neighbourhood residents	Civil society
Elan Wonen	Business
Eoring	Civil society
The Non-Waste Project	Civil society
Social entrepreneur	Business
Buurts	Civil society
Appel van Opa	Business
Boeren voor Buren	Business
PUBLIC PROCUREMENT WORKSHOP	
Municipality of Amsterdam (Team Food Strategy)	Government
Municipality of Amsterdam (Circularity)	Government
Municipality of Amsterdam (Health Department)	Government
University of Amsterdam & University of Applied Sciences	Research
Community Wealth Building	Civil Society
Amsterdam Green Business Club	Business
COOPERATIVE FOOD PRODUCTION WORKSHOP	
Vers aan de Vecht	Civil Society
Caring Farmers	Civil Society
Squarewise	Business
ToekomstBoeren	Civil Society
Agro-ecologie Netwerk	Civil Society
Voedselpark Amsterdam	Civil Society
Wageningen University and Research (WUR)	Research

Description of co-design results

All six co-design sessions contributed to the overall aims as a step in an ongoing process. The main accomplishments were identifying willing collaborators in creating transformative change in the city-regional food system and in neighbourhood food environments, as well as building trust and intensifying these relationships. In addition, the sessions helped to align project goals, timelines and theories of change with local goals and ambitions. We found that in the Living Lab of the AMA, this is a balancing act where objectives and ways of working are constantly being negotiated. The first co-design sessions have been key moments in this negotiation and in the communication of (shared) values and objectives.

An additional achievement of the first sessions in Amsterdam Zuidoost was the formulation of a common goal among participating stakeholders and exploring how collaboration between initiatives can be strengthened.

Furthermore, in the collaboration between large employers on the public procurement of catering and banqueting contracts, the co-design session helped to clarify ambitions and associated actions for drafting a covenant. Besides this formal approach, the different stakeholders also discussed how their collaboration in a community of practice can benefit from an action-learning intervention trajectory to overcome persistent barriers and avoid reinventing the wheel.

Lastly, the co-design session on collaborative food production helped to clarify what has already been done and where the added value of the action-learning intervention of FoodCLIC may lie. This includes a non-exhaustive inventory of tools and best practices available to novices or ambitious residents/farmers who want to work more cooperatively and according to agroecological principles.

Lessons Learned

One lesson learned from this process was that the knowledge gained through FoodCLIC mapping & gapping, system understanding, visioning and strategizing is useful to inform the co-design process. However, the duration of the project and the scattered approach, involving numerous stakeholders who may jump on and off throughout stages of the project, also makes it complicated to maintain strong connections with all the parties involved. Consequently, valuable time is spent bringing co-design participants up to speed, which in many cases, particularly involving relatively food deprived and vulnerable groups, is undesirable. Therefore, finding accessible ways to share insights into key findings and to build trust during the co-design workshops is key. Particularly in the situations where trust between inhabitants, initiatives and (government) institutions is limited, which is the case in some of the neighbourhoods in Amsterdam, it is only possible to advance the project work based upon a trusting relationship. Likewise, in the collaboration with agro-ecological

farmers, there is a noticeable need to identify positionalities towards agriculture ahead of the collaboration, because participants want to avoid collaborations with agro-industry.

There are also self-reflective questions emerging in the Living Lab about what exactly is being co-designed – is it both processes and intervention outcomes in the action trajectories? How will these processes take into account democratic decision-making, financial responsibility and local dynamics? These questions continue to be explored in the ongoing co-design activities.

One of the most successful moments of the co-design process occurred during a session in Amsterdam Zuidoost, when we found four common objectives between the participating stakeholders. Clearly, one of these four objectives was the most important. We managed to feed this back to the participants during the session, with the aim of testing whether there was enough support. Having a bottom-up central objective, shared amongst the group, helps in moving forward with planning. Whereas the mixed group of stakeholders in Amsterdam Noord have multiple different objectives and reasons for existence, the main reason why they collaborate is functional. Together, these initiatives stand stronger. However, due to a lack of intrinsic alignment, it turns out that it is much more difficult to come to a concrete set of first steps and actions.

Outlook

Looking ahead, the FoodCLIC project is poised to embark on a critical phase of development in AMA, with the aim of translating the insights gained from the co-design workshops into concrete, actionable plans. In the immediate future, we have scheduled at least four additional co-design sessions across our intervention areas set for spring 2024. These forthcoming workshops represent an opportunity to refine strategies and ensure that we are prepared to move forward with a clear and focused agenda.

The second round of co-design sessions will be focused on the delineation of responsibilities among stakeholders, a process that is essential for the smooth execution of planned activities. Furthermore, we need to narrow down the long list of potential actions to a selection that is both practical and financially feasible. This is particularly pressing for our neighbourhood interventions, where finding a consensus on immediate, actionable steps has proven difficult. Beyond these practical considerations, a fundamental goal remains to identify those interventions that hold the potential to be truly transformative within the context of food system change. Pinpointing and leveraging these transformative elements will require a nuanced understanding of local contexts and a careful balance between aligning with the aspirations of community initiatives and the overarching objectives of the FoodCLIC project. As we advance, our commitment to navigating these challenges reflects our dedication to fostering a sustainable, equitable food system within the Amsterdam Metropolitan Area.

An important obstacle will be the need to work closely together in the interventions with people who are not paid for their time and efforts. Balancing between good will and tangible results to

keep people motivated is key here. Tangible steps planned are drafting an agreement with the municipality of Amsterdam and several yet-to-be-selected large employers to work together towards more sustainable and healthy food provisioning in canteens. By setting up a community of practice for improved catering, we hope to learn from different situations with regard to internal and external challenges.

In the Amsterdam Noord neighbourhood, the next steps include building trust among a larger group of initiatives and finding a physical location for the Food Circle, described below, jointly with the municipality. In Amsterdam Zuidoost, more clarity is needed on what kind of initiatives are already there. The goal is to start organising larger events with the topic of food at the centre. We aim to work towards having a local and informal “food mayor” of Amsterdam Zuidoost who can link the various initiatives.

2.2.2 PORTFOLIO OF REAL-LIFE INTERVENTIONS

The table below provides an overview of the real-life interventions planned during the co-design workshops in the AMA.

INTERVENTION 1 – INFORMAL FOOD CIRCLES IN CITY-DISTRICT AMSTERDAM NOORD	
Level	Neighbourhood
Brief Description	For quite some time now a few food initiatives, informal food banks and local cooks have been meeting up to discuss local developments regarding food aid. During the Covid-19 pandemic, a large group of people found themselves unable to put a meal on the table. These initiatives aim to tackle that, but they are in precarious situations themselves. The goal is to collaborate, find synergies and define the role of municipal support.
Objectives	<p>Overarching objective: Finding ways to collaborate with the aim of improving food security, health and sustainability in the neighbourhood food environment.</p> <p>Sub-goals:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collaboration towards a physical food hub (food circle) • Administrative/organisational stability • Trust between institutions, initiatives, inhabitants and policymakers.

Activities envisaged	
1.	Build common understanding of what a physical space needs to be/offer.
2.	Search for possible physical food hubs.
3.	Shape a structure for trusting collaboration.
4.	Find durable sources of food (via urban-rural linkages).
Responsibilities	<p>Diaconia of the protestant church – Coordinator</p> <p>Food Circle Amsterdam – logistics</p> <p>City District Municipality – facilitation and funding</p> <p>Central Municipality – involvement through food strategy</p> <p>Neighbourhood initiatives providing meals</p> <p>Neighbourhood initiatives providing fresh (redundant) food</p> <p>Civil society organisations (including the Red Cross, Human Aid Now, local neighbourhood organisations)</p> <p>FoodCLIC – initiator of talks on ‘transformation’</p>
Resources	<p>FoodCLIC intervention budget: € 20K</p> <p>Strong trusting relationship between coordinator and initiatives.</p> <p>Strong involvement from local municipality (also financially)</p> <p>Milan food hubs and Shareaty (Rotterdam) act as lighthouse examples.</p> <p>Current regular coalition meeting space is available in the neighbourhood</p>
Monitoring & Evaluation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Figure out and document which initiatives operate where, how and from which sources they get food, how many people they support, where they have been located and how resilient they consider themselves. • Gain insight into the food that is being distributed through these initiatives. • Monitor where the food comes from. • Monitor the food security of people that rely on these initiatives, as well as (where possible) their food literacy. • Monitor the existing network and the collaborations. How can this network improve to secure the collaboration that emerges? • Monitor the accessibility of spaces for the processing and sharing of food in Noord.

Criteria: How does this intervention meet key project and local criteria?	
Engaging food deprived & vulnerable communities	Primarily through informal food banks.
Engaging innovative business models	Potential through engagement with 'Food Circle Amsterdam'
CLIC dimensions	<p>Co-benefits: health, food waste prevention and just access to food</p> <p>Linkages: potential to create through FoodCLIC involvement</p> <p>Inclusion: focus on food security</p> <p>Connectivities: broad involvement of different policy domains, including health, circularity and social security.</p>
Food environments	This intervention trajectory mainly focuses on community food environments, spaces where people cook for neighbours, or redistribute food from various sources. One of the main sources though is the retail food environment.
Alignment with vision/strategic plan	The vision and strategy outlined the need for more spaces to cook, for communities to share food and for urban-rural linkages. All these aspects are aligned with this line of intervention .
Other important information	This line of intervention requires significant involvement of the FoodCLIC Living Lab team. A lot of time is allocated to building trust and developing the collaboration.

INTERVENTION 2 – FOOD COLLABORATIONS IN AMSTERDAM ZUIDOOST

Level	Neighbourhood
Brief Description	In Amsterdam Zuidoost, food brings people together around the table. There are many people who are interested in cooking or gardening together. Food is seen as a means to engage culturally diverse communities. However, in the spatial development plans of Zuidoost (the Masterplan), there is no attention devoted to food. A coalition partly led by the platform for green initiatives in Amsterdam Zuidoost wants to put food higher on the urban agenda and simultaneously develop collaboration between initiatives to show the benefits of growing, cooking and sharing food and to close the health gap between this city district and the rest of the Netherlands.
Objectives	<p>Overarching objective: Access to healthy food for everyone</p> <p>Sub-goals</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improving knowledge on what constitutes a healthy diet.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collaborate on physical space in the neighbourhood for growing, processing, cooking and eating food. • Create a network structure among food initiatives, cultural networks and governmental organisations.
Activities envisaged	
1.	Mapping and inventory of kitchens and gardens in the city-district, including their accessibility.
2.	Engagement of different (including ethnic and faith-based) cultural groups in neighbourhood restaurants.
3.	Setting up a collaboration between all food initiatives in Zuidoost.
4.	Developing a physical infrastructure to redistribute locally grown food into the city-district.
Responsibilities	<p>FoodCLIC: coordination and transformative capacity</p> <p>Municipality of Amsterdam: lead initiator</p> <p>Platform for green initiatives: co-coordinator and network party.</p> <p>Community leaders: involving communities from across Zuidoost, through meet-ups and media.</p> <p>Other organisations: work out concrete actions in one of three working groups.</p>
Resources	<p>FoodCLIC intervention budget: € 20K</p> <p>The platform for green initiatives is a well-networked partner who is intensively involved in the FoodCLIC trajectory.</p> <p>There are connections established with several community leaders for groups that work with undocumented residents.</p>
Monitoring & Evaluation	<p># of kitchens publicly accessible to neighbourhood cooks.</p> <p># of neighbourhood cooks with improved food/health literacy.</p> <p>% of kitchens serving 'healthy' (according to national nutrition guidelines) meals.</p> <p># of citizens with access to locally originated and sustainably produced food through initiatives/# of initiatives providing sustainably produced and locally originated food.</p>
Criteria: How does this intervention meet key project and local criteria?	
Engaging food deprived & vulnerable communities	Yes
CLIC dimensions	<p>Co-benefits: clearly present (sustainability, food literacy, health)</p> <p>Linkages: potential connection to rural sustainable production</p>

	<p>Inclusion: clearly present, we work with groups that normally do not have a loud voice in the debate around food, including undocumented immigrants.</p> <p>Connectivities: need to be strengthened.</p>
Food environments (and digital aspects if applicable)	Agri-food environment, including neighbourhood gardens Community food environments – e.g. Informal retail & hospitality (neighbourhood restaurants).
Alignment with vision/strategic plan	Well-aligned; the vision outlined the need for more community spaces, access to kitchens and more access to green space for food production. This is all part of the process here.
Other important information	Key weaknesses: lack of established contacts with the local department of the municipality.
INTERVENTION 3 – COMMUNITY FOOD INITIATIVES IN HAARLEM SCHALKWIJK	
Level	Neighbourhood
Brief Description	Schalkwijk is a city-district in Haarlem with a variety of challenges. This line of intervention is aimed at empowering the local communities within the neighbourhoods. There are numerous ideas and initiatives for more green and healthier lifestyles, yet so far these initiatives lack in continuity and networking. Within the group of initiatives, there is a call for more healthy food and use of green space for food.
Objectives	Building a trusting community of residents in Haarlem Schalkwijk through food-related neighbourhood initiatives and ‘neighbourhood enterprises’.
Activities envisaged	
1.	Identifying current initiatives and their levels of development.
2.	Co-selection of activities/initiatives that strategically strengthen the neighbourhood ‘glue’ and build a trusting community of residents.
Responsibilities	<p>Haarlem Food Future: Anchoring of activities</p> <p>Social food entrepreneurs: Shaping the line of interventions, based on local experience.</p> <p>Municipality: unclear.</p> <p>Various local food initiatives: share wishes and bring forward ideas.</p> <p>FoodCLIC: facilitate, provide Theory of Change, allocate budget, support monitoring & reflection.</p>

Resources	FoodCLIC intervention budget: € 20K Ties with the local housing association Links with municipality Strong network: Haarlem Food Future
Monitoring & Evaluation	To develop a suitable monitoring and evaluation strategy, we still need to narrow down the actual activities. Directions have been discussed, but monitoring criteria have not yet been identified. This is on the agenda for the 2 nd stage of the co-design.
Criteria: How does this intervention meet key project and local criteria?	
Engaging food deprived & vulnerable communities	We really work together with living in Schalkwijk. By finding ways to link existing initiatives with local residents and by giving them a voice in co-design, this line of interventions includes bottom-up engagement with food-deprived and vulnerable communities.
Engaging innovative business models	The term Wijkbedrijf (neighbourhood business) is inspiration for collaborations to ultimately develop towards a locally supported business both set up and run by local inhabitants.
CLIC dimensions	Co-benefits: health, sustainability Linkages: are not strongly represented at this stage. Inclusion: of deprived and vulnerable communities, migrant communities. Connectivities: connecting domains of space, housing, healthcare may have potential.
Food environments (and digital aspects if applicable)	Community & alternative food environments engaged.
Alignment with vision/strategic plan	Bringing community aspects into all food environments in a neighbourhood. Open and wide accessibility of food in neighbourhoods through public spaces. By working together with the housing corporations, we are seeking ways to improve healthy food access for people in the neighbourhood.
INTERVENTION 4 – SUSTAINABLE PUBLIC PROCUREMENT	
Level	City(-region)
Brief Description	The municipality of Amsterdam has a food strategy which contains 6 lines of action, with the ambition to provide an example of sustainable and healthy food in their own canteens while complying with public procurement legislation. The municipality aims to create more impact by involving semi-public institutions.

	The goal is to draft a covenant and set up a community of practice (CoP) for large employers within the city, and together find a way to make the catering more sustainable.
Objectives	<p>More plant-based: 70% plant-based offerings.</p> <p>Less food waste: 50% reduction in 2030 compared to 2015.</p> <p>Healthy food environment: 80% of food offerings to be considered healthy.</p> <p>Sustainable production: 25% of produced food should be sustainable (local, short food chain, seasonal).</p>
Activities envisaged	
1.	Set up a community of practice with large employers to get a better understanding of how they plan to reach these goals with industry partners
2.	Draft a covenant for large employers to sign and set an example
3.	Bring together industry partners to find answers to 'how' they can collaboratively experiment with promising and transformative changes that help them reach their goal addressed in the covenant.
4.	<p>Find ways to integrate the 'community wealth-building' approach into the procurement plans of governmental institutions.</p> <p>Community Wealth-Building is an international approach focused on increasing wealth in local communities, through for example the local procurement of services for anchor institutions, such as universities or hospitals via cooperative community enterprises.</p>
Responsibilities	<p>Municipality of Amsterdam – initiator</p> <p>FoodCLIC – process facilitator and responsible for monitoring</p> <p>University of Amsterdam – Part of CoP</p> <p>University of Applied Sciences – part of CoP</p> <p>Green Business Club – part of CoP</p> <p>Community Wealth Building – Part of CoP</p>
Resources	<p>FoodCLIC intervention budget: € 10K</p> <p>The Food Strategy as our guiding document.</p> <p>A strong willingness from partners.</p> <p>A lot of energy on this topic currently in the AMA.</p>
Monitoring & Evaluation	TBD
Criteria: How does this intervention meet key project and local criteria?	
Engaging food deprived & vulnerable communities	By collaborating with the 'Community Wealth-Building; programme of the municipality, the goal is to set up contacts and contracts

	with local parties in the city-districts and bolster local economies and small entrepreneurs.
Engaging innovative business models	By finding new ways to work together, i.e. collaboration on contracts and working with community wealth-building on a new business model drafted together with catering partners.
CLIC dimensions	Potentially all CLIC dimensions are represented here
Food environments (and digital aspects if applicable)	Institutional food environment
INTERVENTION 5 – COOPERATIVE FOOD PRODUCTION	
Level	City-region
Brief Description	A lack of access to land is a key bottleneck in creating a more sustainable food system in the AMA. Various local parties, often organized as CSAs or through other forms of cooperatives, face difficulties both in finding ways to access land and to create a market for their products. Access to land is a financial, but also a governance issue. In what form or shape can people organise themselves to get access to land? The development of instruments for these questions and a narrative around these issues is key here.
Objectives	Determine the social, financial and ecological value of pioneering food projects in the AMA and have these insights shared with a larger audience.
Activities envisaged	
1.	Storytelling, finding ways to reach a larger audience
2.	Bring together various local stakeholders with more knowledge and experience on the topics of accessing land and building governance structures and setting up a collaborating network.
Responsibilities	Yet to be determined. So far, all parties have shown interest in working together, but discussion of responsibilities is on the agenda for the second co-design session.
Resources	FoodCLIC intervention budget: € 25K Plentiful knowledge on setting up collaborations, CSAs and cooperatives. High motivation of stakeholders to create a better world and will to put in a lot of time and effort.

Monitoring & Evaluation	Still need to narrow down activities to inform monitoring criteria – also on the agenda for the 2 nd co-design workshop.
Criteria: How does this intervention meet key project and local criteria?	
Engaging food deprived & vulnerable communities	Potentially, depending on the direction of the collaboration and the eventual focus.
Engaging innovative business models	The key element of this intervention is finding new governance structures and building feasible business models around community farms.
CLIC dimensions	Linkages: could be made with the three neighbourhood interventions or perhaps with local communities close by.
Food environments (and digital aspects if applicable)	Agri-food, community & alternative food environments
Alignment with vision/strategic plan	Yes, the access to land and a shared responsibility of growing crops were two of the key elements from the visioning process. In addition, the strategic plan supports engagement in producer-oriented interventions in the food system.
Any other criteria developed with co-design partners	Expanding beyond consumer/urban to engage in rural and food producer focus.
Other important information	This trajectory has only surfaced a short time before the first co-design session- subsequent sessions needed to fully shape a strong action-research pathway.

2.3 BARCELONA

2.3.1 SUMMARY OF THE CO-DESIGN PROCESS IN BARCELONA

Background and aims of the co-design workshops

The Living Lab of Barcelona centred the FoodCLIC process in the following neighbourhoods of the city region, the metropolitan area of Barcelona (AMB):

- Fondo, a highly densified neighbourhood and urban area, with low-rent migrant population as a main profile, in Santa Coloma de Gramanet, on the northeast side of the AMB, with very little space for green areas.
- Sant Cosme, a peripheral and underserved neighbourhood on the other side of the AMB with a very low population density and important social needs despite the municipality's efforts to improve the living conditions of its population.

A sustained and committed participatory process had taken place during November 2022 and March 2024 that involved more than 100 key entities and residents interested in the food system transformation in the selected neighbourhoods and in the metropolitan area. Throughout the process, a shared understanding of the needs, main problems and opportunities in the neighbourhoods' food environments was reached, and a consensus on themes and objectives for the interventions and possible lines of action was built, based on the main needs identified in the two neighbourhoods of the project.

The Living Lab Barcelona decided to organise a single co-design workshop that could assemble all the actors involved so far, taking into consideration that during the strategizing workshops complementarities and possible synergies between the interventions co-created in the two neighbourhoods and at the metropolitan level were identified.

Scene setting and planning

The co-design workshop took place in a single session on 22nd March 2024 from 9:45 to 14:00, at a civic public venue in the centre of Barcelona.

The Living Lab had sent invitations targeting entities and inhabitants working at neighbourhood, municipal, and metropolitan levels, including information about previous and future actions and a detailed document summarizing previous results.

The specific aims of the co-design workshop were:

- Moving forward with the conceptualisation of systemic interventions and policies based on the results of the planning workshops that took place in the neighbourhoods of Sant Cosme, Fondo, and at the metropolitan level;
- Creating collaboration among actors from different neighbourhoods and at the metropolitan level who want to promote similar interventions, to enhance their cooperation and networking sharing capacities, resources, and successful strategies;
- Explaining how the four interventions which use the resources of the FoodCLIC project would be selected, based on the prioritized interventions;
- Prioritizing interventions and policies with participants;
- Fostering synergies and collaborative work among actors from different neighbourhoods and at the metropolitan level who want to implement similar interventions, to enhance their cooperation and the sharing of capacities, resources, and successful strategies.

Photo: L.Bosch

Photo: edomete

Photo: L.Bosch

Photo: L.Bosch

Co-design methodologies

To implement integration of approaches and stakeholders from different sectors, we made great efforts to facilitate participation of the different actors, with a special focus on the active involvement of individuals in situations of vulnerability, but also of the different departments of the city council and organizations that could both support and benefit from the process.

By creating the Living Lab of Barcelona, we also created a central body that encouraged cooperation and provided ways to influence decision-making processes. We also planned some policy dialogues within FoodCLIC and CLEVERFOOD, another EU-funded project, to provide ways to influence decision making within the local governments and at other geographical scales. Academic experts were also involved, helping to identify how other cities had tackled similar problems. The process was designed to invite diverse stakeholders into the design of the policies, and they were informed that they were also welcome to support the implementation, evaluation and monitoring.

We were very careful in collecting, integrating, processing, informing, and validating the contributions of the different actors at each phase of the process, providing transparency and visibility to the different steps we were taking, to facilitate the groundwork and highlight a gradual and collective community-building process, in which all parties feel fully integrated. As a result, we jointly co-designed common definitions, goals and processes.

Similar food needs in neighbourhoods with very different situations and characteristics were identified, so the LL team chose to facilitate the cooperation and co-design between actors in different neighbourhoods and at different scales throughout the definition of the interventions and policies to transform these realities.

In methodological terms, we planned the co-design workshop following the guide proposed from WP1 ("Guidelines for co-designing real-life interventions"), with the necessary adaptations, and the following structure:

- "Teams and second conceptualization": Setting up participants' teams by objectives to present and modify the first conceptualization of interventions carried out during the strategizing phase. In this part of the workshop, participants validated and readjusted the former teams, interventions and actions that had been defined in the strategizing workshops.
- "Teams adjustment": If needed, and according to their own interests, participants were invited to move to another team to join another intervention.
- "Pollination phase": In this step, participants moved to other tables to learn from other proposals. They gathered ideas and generated possible connections between the different interventions.
- "Third conceptualization": Using an adaptation from the RLI template proposed in the guideline, teams completed the intervention template by defining the basic aspects of the 5Ws (who and with whom, what, when, how, etc.) and justifying how it fulfilled the FoodCLIC criteria.

- Presenting the proposed interventions, prioritisation, call to action and presentation of the next steps.

In the workshop, we brought together 39 participants from organizations in the two selected neighbourhoods (Sant Cosme and Fondo) and at the regional level. Participants were allocated to different tables to form five teams based on the themes/objectives prioritized in previous workshops (Education, Production, Right to food and justice, Food accessibility, Community facilities). The session generated an intense and substantive process of exchange and co-creation of interventions that could be implemented among different actors.

Before the workshop, we had conducted various visits and meetings with actors from territories who had difficulties to participate in the workshop. We engaged with residents, social entities, municipal departments or administrations, important actors in the territory not yet included in FoodCLIC. In all cases, they had shown interest in the work we were doing within FoodCLIC and had asked us to maintain communication about the project. They had also expressed their willingness to collaborate in some of the interventions.

Table 1: List of participants in the co-design workshop in Barcelona

ORGANISATION	SECTOR
CITY-REGION WORKSHOPS	
Associació cultural i gastronòmica Manjaretti (Food and cooking association)	Civil society
Cuina Comunitària Sant Antoni (Community kitchen association)	Civil society
Keras Buti (consumer group and community food cooperative)	Civil society
Antígona (Food and cooking association)	Civil society
Via Campesina Europe (international social movement of peasants, farm workers, fisher people)	Civil society
EcoRegió – Fundació Ferrer Sustainability (production & social integration foundation)	Social business
La Fàbrica Sccl (Social innovation cooperative)	Social business
La Fundició (production & social integration cooperative)	Social business
sObres Mestres (Catering)	Social business
Conreu Sereny SCCL (Farmer’s coop)	Social business
AMB - Servei de Polítiques Socials i d'Identitat (Food aid programmes from the Metropolitan Area of Barcelona)	Government
AMB – Pla de Desenvolupament Urbanístic (Urban planning from the Metropolitan Area of Barcelona)	Government
ASPCAT (Health services from the Government of Catalonia)	Government
Universidad HafenCity (University in Hamburg)	Research/education

Centre for Agro-food Economics and Development (CREDA)	Research/education
Agricultural Coop	Business
Institute of Agrifood Research and Technology (IRTA)	Research/education (2)
Institute for Advanced Architecture of Catalonia (IAAC)	Research/education
Catalan Institute of Oncology (ICO)	Research/education
Gasol Foundation (health foundation)	Research/education
Institut Metròpoli (research centre)	Research/education
NEIGHBORHOOD: SANT COSME	
Associació Manjaretti (Food and cooking association)	Civil society
Cuina Comunitària Sant Antoni (Community kitchen association)	Civil society
Keras Buti (consumer group and community food cooperative)	Civil society
Antígona (Food and cooking association)	Civil society
La Casa dels Futurs (Activist & community organization for climate justice and food sovereignty)	Civil society
Agricultura pel Territori (Agroecological Farmers' association)	Civil society
Espigoladors (Social enterprise working in Food waste)	Social business
La Botiga (Food aid supermarket)	Social business
Institut Català de la Salut: Centre de Sant Cosme (health service)	Government
NEIGHBORHOOD: FONDO	
Associació Coordinadora d'Ajuda Unida (ACAU) (Community support association)	Civil society
Ajuntament Santa Coloma de Gramenet (Social service)	Government
Ajuntament de Santa Coloma de Gramenet (Public health service)	Government
Ajuntament de Santa Coloma de Gramenet (Social programmes)	Government
CAP Santa Coloma de Gramenet Centro (Health service)	Government
CAP RIU NORD RIU SUD (Health service)	Government
CNL L'Heura (Catalan teaching service)	Research/education
Fundació Hospital Esperit Sant	Research/education

Description of Co-Design Results

The energy at the end of the workshop was extremely high, with a lot of satisfaction for the work done, the co-creation results obtained, and the richness of the exchanges and ideas shared in the session. A higher level of involvement and commitment very favourable for the continuation of the process was generated, very stimulating for all parties involved and, specially, for the Living Lab team.

This co-design workshop concluded another big step towards the creation and development of a network of food stakeholders committed to improve the food system globally, but also locally in the neighbourhoods, with special attention to people in situations of social vulnerability.

Five intervention proposals were formulated, following the FoodCLIC criteria, meeting the initial needs of the neighbourhoods/region and being complementary to each other.

Lessons Learned

The diversity of professional and personal backgrounds of the participating actors and the quality of the exchange of perspectives and contributions on the topics discussed were highly valued aspects, as spaces of this kind are not usual.

However, the discontinuity of participants taking part in the different FoodCLIC workshops posed a challenge: the incorporation of new people in each workshop, although it brought enrichment and new ideas, along with the absence of former participants, did also require a reinterpretation of previous proposals and the need to readapt the contents to the available audiences at each moment.

The significant organizational effort which the Living Lab had dedicated to preparing the workshop was an important facilitating factor. Activities had been planned with great attention to the objectives defined, deploying a wide range of elements to ensure all necessary information and resources were available.

We also paid special attention to bringing the information from the previous workshops, to assure that the knowledge generated is always used to improve the next phases and to keep alive the very specific expectations about the networking process and the collective effort we are developing to have a greater impact in the transformation of urban food environments.

Finally, and as usual, but especially with the diversity and plurality of stakeholders in this workshop, the lack of time to delve deeper into the reflexions and intense face-to-face exchange remained a limiting factor. But given the circumstances, the Living Lab in Barcelona considers that the FoodCLIC process, throughout the sequence of the different workshops and results obtained, has been very effective in terms of building a food policy network on a collaborative and trustful basis.

Outlook

Working groups were formed to advance on the interventions. The Barcelona Living Lab will gather these groups to clarify intervention details, set a final plan in 4 action-reflection cycles, with activities, roles, evaluation indicators, and budget, based on simplified systems analysis to enhance actions. A feasibility study on interventions will be conducted with local officials and legal experts. Post-validation, costs will be estimated and FoodCLIC funds allocated to selected interventions for the project's final two years. A public tender will then seek organizations to allocate resources to co-designers and citizens.

During the first cycle of action-reflection, the detailed concretization of the proposals is planned to take place, as well as the bidding for interventions and the selection of the organizations that will coordinate them in each territory. We also need to reach out to stakeholders in the neighbourhood who had not been able to attend the FoodCLIC workshops but whom we believe are essential to join the proposed interventions.

On the other hand, as administrative management and processing times are slow, a 6-month period will be needed to make the financial resources of FoodCLIC available to the actors who will carry out the interventions in each case. During this period, we will also need to get approval from an ethics committee for some of the actions.

In parallel, the Living Lab for Health at IrsiCaixa will assure fruitful collaboration with other EU funded projects such as Foster or CleverFood, that we believe could complement and strengthen the FoodCLIC interventions. The overall ambition is to achieve systemic interventions that are sustainable beyond the duration of the FoodCLIC project.

2.3.2 PORTFOLIO OF REAL-LIFE INTERVENTIONS

The table below provides an overview of the real-life interventions planned during the co-design workshops carried out by the Living Lab of Barcelona:

INTERVENTION 1 – NOURISHING LINKS	
Level	Regional (to be implemented in Fondo and Sant Cosme)
Brief Description	Nourishing links, a community-based proposal for food literacy and inclusion of residents living in vulnerable situations
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creating learning environments leveraging community ties. • Promoting healthy habits while considering socio-economic and cultural diversity. • Networking and collaboration.

Activities envisaged	
1.	Diagnosis of the neighbourhood: needs assessment for each neighbourhood and community within the neighbourhood (first evaluation of dietary practices as well as knowledge and attitudes related to it)
2.	Detailed mapping of offers and demands within each neighbourhood
3.	Identification of community leaders that will be empowered to act as trainers and will help as well with the engagement of inhabitants and the dissemination of the activities
4.	Co-definition of learning needs and activities and validation
5.	Practical community food literacy pilots within the neighbourhood facilities: first, the educational activities will be piloted with community groups that use neighbourhood facilities such as civic centres, schools, etc. In a second piloting phase, educational activities will be implemented as well in other relational spaces such as shops, restaurants, etc.
6.	Monitoring of the effectiveness of the activities
7.	Re-definition of the activities based on the monitoring
Responsibilities	Organisations: ICS/CNL/City councils/FHES/Associació Manjareti/Antigona Other organisations: Education Department/La Ciba/Fundació Germina/Casal d'infants/Biblioteca de Fondo/Rellotge 21/Creu Roja/UB-Torribera/GISC/Espigoladors/Comunalitat Benviure/AFAs/Community leaders/Market gardens, others
Resources	TBD
Monitoring & Evaluation	TBD
Criteria: How does this intervention meet key project and local criteria?	
Engaging food deprived & vulnerable communities	Participatory process that is based on their needs. Multicultural approach
Engaging innovative business models	New public procurement and school canteens' management model (considered a novelty in the national public procurement landscape)

CLIC dimensions	<p>Co-benefits: Food literacy can help to adopt a better way to consume food in a more responsible way, better for people and the planet</p> <p>Linkages: the initiative will include theoretical-practical learning and visits to agricultural land, as well as consumption of seasonal products</p> <p>Inclusion: identification of needs from different ethnic groups and co-creation of learning activities with them</p> <p>Connectivities: implementation of the learning activities taking into account social cohesion</p>
Food environments (and digital aspects if applicable)	Local commerce, local restaurants, community & public centres, agrifood.
Alignment with vision/strategic plan	The activity addresses a need for social cohesion and integration in both neighbourhoods through community empowerment and aims to improve their capacity of understanding and aims to improve the local/regional food culture through capacity building.

INTERVENTION 2 – FOOD RETAIL WITH A COMMUNITY KITCHEN

Level	Neighbourhood level: Both Fondo and Sant Cosme
Brief Description	Food retail with a community kitchen
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Selling and cooking healthy products at an affordable price. • Demonstrating an economic viability plan. • Involving the community.
Activities envisaged	
1.	Diagnosis and networking with similar projects and existing facilities. Adaptation of a physical space within the neighbourhood. Building a community network around the infrastructure. Technical advice and learning support.
2.	Connect with local and regional producers. Generate demand, organize distribution, and support producers.
3.	Set up the shop with the kitchen and animate participatory activities. Sell or distribute for free.
4.	Communicate and grow the community to different audiences within the neighbourhood. Generate support networks through food-related activities.

Responsibilities	Municipality of Santa Coloma, Gramelmpuls, AMB, Creda, La Fundició, sObres Mestres. Other organisations to invite: Campus Torribera, municipal network of community kitchens and healthy food of Santa Coloma
Resources	TBD
Monitoring & Evaluation	TBD
Criteria: How does this intervention meet key project and local criteria?	
Engaging food deprived & vulnerable communities	They are the actors of the intervention.
Engaging innovative business models	Social community-based benefits, combining with economic sustainability
CLIC dimensions	Co-benefits: Self-sustained community kitchen with fresh product Linkages: Connections with local producers Inclusion: Participation of different stakeholders in its co-design and implementation Connectivities: Different municipal services take part in the process, as well as local organisations
Food environments (and digital aspects if applicable)	Local retail Community kitchens Peri-urban production
Alignment with vision/strategic plan	Link with the following prioritised objectives: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation and work as a network (community action) • Right to food, justice and access to food
Any other criteria developed with co-design partners	Try to reach young students in service-learning activities Intercultural approach
INTERVENTION 3 – COMMUNITARIAN AGROECOLOGY	
Level	Neighbourhood
Brief Description	Soil recovery & community-organised social agroecology project
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Renovation and restoration of agricultural land in El Prat for community management. • Opening access to the countryside and agricultural co-education spaces for migrant women, youth, residents of Sant Cosme, and marginalized groups. • Creation of a diverse core group of users to define needs and steps forward and negotiate with the authorities.

Activities envisaged	
1.	Financial plan and resource gathering. Secure permissions to access land.
2.	Training of the core group. Generating and expanding community bonds. Visits to existing projects and sharing of project/design with future users (dissemination).
3.	Cultivation of the land with community and solidarity events. Popular cooking and sharing harvest activities.
4.	Learning, festival, dissemination and “pollination” (exchange of ideas and experiences).
Responsibilities	TBD
Resources	TBD
Monitoring & Evaluation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase in health and well-being of the participants • Diversification of the people involved in this peri-urban agroecology project • Increased capacity to (re)produce healthy and sustainable foods at an accessible cost • More connections between social and food movements
Criteria: How does this intervention meet key project and local criteria?	
Engaging food deprived & vulnerable communities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased availability and accessibility of healthy food for vulnerable people experiencing food insecurity • Empowerment through land use, social and community self-production activities • Community building and connecting between different communities
Engaging innovative business models	Livelihood models, long-term care and protection of healthy soils that nourish environmental and social justice.
CLIC dimensions	<p>Co-benefits: Self-sufficiency in the economy; Food and climate education</p> <p>Linkages: Food sovereignty; Peri-urban agroecology; Climate change resilience; Urban citizens reconnect with countryside</p> <p>Inclusion: Community leadership from women who are migrated and/or ethnic minorities; Intercultural exchange; Inter-group cohesion</p> <p>Connectivities: creation of jobs for migrated people; regularization of their legal situation; ecosystem services – land and water protection</p>

Food environments (and digital aspects if applicable)	Agri-food, alternative/community & wild food environment.
Alignment with vision/strategic plan	Increase access to healthy food options that generate social justice, e.g. acquisition of residency permits for migrants, social participation, and inter-community empowerment. Nourish social and community leaders who fight for justice across different systems e.g., environment, migration, work, gender, and social services.
Other important information	Municipal food strategy, connected with intervention 4 to have a place-based pilot for new livelihood models of peri-urban agriculture. Support from La Fundicio and Keras Buti to organise a visit to Conuco to see if it is a suitable place to start with.
Other important information	Involves the participation of social and food movements
INTERVENTION 4 – GENERATIONAL RENEWAL OF FARMERS	
Level	City-region
Brief Description	Promote the inclusion of young people in agricultural and livestock jobs through training, support, and mentoring by retirees from the farming community.
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incorporating new workers into the agricultural sector and offering occupational projects to vulnerable populations. • Ensuring the viability of the agricultural sector.
Activities envisaged	
1.	Studying and valuing the ecosystem services that agriculture could potentially offer in the Barcelona Metropolitan Area
2.	Improve the economic performance of agricultural activity in the Metropolitan area through governmental payment for agricultural work that generates lateral ecosystem services such as the prevention of forest fires, the reduction of erosion or resilience to drought.
3.	Offer an advisory service to the population interested in farming in the metropolitan territory, facilitating their access to available resources.
4.	Connect owners of agricultural land with people that could cultivate them.
Responsibilities	TBD
Resources	TBD

Monitoring & Evaluation	TBD
Criteria: How does this intervention meet key project and local criteria?	
Engaging food deprived & vulnerable communities	Offering occupational activity with proper wages
Engaging innovative business models	Payment to farmers for environmental services could be considered a practice already carried out through agricultural subsidies. However, here we talk about associating agricultural and urban processes to guarantee a lively and dynamic landscape.
CLIC dimensions	<p>Co-benefits: social: improving the labour market; environmental: achieving more resilient agricultural territories; economic: redistributing resources in a more effective way.</p> <p>Linkages: facilitating the production and lifestyle of farmers in metropolitan territories.</p> <p>Inclusion: The agricultural population can improve their income, converting urban agriculture into meeting places for knowledge and protection of nature.</p> <p>Connectivities: migration policies, development of economic and enterprises, integration into the labour market, social services.</p>
Food environments (and digital aspects if applicable)	Sustainable agriculture
Alignment with vision/strategic plan	Increase the production of healthy and sustainable food and enhance the territory management levels
Any other criteria developed with co-design partners	None so far.
Other important information	The Urban Master Plan of the Barcelona Metropolitan Area has assessed that the land compatible with agriculture is more than twice than what is currently used. However, these lands are frequently abandoned. The project seeks to promote agriculture by making it more economically attractive for those who (want to) work in this field.

INTERVENTION 5 – FOOD SYSTEM TRANSFORMATION NETWORKING	
Level	Neighbourhood
Brief Description	Engage local communities in food system transformation by empowering them with personalised action plans and support to implement them
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To empower proactive, motivated and literate citizens' communities to engage in food system transformation; • To support the collaboration of the communities within a sustainable network; • Co-create initiatives to access, produce and process healthy and sustainable food with innovative business models.
Activities envisaged	
1.	Benchmarking of different models of community kitchens (e.g. Ca l'isidret, gramaimpuls, cuina comunitària Sant Antoni, cuina comunitària Fundició...)
2.	Build a repository of existing and potential services (educational activities, events, consume groups, etc.; catering and community kitchens in the second phase of the project)
3.	Design a methodological guideline to engage communities to carry out a self-diagnosis and co-design personalized action plans with participatory and systemic approaches
4.	Invitation and presentation of the project
5.	Creation of working groups and implementation of diagnosis and design of action plan
6.	Implementation of action plans
Responsibilities	Fundació Gasol, Ajuntament Santa Coloma- Salut Pública, IRTA, La Fabrica
Resources	TBD
Monitoring & Evaluation	Indicators: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Proactive citizenship • Healthy and sustainable food habits • Communities organised within a network • Social health • Political collaboration • Jobs creation (second phase of the project)

Criteria: How does this intervention meet key project and local criteria?	
Engaging food deprived & vulnerable communities	The target are food-deprived and vulnerable communities.
Engaging innovative business models	The initiatives to promote access, production and processing of healthy and sustainable food will include sustainable business models. This will be part of the second phase of this intervention.
CLIC dimensions	<p>Co-benefits: Sustainability; Social and physical health; Economy: through the innovative business models</p> <p>Linkages: Agreement with local producers</p> <p>Inclusion: of communities living in vulnerable situations as proactive change agents</p> <p>Connections: consumption, economy and commerce, education, sustainability, health, social services, community action</p>
Food environments (and digital aspects if applicable)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Infrastructures for food communities • Retail • Collective restaurants
Alignment with vision/strategic plan	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communities are empowered • Cultural diversity is addressed through personalization • Access to infrastructures, affordable food, information and education • Networking • Recovery of contaminated agricultural land
Any other criteria developed with co-design partners	Collaboration with other interventions: community kitchens, training for community leaders, local production
Other important information	The activity also counts on the Alison platform, a digital space to facilitate the participation of local networks in food system transformation, to reach many more people and improve cooperation between participants. The platform is intended to accommodate multiple users (residents, volunteers, professionals) and experiences. Its functionalities are meant to boost cooperation between citizens and organisations. This platform was first conceptualised within the Fit4Food 2030 project and has been developed with the support of the “la Caixa” Foundation.

2.4 BERLIN

2.4.1 SUMMARY OF THE CO-DESIGN PROCESS IN BERLIN

Background and aims of the co-design workshops

The co-design of interventions was initiated through the Berlin Living Lab, led by the Berlin Food Policy Council (BFPC) and Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin (HUB) as a research partner. Following joint-sensemaking activities on the key barriers to healthy, sustainable and inclusive food environments, two multi-stakeholder workshops were organized during Fall and Winter 2023, first to envision future food systems, and then to consolidate strategic planning and prioritization of pathways for transformation at city-region and neighbourhood level (see FoodCLIC Deliverable 3.1 Report on the co-design of city-regional integrated food strategies).

Based on a mapping and gapping of food environments, food policies and stakeholder networks, two neighbourhoods were identified for co-design of interventions. These neighbourhoods are based in two of Berlin's districts with the highest unemployment and public financial assistance rates, and the shortest average life expectancy (see Senatsverwaltung für Wissenschaft, Gesundheit, Pflege und Gleichstellung (2022): Gesundheits- und Sozialstrukturatlas Berlin). The first neighbourhood, Rollbergkiez, located in the district of Neukölln, is an inner-city hub of urban infrastructure, food retailers, gastronomy, local food initiatives and cultural diversity, but it is at the same time grappling with the challenges of gentrification and competition for urban space. The second neighbourhood, Falkenhagener Feld, is situated on the outskirts of the city in the district of Spandau. This neighbourhood is marked by an ageing population, high-rise housing, proximity to natural landscapes and green spaces, but with relatively long travel distances and lack of diversity of food outlets available in the community.

At the start of the co-design design process, the aim was to produce inclusive real-life intervention proposals which would engage stakeholders on their own terms and in their own shared spaces. A key focus was set on building relationships and collective ownership by aligning with ideas and objectives which emerge from the communities.

Scene setting and planning

The co-design process took place in Berlin over the course of a series of dialogs between January 2024 and March 2024, and posed a core question across different sectors and stakeholder groups: "What are your ideas to improve food in your city and neighbourhood?" By visiting residents and community organisations in neighbourhood spaces (i.e., a town hall fair, a community knitting group, an after-school club, a health collective), the co-design process can be described as

'decentralized' in the sense that it did not follow a traditional workshop format where all stakeholders would be assembled at the same place and time. The methodological details below provide an overview of the three formats of co-design activities conducted at neighbourhood and city-region level, as well as the list of participants and preliminary results.

Co-design methodologies

- **Format 1: Decentralized co-design at community organizations in Rollbergkiez (Neukölln)**

The neighbourhood is characterised by a comparatively large number of local organisations and initiatives, often publicly funded, which aim to improve integration, family welfare and social inclusion. Neighbourhood engagement, self-mobilisation and attendance at project-level is often low, with some exception, e.g. some mother- and/or children-focused and after-school activities as well as a resident group on residential rent and lack of decent housing. Moreover, most of the local groups only reach particular fractions of the neighbourhood or marginalised groups (e.g., people with special needs) from outside the neighbourhood. However, these groups do not generally mix across venues and cultural, social or societal identities. Therefore, the context for neighbourhood participation in the co-design of possible real-life interventions in this area required the design of a methodological process that combined a) ongoing participation within local groups and events, and b) a wrap-up synthesis meeting with core project partners. First, a postcard was designed and printed which was then presented and placed in different community spaces (e.g., after-school club, Arabic culture club, the premises of the local health collective, etc.). The text on the card invited people in the neighbourhood to "post" their ideas in a self-made "ballot box". In total, 67 people responded to the post-card initiative and posted 62 different ideas. In addition, Living Lab representatives attended 6 community meetings organised by local initiatives and engaged in collaborative sit-down discussions with a further two organisations. The culminating synthesis meeting hosted by the Living Lab team invited two representatives of the local community garden, our collaborating organisation for the intervention, to discuss shared goals and the implementation timeline. We reviewed the results of the consultation and designed a process of implementation for a neighbourhood hub ("Lebensmittelpunkt") for sharing, cooking and learning about food.
- **Format 2: Online co-design brainstorm on spatial planning strategies for Falkenhagener Feld (Spandau)**

The co-design workshop on spatial planning held on 21. March 2024 and led by the BFPC followed an open call for participation on the BFPC website, newsletter, LinkedIn, etc., for spatial and urban planning experts and practitioners. The workshop brought together five experts in climate-smart cities, digitalization, urban food mapping and edible green spaces. This session began with a presentation by a BFPC member on the specific food and housing

environments in the Falkenhagener Feld neighbourhood, in particular the structural and urban planning context of this project area. The group then had an open floor to exchange and brainstorm on urban planning approaches, referring to innovative examples of research and actions in other urban areas of Germany, and compiled ideas for activities which could improve spatial access to food in this district. Particular attention was given to the role of retail, public green areas, private garden allotments and travel/walking distances between food infrastructure and residential areas. The exchange informed possible interventions with respect to critical food infrastructure and spatial planning of food environments. No decisions were taken at the meeting, but the meeting unveiled relevant spatial assessments that have been undertaken in the past and opened up new possibilities for collaboration that will be further explored with an urban planning office.

- Format 3: Pre-cursory co-design consultations at city-regional level within the Food Policy Network and the food poverty strategic planning workshop**

Three precursory meetings were instrumental in brainstorming and building commitment for a list of potential interventions at city-regional level; this list was subsequently narrowed down during the co-design phase to suit the context of the two project areas. First, two meetings took place in Fall 2023 in the regular planning cycle of the BFPC with members and working group representatives (one attended by around 10 BFPC activists/volunteers and one included five representatives of social- and consumer-welfare organisations). The agenda items focused on potential interventions in the context of the strategic direction and planned political work. Additionally, the food poverty strategic planning workshop held in January 2024 (see FoodCLIC Deliverable 3.1) included a session for detailed feedback and discussion of the potential indicators for the proposed Berlin food poverty tracker to create a basis for the co-design of real-life interventions.

Images 1 & 2: Co-design with partner in new urban garden in Rollberg Neighbourhood meeting. Source: Julia Behringer

Wie spannend findet Ihr einen gemeinsamen Ort, wo wir Essen teilen?
 ما هو مدى اهتمامك أن يكون هناك مكان مشترك لمشاركة الطعام؟

Hier ist Platz für Eure Ideen. Jede Stimme zählt!
 مساحة لأفكارك هنا. كل صوت يحسب!

Figures 1 & 2: Front and back of the postcard used to generate co-design ideas in the Rollberg neighbourhood: 'Your ideas for a better neighbourhood!' Source: Amna Alhashemi

Figures 3 & 4: Food environment mapping and image of an inactive supermarket in Spandau district, presented to stimulate brainstorming during the urban planning co-design consultation. Source: Saskia Richartz

Table 1: List of participants in the co-design activities in Berlin city-region

ORGANISATION	SECTOR
NEIGHBORHOOD WORKSHOP 1 (FALKENHAGENER FELD, SPANDAU)	
Co-ordinator healthy city network (City of Frankfurt administration)	Government
Bohn & Viljoen Architects	Business/Industry/Research
Creative Climate Cities (economic/planning bureau)	Business/Industry (2)
Switch (urban food project)	Civil Society

NEIGHBORHOOD WORKSHOP 2 (ROLLBERG, NEUKÖLLN)	
Awo Falk Club (social welfare and inclusion organisation)	Civil society (17)
Community fair of the Intercultural Counselling and Meeting Centre	Civil society (open participation +/- 8 ideas contributed)
Women's group of the Arab cultural centre	Civil society (17)
Neighbourhood language circle for learning German	Civil society (3)
Neighbourhood mothers' group	Civil society (12)
After school club	Civil society (10)
Geko community health collective (open ballot box)	Health clinic / civil society collective
PRE-CURSORY MEETINGS	
Extended Berlin Food Policy network with BFPC activists/volunteers from health, school catering, food culture and food transition, Turkish and inclusion organisations	Civil society (10)
Policy round table with social welfare organisations, poverty groups, food banks etc.	Civil society (5)

Description of co-design results

In **neighbourhood 1 (Rollberg, Neukölln)** the Living Lab will be collaborating with the new community garden and neighbourhood organisations to create a multifaceted community food hub ("Lebensmittelpunkt") that serves the diverse food cultures in the community and offers shared cooking space and a collection point for produce from community supported agriculture (CSA) schemes. Suitable spaces, necessary resources and financial contributions will be determined during further negotiations.

In **neighbourhood 2 (Falkenhagener Feld, Spandau)** preliminary intervention planning has been successful in narrowing the scope for the potential interventions. The focus will be on creating a structural and spatial interventions that innovate a new urban planning design to enable shorter distances to access food and to increase the diversity of food options, by one or all of the following interventions: use of green spaces (edible city components) for urban farming or common space food collection; using mobile, market- or veggie-box-like solutions to link local residents to CSA schemes and engage in dialog with the locally based businesses to support and diversify food offers.

The other two lines of real-life interventions proposed are based on convening a political round table and piloting the Berlin food poverty tracker survey. Both are directed at the city-level and are meant to work synergistically to increase political and public awareness to food poverty and to provide evidence on the complex factors and barriers in the food environment.

Lessons Learned

In the context of the two selected neighbourhoods, elaborate brainstorming and moderation methodologies are not working for multiple reasons, notably the need to cater for different language groups, cultures, age groups and literacy levels. Moreover, people are often reluctant to visit new venues, engage with new stakeholders or access/draw on support, self-empowerment and community spaces. The postcard consultation effectively lowered such barriers to participation, created some enthusiasm and enabled people to take part without leaving their preferred community group. Nonetheless, we observed that a considerable number of people leaned on their respective community leaders to generate, iterate and/or write ideas on the cards, apparently largely because of a lack of self-confidence, self-efficiency and literacy.

The city district in Spandau is dominated by high-rise buildings and comparatively spacious/leafy neighbourhoods and correspondingly long distances between residential and commercial areas. In addition, residents and initiatives criticised a lack of diversity in commercial food environments. Our open call for urban planning expertise aimed to bring forward new perspectives and intervention strategies for spatial and structural solutions. The resulting online meeting was helpful in this respect, but not conclusive. While there is a growing body of expertise in the mapping of food systems, we noted less expertise or experience in applied urban planning for solutions to improve food access and reduce food poverty. We had identified gaps earlier in the process but need additional time to build relationships in the urban planning network and help address this point early enough in the intervention planning.

Outlook

The two interventions at city-region level – a political roundtable on food poverty and inclusive food environments and a food poverty tracker (see below) – will be further detailed during spring 2024. The food poverty tracker also requires additional practical considerations and forward planning with respect to the methodology, multi-dimensional food poverty indicators, recruitment and outreach strategy.

The interventions in the Rollberg neighbourhood are more advanced and already have a timeline until autumn 2024 with collaborative partner events and initiatives (e.g. spring garden launch, joint open kitchen event, community cooking). However, an effective resource plan and further investments in creating an effective network of support are still needed.

Lastly, the interventions in the Falkenhagener Feld neighbourhood, which focus on urban planning, require further conceptual elaboration, following the kick-off consultation with experts, as well as continuation of ongoing meetings to reaffirm support from the district administration and local community stakeholders.

2.4.2 PORTFOLIO OF REAL-LIFE INTERVENTIONS

The table below provides an overview of the real-life interventions planned during the co-design workshops in the Living Lab

INTERVENTION 1 – POLITICAL ROUNDTABLE	
Level	City-region
Brief Description	Political roundtable on food poverty and inclusive food environments
Objectives	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Increase political and public awareness of food poverty impacts 2. Secure political support for measures that create inclusive food environments 3. Develop and promote statutory measures and regulatory responses to tackle food poverty and improve/maintain sustainable and healthy food environments 4. Create a political dialog at district, city, and national level to facilitate the uptake of pilot interventions and lessons learned during the project (for instance that food environments are considered as part of the urban/spatial planning and/or that food poverty reporting mechanisms are included in public reporting and considered in the design of measures to reduce food poverty), thereby: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • strengthening the collaborative value of the overall project for relevant stakeholders; • giving a political and public platform to those impacted, to marginalised groups and social-welfare/social-justice groups
Activities envisaged	
1.	Initiate direct political discourse, meetings and political communication with/towards decision-makers
2.	Produce tailored demands/policy recommendations for policy-makers

3.	Organise public media events and communication materials to engage broader audiences, notably to reduce stigma around food poverty, increase awareness and heighten public attention
4.	Create opportunities for relevant stakeholders and representatives from marginalised/deprived communities to take the floor and amplify their voices
Responsibilities	<p>Lead: BFPC</p> <p>Co-ownership/cooperation planned with:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • social welfare organisations (e.g. Arbeiterwohlfahrt and Diakonie), • anti-poverty stakeholders and poverty-relief organisations (e.g. Armutsnetzwerk, Berliner Tafel), • consumer protection, health and food transition organisations (like Verbraucherzentrale Bundesverband)
Resources	This intervention requires a communication budget, staff hours in network coordination and an event and hospitality budget. Overall, however, we expect a lower budget intensity than for the neighbourhood-level interventions.
Monitoring & Evaluation	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Increased political and public awareness of food poverty impacts <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of reports in leading city-region media on the topic 2. Secure political support for measures that create inclusive food environments <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of high-level statements on the topic by the city government (Berlin Senate); • Number of motions on the topic in the City Parliament (Abgeordnetenhaus); • Number of political initiatives at district level (in Neukölln and Spandau) 3. Develop and promote statutory measures and regulatory responses to tackle food poverty and improve/maintain sustainable and healthy food environments <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number and type of measures developed • Number and type of related outreach activities • Eventual uptake of these proposals 4. Create a political dialog at district, city, and national level to facilitate the uptake of pilot interventions and “lessons learned” during the project

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number and type of activities at district, city, and national level • Of these: number and type of activities that give voice to those impacted, to marginalised groups and social-welfare/social-justice groups • Number and type of participants <p>To be further developed in consultation with intervention partners and stakeholders.</p>
Criteria: How does this intervention meet key project and local criteria?	
Engaging food deprived & vulnerable communities	This line of intervention is implemented in cooperation with relevant social-welfare and poverty organisations and will engage individual members of impacted communities when feasible.
Engaging innovative business models	This line of intervention aims to develop and adopt innovative public policy and urban planning solutions (not private business models) and might consider business solutions as part of the portfolio of actions that public institutions may promote or mandate as part of public (or public-private) governance.
CLIC dimensions	The ultimate aim is to trigger policy responses that will consider the co-benefits of sustainable and healthy eating (health, social-welfare and cohesion, social, economic and environmental sustainability), strengthen social inclusion and address the connectivity impacts of multiple sectoral and structural disadvantages and discrimination through coherent governance and decision-making across issue areas (from health policy to urban planning and agriculture policies). The activities will create and strengthen linkages between a broad range of actors.
Food environments (and digital aspects if applicable)	All types of food environments and their connections are considered, with more focus on areas where public governance is most relevant, and thus somewhat less of a focus on hospitality and retail environments.
Alignment with vision/strategic plan	This line of intervention addresses the goal to increase reliable data and political awareness, to lower the stigma associated with food poverty, and to increase the empowerment of marginalised voices.
Any other criteria developed with co-design partners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create or support initiatives or measures that strengthen the right to adequate food and re-establish access to food as a public good.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Test, evaluate or build inclusive concepts for easier access to regional, organic produce. • Reduce the prevalence, advertising and pricing strategy of 'junk' food and sugary drinks.
INTERVENTION 2 – BERLIN FOOD POVERTY TRACKER	
Level	City-region
Brief Description	Piloting a Berlin food poverty tracker for evidence-based policy and advocacy
Objectives	Improve data and first-hand perspectives on food poverty to enable effective political responses and food governance, while contributing tools to decrease stigmatisation, exclusion and improve public sentiment
Activities envisaged	
1.	Develop a research design for a replicable annual food poverty survey based on participatory feedback and input from stakeholders
2.	Questionnaire-based data collection and purposeful interaction/communication with marginalised groups to produce baseline and endline data during the project lifetime
3.	Analysis report and research publication
4.	Produce communication material on data and lessons learned (i.e., infographics) for political audiences, for the general public and media
Responsibilities	Lead: HUB Consultation with <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • other academics (e.g. in the FoodBerlin research network), • consumer and citizen initiatives, • local government, i.e., social welfare and health statistics department
Resources	This intervention requires a sufficient research budget to ensure an effective sampling and surveying strategy to enable underrepresented groups in society to take part in the survey and to reach adequate coverage of the two project target areas.
Monitoring & Evaluation	Indicators of success: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Food tracker concept developed in consultation with relevant stakeholders

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Baseline survey conducted • Follow-up survey conducted • Public dissemination of results (e.g. infographics) • Scientific dissemination of results (e.g. scientific presentations, publications) • Uptake in public debates (e.g. media coverage) • Uptake in policy initiatives (e.g., citation in government documents or parliamentary motions) <p>To be further developed in consultation with intervention partners and stakeholders.</p>
Criteria: How does this intervention meet key project and local criteria?	
Engaging food deprived & vulnerable communities	Purposeful communication and interaction with members of marginalised groups and social welfare groups to improve data and include the experience and perspectives of deprived and vulnerable members of the community
CLIC dimensions	<p>While the immediate focus is on generating better data on social and food poverty indices, the ultimate aim is to trigger a policy response that will consider the co-benefits of reducing food poverty and promoting sustainable and healthy eating. Similarly, the intervention will focus on food intake and barriers to food justice, conscious of the fact that there are connectivity impacts of multiple sectoral and structural disadvantages and discrimination, correlating with: impoverished, unfit or unhealthy living conditions; unfit and underfunded neighbourhood infrastructure and facilities; missing access to welfare; impacts of exclusion, racism and stigmatisation; etc.</p> <p>This intervention does not address urban-rural linkages. While it is pursued in collaboration with researchers, physicians and social welfare/justice partners, it is not inclusive of and not relevant to all food system actors.</p>
Food environments (and digital aspects if applicable)	The intervention focuses on consumption patterns and factors influencing food choices and food experiences. It acknowledges the impact of all food environments.
Alignment with vision/strategic plan	Aims to address knowledge gaps, stigmatisation and political inaction.

Any other criteria developed with co-design partners	The intervention reframes public discourse to destigmatise food poverty and to make food environments visible and raises knowledge and awareness on barriers to the right to food.
INTERVENTION 3 – INTERCULTURAL FOOD HUB	
Level	Neighbourhood
Brief Description	Creating an intercultural neighbourhood food hub linked to the community garden (Rollberg Kiez, Neukölln District)
Objectives	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Create a community space and programme to cook, process, share and learn about food and food growing 2. Strengthen the link to community supported agriculture and regional fruit and vegetable producers
Activities envisaged	
1.	Ongoing programme of community events around the issue of food, including community cooking and soup kitchen for all
2.	Activities to increase participation and ownership in community garden and food hub planning amongst local Arab and Turkish communities
3.	Assist community office (Quartiersmanagement) in securing medium term viability of the space
Responsibilities	<p>Lead: BFPC lead</p> <p>Co-ownership/cooperation with</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prinzessinnengarten, • Netzwerk der Lebensmittelpunkte • and other local stakeholders
Resources	<p>This intervention requires a budget for</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • a community organiser/facilitator; • food, material and event planning; • a modest communication, design and translation budget.
Monitoring & Evaluation	<p>Create a community space and programme to cook, process, share and learn about food and food growing</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number and type of spaces created • Number and types of programme activities • Number and diversity of participants • Participant feedback <p>Strengthen the link to community supported agriculture and regional fruit and vegetable producer</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number and types of activities involving CSA and regional food and vegetable producers • Number and types of lasting links created • Number of participants • Participant feedback <p>To be further developed in consultation with intervention partners and stakeholders.</p>
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Criteria: How does this intervention meet key project and local criteria?

Engaging food deprived & vulnerable communities	The intervention will be based in a location characterized by a prevalence of socio-economic and health hardship indicators.
Engaging innovative business models	Cooperation with CSA, possibly in combination with food sharing and a solidarity pricing model.
CLIC dimensions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Co-benefits: creation of green spaces, outdoor activities and plant-based food; • Inclusion of marginalized groups that so far have little access to community supported agriculture and regional food producers; • Strengthening spatial linkages and connectivities between an inner-urban neighbourhood and rural producers
Food environments (and digital aspects if applicable)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Community food environments: community space and programme • Agri-food environments: Community supported agriculture and links to regional food and vegetable producers
Alignment with vision/strategic plan	This line of intervention contributes to addressing the urgent need to increase the availability and affordability of local and regional fruit, vegetables and plant-based proteins and to test, evaluate or build inclusive concepts for easier access to regional, organic produce.

INTERVENTION 4 – FOOD-RELATED URBAN PLANNING

Level	Neighbourhood
Brief Description	Urban planning intervention to shorten the distances and increase the diversity of food options in Falkenhagener Feld, Spandau district
Objectives	To contribute to diversifying and increasing the proximity of affordable food environments in Falkenhagener Feld in participation with residents and local businesses
Activities envisaged	
1.	Commission an urban planning concept to validate options

2.	Engage local businesses in dialog to test expansion of fresh goods and services
3.	Potentially create links to edible and green spaces in the neighbourhood
Responsibilities	Lead: BFPC, in consultation with <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • district administration, • Quartiers management, • local food coach programme • and social housing organisations.
Resources	Consultancy budget Budget for project pilot Budget for events
Monitoring & Evaluation	Diversifying and increasing the proximity of affordable food environments in participation with residents and local businesses <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number and types of businesses participating in dialog and tests to expand fresh goods and services • Participant feedback (businesses, customers, citizens) • Lasting effects To be further developed in consultation with intervention partners and stakeholders.
Criteria: How does this intervention meet key project and local criteria?	
Engaging food deprived & vulnerable communities	Based in a location marked by a prevalence of socio-economic and health hardship indicators
Engaging innovative business models	To be determined in further consultation meetings with intervention partners and stakeholders including local businesses
CLIC dimensions	Co-benefits: creation of more diverse and healthy food options and relating health benefits Social inclusion and connectivity in the context of different policy and urban planning processes Linkages: potential to create more linkages between urban retailers and regional producers
Food environments (and digital aspects if app.)	Retail or institutional food environments, as well as agri-food and community environments
Alignment with vision/strategic plan	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase the availability and affordability of regional fruit, vegetables and plant-based proteins. • Create or support initiatives or measures that strengthen the right to adequate food and re-establish access to food as a public good.

2.5 BRASOV

2.5.1 SUMMARY OF THE CO-DESIGN PROCESS IN BRASOV

Photo: Andrei Paul

Fig. 1. Participants in the FoodCLIC Living Lab in Brasov

Background and aims of the co-design workshops

The co-design process in Brasov built upon the priority themes for the city-regional food system: enhancing **food security** and improving the **rural-urban connection**. These themes include key concerns such as lack of education in nutrition and health, lack of political programs with an agri-food system focus, and encroachment of the city into the rural hinterland without a common strategy. The themes and concerns were established in visioning and strategizing activities that took place as part of the FoodCLIC project in Brasov in winter 2023.

Various actions have been subsequently identified to address these big strategic themes, such as

- increasing the public budgetary amounts allocated for social services;
- organizing farmers' markets with local producers in deprived neighbourhoods;
- organizing stalls with local products in urban agri-food markets;
- dissemination of information related to nutrition and health in schools;
- the development of a special chapter on the food system in the development strategy of the Braşov Metropolitan area and
- the adaptation of a food-sensitive urban development plan to manage the real estate expansion towards the peri-urban and rural areas.

As highlighted in previous analyses related to mapping and gapping of key food stakeholders at the city-regional and neighbourhood levels (details in FoodCLIC Deliverable 2.3), the food system in Braşov has not previously benefitted from the type of systemic approach by means of a food policy network (FPN) that would include all actors of the food system. The transition from the food system organized by the state during communism to the current situation was realized in an evolutionary, spontaneous way, with the intervention of the authorities mostly limited to crisis situations or in moments preceding some socio-cultural events (Easter, Christmas, etc.).

Scene setting and planning

The co-design process involved three workshops: one focusing on the city-region and two focussing on two selected neighbourhoods: Noua and Bartolomeu Nord. The workshops in the two neighbourhoods used the headquarters of the secondary schools in these locations. Representatives from the quadruple helix (administration, civil society, private sector and science) from the local and central level were invited.

The two neighbourhoods were identified through the mapping and gapping as potential areas for interventions due to post-industrial transitions that have created hardships as well as opportunities to improve their food environments.

The **Noua neighbourhood**, which is located on the south side of Braşov city, was mainly built during the communist era and populated with people who worked in the large industrial platform "Autocamioane Braşov". The company reduced its activity after the 1990s, shrinking from 15,000 employees to around 500 today. Resulting unemployment and the lack of adaptation to the new realities of Romanian society have created a social structure characterized by high unemployment, an ageing population and low birth rate. A general analysis of food supply sources from the FoodCLIC mapping and gapping shows that there is a greater number of specialized stores, but the lack of an agri-food market with fresh fruits and vegetables is one of the main needs of the citizens.

The **Bartolomeu Nord neighbourhood** is located on the North side of Braşov city and its residents are part of a group of citizens who were involved before 1990 in the activity of some companies that currently no longer exist or have reduced their activity (Ghimbav Airplane Factory, SRL Codlea, Institute for Research and Development for Potato and Sugar Beet, etc.). The average age is around 60 and many citizens are unemployed, receive social assistance or have very low pensions. Of the 3 grocery stores that have operated in the Western area of the Bartolomeu Nord neighbourhood (Fundaturii Street) in recent years, only one is currently operating, which supplies the cheapest food products of an inferior quality and with a narrow spectrum of vegetables and fruits. Instead, canned foods with a long shelf life and a poor nutritional structure predominate.

Fig. 2. Bartolomeu Nord neighbourhood workshop, secondary School no. 9

Co-design methodologies

All three workshops – one each focusing on the city-region and each of the two neighbourhoods – aimed at the identification of actors, resources and the possibilities of monitoring and evaluation of the necessary actions to be taken within the food system according to the vision and strategy previously established.

Attendees of the Noua and Bratolomeu Nord neighbourhood workshops received educational materials printed in the form of brochures and leaflets, totalling about 50 pages. 500 copies of these materials were distributed free of charge to teachers, students and consumers. Furthermore, 140 food packages from local producers (apples, apple juice, sandwiches) were distributed, as well as 140 food boxes with the FoodCLIC logo and 140 expandable plastic cups and puzzles on the theme of proper nutrition. The dissemination of physical copies of information was carried out in both schools. The information was also provided in electronic format on USB sticks for the teachers, together with a diary, pen and personalized bags with the FoodCLIC logo.

The brochure entitled “healthy eating guide” had been created by specialists from the Faculty of Food and Tourism and the Faculty of Medicine. The brochures and leaflets were distributed as an element of co-interest and the creation of a discussion framework about the nutritional habits of the families in the neighbourhoods under study. Starting from these discussions about improved diets, the availability of healthy foods in the vicinity of the neighbourhoods was evaluated, and different solutions were proposed that were taken into consideration by the city hall representatives.

The co-design workshops started with a presentation of the vision and development strategy of the agri-food system, the results of the previous FoodCLIC events (see FoodCLIC Deliverable 3.1). This was followed by discussion and identification of individual actions, local specificities at neighbourhood level, possible resources, responsible persons and implementation deadlines. Open discussions were moderated by representatives of the city hall and the university, as this was determined to be the most effective method for stimulating and collecting valuable information.

Fig. 3. City Food walks in Noua neighbourhood – Selgros Hypermarket (photos: Oprea Oana)

The verification of some elements of the implementation options required the Living Lab to organize complementary **city food walks**. These took place in both neighbourhoods after finishing the workshop activities, with emphasis on stores such as hypermarkets, supermarkets and small vegetable and fruit markets available to the citizens of the two neighbourhoods. 10-12 representatives from all categories of the quadruple helix participated, namely government (Brasov city hall), education (Faculty of Food and Tourism), business (Catean Farm and Selgros Supermarket) and civil society (consumers).

Fig. 4. Co-Design workshop at city level

Fig. 5. Co-Design workshop Noua neighbourhood

Fig.6. City Food walk at Research Institute (Bartolomeu Nord)

Fig. 7. City Food Walk at retirement home (Noua)

In the Noua neighbourhood, participants visited the Penny Supermarket (on Prunului str. 3A), which is the most reachable for local residents, and the Selgros Hypermarket (on Calea Bucuresti str. no.

231), which is located for customers with a car. In Selgros, we talked with consumers, who expressed their thanks and needs, and with those in production, especially small farmers, who were allowed access into the store in order to sell their own products (fig. 2). In the Noua neighbourhood, also the centre for the elderly (on Gladiolelor str. no. 4) was visited (see Fig. 7), where aspects related to the residents' food as well as their needs and grievances were discussed. With the management of the unit, future methods of improving menus through collaboration with a nutritionist from Transilvania University were discussed, as well as possible ways to increase food funds.

In the Bartolomeu Nord district, the walk included Agro Stupini wholesale market (on Calea Feldioarei Street no. 75C), which is occupied by wholesale traders who sell products only in large quantities, not being accessible to the average consumer. At the Carrefour Express store (on Dimitrie Anghel str. no. 20), which is of small size, we talked to consumers who said that they generally avoided this store because of its higher prices compared to ordinary markets. The Food Walk also included a small neighbourhood store (on Fundaturii str.) in which the product range was very limited.

Finally, wrap-up discussions to draw conclusions after the 3 co-design workshops and 2 city food walks were held at the research and development centre of Transilvania University (see Fig. 6s), which is also located in the Bartolomeu Nord neighbourhood. Members of the Braşov LL, which combines government, education and research representatives, joined to analyse the results and put together the initial proposal for RLIs in the city-region and target neighbourhoods.

Table 1: List of participants in the co-design activities in Brasov city-region

ORGANISATION	SECTOR
CITY-REGION WORKSHOP	
Veterinary health and food safety department	Governance (1)
Directorate of Social Assistance	Governance (1)
Braşov Prefecture	Governance (1)
Brasov City Hall – different departments	Governance (17)
Public Health Department	Governance (1)
Brasov Market Service Administration	Governance (2)
County Directorate of Statistics	Governance (1)
Payments and Intervention Agency for Agriculture	Governance (1)
Romanian Society for Ethnopharmacology	Civil Society (1)
Local consumers	Civil Society (9)
Tenants Association representative	Civil Society (1)

HighClere Consulting	Civil Society (1)
Transilvania University of Brasov	Education and Research (6)
Local producers/farmers	Business (2)
NOUA NEIGHBORHOOD WORKSHOP	
Brasov City Hall	Governance (3)
Home for the elderly	Governance (1)
Romanian Society for Ethnopharmacology	Civil Society (1)
Transilvania University of Brasov	Education and Research (6)
School No. 9 “Nicolae Orghidan” teachers	Education and Research (18)
Selgros	Business (2)
BARTOLOMEU NEIGHBOURHOOD WORKSHOP	
Brasov City Hall	Governance (3)
Romanian Society for Ethnopharmacology	Civil Society (1)
Local citizens/consumers	Civil Society (25)
Transilvania University of Brasov	Education and Research (5)
School No. 14 teachers	Education and Research (46)
Carrefour market	Business (1)

Description of Co-Design Results

In the **Noua neighbourhood**, the lack of a nearby agro-food market causes citizens to stock up from supermarkets such as Penny, Carrefour, Selgros, etc. with food from long value chains. The visit to the home for the elderly in the Noua neighbourhood allowed the study of the daily menu of 4.5 euros/day/person and identified the needs to increase the daily food allowance, as well as the need for nutritional education of those hospitalized. Interaction with consumers, teachers and students of secondary school no. 9 also highlighted deficiencies in nutritional education and the lack of information regarding the impact of nutrition on health.

In the **Bartolomeu neighbourhood**, the lack of an agri-food market in the neighbourhood is felt especially by the elderly citizens, since the youngest have their own gardens and can practice a limited form of subsistence agriculture. The management of school no. 14 declared their willingness to implement an educational greenhouse as a pilot project and model for other schools in the Municipality of Braşov. A better awareness of the importance of adequate nutrition was noted, as well as an openness to educational actions on this topic.

The **Braşov city-region level** workshop was honoured with the presence of key actors from the governance area, which helped to find resources and identify those responsible for the actions to be implemented. All RLIs were established by common agreement, with the specification that approvals from higher levels are still required.

Lessons Learned

On reflection, four factors are of particular importance for the further development of the FoodCLIC LL in Brasov:

- The integration of actors from different backgrounds in the form of the FoodCLIC LL has energized the actors of the entire food system, enabling them to understand specific problems through the lens of all CLIC components.
- Generally, the lack of education in the nutritional field was found as a determining factor in the current state of the agri-food system, characterized by a low demand for fresh vegetables and fruits from short food chains.
- During the co-design processes it was interesting to note that the personal involvement of some key characters was a decisive element to ensure success. The recognition of the importance of the nutrition-health effect by the meeting participants was the starting point in motivating the need to change the local agri-food system.
- The electoral processes from June-September 2024 were identified as a factor of uncertainty in decision-making. The issue of food inclusion is regulated by a unitary legislation at the national level and for now at the local level no solutions have been identified to supplement the daily food allowance for social assistance.

Outlook

The LL Brasov has identified a comprehensive list of RLIs (see section 2.5.2 below). On this basis, the following steps are foreseen:

- Based on the list of RLIs, meetings will be organized with those responsible for the interventions to develop an action plan, followed by the implementation of the proposed objectives.
- Monthly meetings will be held to monitor the result indicators, and measures will be proposed to improve the ongoing activity.
- Other events are expected in the near future related to nutrition and health, as one of the issues dealt with in the city-region intervention.
- Throughout the duration of the interventions activities in the frame of the FoodCLIC project, there is a high probability of identifying new resources, new actors and new connections

that will support the process of sustainable transformation of the agri-food system in Braşov.

2.5.2 PORTFOLIO OF REAL-LIFE INTERVENTIONS

The table below provides an overview of the real-life interventions that have been planned during the co-design workshops in the Brasov Living Lab.

INTERVENTION 1 – EDUCATION IN NUTRITION AND HEALTH	
Level	City-region
Brief Description	The objective of the intervention is the dissemination of correct information regarding the benefits of an adequate diet on health, as well as the risks of the modern diet with low content of fibres, minerals and high content of additives, saturated fats, refined sugars, etc.
Objectives	Increasing awareness about the influence of nutrition on health
Activities envisaged	
1.	<p>Development of educational materials</p> <p>Brochures, monographs – Faculty of Food and Tourism Leaflets – Faculty of Medicine Other promotional materials</p>
2.	<p>Dissemination of information</p> <p>The materials developed in activity 1 will be multiplied and distributed in secondary schools, high schools, but also among consumers (in markets, at the level of tenants' associations, etc.).</p> <p>Special emphasis will be placed on disseminating information in disadvantaged neighbourhoods (Noua neighbourhood – School no. 9 and Bartolomeu Nord neighbourhood – School no. 14. Partnerships have been established with both schools).</p> <p>Other events at which the dissemination of information related to nutrition and health are expected:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 14-15 September 2024 – first steps in research Symposium Faculty of Medicine – Mesota High School; • FSHL Summer School 8-11 May 2024 (Bucharest) – Food safety; • Researchers Night – 30th of September 2024 – Transilvania University of Brasov; • Periodic campaigns at the home for the elderly – healthy lifestyle – senior support NGOs Bucuria Darului & Hospice Casa Sperantei

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Joint campaigns with the County School Inspectorate in schools in the county (“different school week”, “green school week”); joint campaigns with other projects like “School Food for Change”, where Brasov is “replication city” • Connections with the educational measure’s component (Brasov Prefecture, Brasov City Hall, County School Inspectorate) through the national program “Healthy Food in Schools”
3.	<p>Establishment of an educational greenhouse at school no. 14 (Bartolomeu Nord neighbourhood)</p> <p>There is already support from the management of School no. 14 for the establishment of a greenhouse and school gardens with medicinal, aromatic, seasonal and tincture plants, as well as an orchard.</p> <p>The Romanian Society of Ethnopharmacology will provide the necessary knowledge for the establishment of cultures.</p> <p>Including the greenhouse established in the programme “Green School” as model for other schools from Brasov city.</p> <p>The proposed greenhouse will serve a pedagogical purpose, encouraging contact with nature, knowledge of agricultural technologies and promoting the concept of a short food chain. The sensory experiences produced by tasting the vegetables produced in the school’s own garden together with the satisfaction from own small production create the prerequisites for continuing agricultural education at the Prejmer agricultural high school, located in the vicinity.</p>
4.	<p>Educational visits (guided tour of farms, guided tour of hypermarkets). Campaign: nutritional label for everyone to understand</p> <p>There are preliminary agreements with the management of the Selgros supermarket, local farms, and the management of the market administration service</p>
Responsibilities	Transilvania University of Brasov and Brasov City Hall
Resources	Transilvania University of Brasov and Brasov City Hall
Monitoring & Evaluation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No. of educational material pages (December 2024); • Number of nutritional education beneficiaries (500) in 2024, 2025, and 2026; • Number of students actively involved (minimum 50) by end of 2025; • Number of persons involved (target: 200) by 2024 and 2025.

Criteria: How does this intervention meet key project and local criteria?	
Engaging food deprived & vulnerable communities	The elderly home in the Noua neighbourhood, secondary school no. 9 from Noua, and secondary school no. 14 from Bartolomeu Nord, and NGOs take part in this intervention
Engaging innovative business models	Not foreseen
CLIC dimensions	<p>Co-benefits: between nutrition, health and sustainability</p> <p>Linkages: donations in the rural environment by NGOs, education</p> <p>Inclusion: children, adolescents and the elderly in disadvantaged neighbourhoods will be the beneficiaries of the intervention</p> <p>Connectivities: civil society, education, business, governance</p>
Food environments	urban, rural Indirectly all types, in particular retail
Alignment with vision/strategic plan	The intervention is part of the visioning and strategy program developed in previous FoodCLIC workshops, which included the need to address the lack of education regarding the importance of food for health and aligned with the sustainable development strategy of Brasov metropolitan area to support education on healthy food habits. (The main 3 topics addressed during the visioning workshop were related to food security, food quality and the lack of education regarding the importance of food for health. Related to the lack of education in nutrition and health, it was proposed to organize workshops and seminars in the academic and research environment, with guests from the fields of food and medicine.)
Any other criteria developed with co-design partners	None

INTERVENTION 2 – SHORT FOOD VALUE CHAINS

Level	City-region
Brief Description	<p>The intervention aims to promote short food value chains by connecting networks of local producers (e.g. ROMO) with consumers within the agri-food markets.</p> <p>Background: An important issue in the Romanian agri-food markets is the prevalence of resellers of agricultural products from long food value chains (e.g. tomatoes from Turkey or Greece, onions from Spain, etc.).</p> <p>The objective is to connect local farmers with urban consumers by</p>

	increasing consumer trust in local farmers' technologies, as well as local promotion of the small local farmers activity.
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Familiarization of small producers with notions of food safety and traceability. • Knowledge of the activity of small local producers in various environments (online, public transport, etc.). • Improving producer-consumer connectivity
Activities envisaged	
1.	<p>Creation and dissemination of food safety and traceability guides</p> <p>Together with the veterinary health and food safety department, good practice guides for producers will be created and multiplied and will be disseminated periodically.</p>
2.	<p>Actions to promote local producers through various media</p> <p>Announcements in public transport buses for customers Free web pages for FPN producers (admin support from Transilvania University masters students – web host organization TBD).</p>
3.	<p>Development of an online platform model with all local producers (presentation + pre-orders + delivery)</p> <p>Preliminary collaboration agreement with the market administration service for a common producer-consumer platform</p>
4.	<p>Proposal for the purchase of a mobile laboratory for the control of food safety factors in urban markets</p> <p>Mixed working group (city hall, prefecture, university, DSVSA - veterinary health and food safety department) defines the feasibility of the self-laboratory project for the detection of pesticides, heavy metals, mycotoxins, etc.</p>
Responsibilities	Transilvania University of Brasov and Brasov City Hall
Resources	Transilvania University of Brasov and Brasov City Hall
Monitoring & Evaluation	
Criteria: How does this intervention meet key project and local criteria?	
Engaging food deprived & vulnerable communities	Markets will act as food hubs and meetings organized in vulnerable neighbourhoods.
CLIC dimensions	<p>Co-benefits: health, sustainability, and income benefits</p> <p>Linkages: rural-urban in the city-region</p>

	<p>Inclusion: new market access for small local producers</p> <p>Connectivities: aligned with food strategy vision developed by the FPN</p>
Food environments (and digital aspects if applicable)	Retail
Alignment with vision/strategic plan	The intervention is part of the visioning and strategy program developed in task 3.2.
Any other criteria developed with co-design partners	
INTERVENTION 3 – URBAN AGRIFOOD MARKET	
Level	City-region
Brief Description	The aim of the intervention is to streamline and intensify the activity of urban agri-food markets.
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Connecting disadvantaged neighbourhoods with agri-food markets. • Complete consumer information in the environment represented by the agri-food market
Activities envisaged	
1.	Organizing of flywheel markets with local products, especially in disadvantaged neighbourhoods (Noua and Bartolomeu Nord neighbourhoods)
2.	<p>Marking with differently coloured stalls where products from the local mountain farms are sold</p> <p>Green stalls for local mountain food products Yellow stalls for local producers Blue stalls for resellers</p>
3.	<p>Optimizing RATBV (Brasov Public Transport Operator) routes for citizens' access to existing markets</p> <p>The initiative to change bus routes on the Bartolomeu Nord route and the Dacia route</p>
4.	The initiative to request the location of a market in the Bartolomeu Nord area to the Department of Urban Planning
Responsibilities	Transilvania University of Brasov and Brasov City Hall
Resources	Transilvania University of Brasov and Brasov City Hall
Monitoring & Evaluation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No. of flywheel markets (December 2025); • No. of stalls (target: 20) in 2024, 2025, and 2026;

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No. of beneficiary consumers (minimum 500) by end of 2025; Draft application – by end of 2025.
Criteria: How does this intervention meet key project and local criteria?	
Engaging food deprived & vulnerable communities	Involve small regional producers and citizen-consumers in deprived neighbourhoods in the development of the urban agrifood market
Engaging innovative business models	The aim is to stimulate the development of local food value chains.
CLIC dimensions	<p>Co-benefits: health, sustainability, and income benefits</p> <p>Linkages: rural-urban in the city-region</p> <p>Inclusion: yes, small local producers who would otherwise not have access to value chains</p> <p>Connectivities: aligned with food strategy vision developed by the FPN</p>
Food environments (and digital aspects if applicable)	Retail
Alignment with vision/strategic plan	The intervention is part of the visioning and strategy program developed in task 3.2.
INTERVENTION 4 – FOOD SECURITY	
Level	City-region
Brief Description	The initiative aims to reduce the level of food insecurity in the city of Brasov by engaging all the actors in the FPN
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Creation of an institutional framework to support existing social institutions; Promotion of sponsorship activities to NGOs dedicated to food security
Activities envisaged	
1.	<p>Formalization of the "FPN" working group</p> <p>Establish a prefect's order type initiative to formalise the creation of a food policy working group.</p> <p>For the moment, the concept of FPN is quite new for Romanian society, especially for Governance. The periodic FOODCLIC meetings that took place mainly in the governance buildings and the connections established between food system stakeholders have created the preconditions for the official start of Brasov FPN, by a Prefect Order.</p>
2.	Integration of the concept of food security in the development strategies of the Brasov community

	Creation of a chapter on food security in the sustainable development strategy of the Brasov Metropolitan area
3.	<p>Initiatives to increase funds for the daily food allowance at social services</p> <p>A HCL (local council decision) type initiative – the daily allowance for food at social services</p>
4.	<p>Supporting NGOs dedicated to social food services through sponsorships within the FPN</p> <p>Charity events (through schools, festivals, etc.) connecting donors and NGOs – food waste law</p> <p>Hot meal for the elderly</p> <p>Updating the database of elderly people at DAS, the county agency for social benefits</p>
Responsibilities	Transilvania University of Brasov and Brasov City Hall
Resources	Transilvania University of Brasov and Brasov City Hall
Monitoring & Evaluation	No. beneficiaries (minimum 100) by end of 2025
Criteria: How does this intervention meet key project and local criteria?	
Engaging food deprived & vulnerable communities	The intervention targets low-income households and individuals that depend on state and community support.
Engaging innovative business models	Not yet foreseen.
CLIC dimensions	<p>Co-benefits: poverty relief, health</p> <p>Linkages: care for the elderly, social services, city hall</p> <p>Inclusion: the intervention aims to improve access of poor people to healthy food.</p> <p>Connectivities: aligned with food strategy vision developed by the FPN</p>
Food environments (and digital aspects if applicable)	Institutional
Alignment with vision/strategic plan	Part of the vision created by the FPN

2.6 BUDAPEST

2.6.1 SUMMARY OF THE CO-DESIGN PROCESS IN BUDAPEST

Background and aims of the co-design workshops

Prior to the co-design process in Budapest, the FoodCLIC visioning and system understanding workshop in Fall 2023, and the strategic planning workshop in Winter 2023 laid a foundation for conceptualizing the RLIs. One of the key milestones during previous activities was the establishment of the first FPN in Budapest, launched by the Budapest Municipality as a FoodCLIC LL partner. This FPN was created as a food-to-table collaborative network to stimulate attention and resources at the city-region level to implement policies for sustainable urban food systems.

Within this frame, the overall objective for food system transformation and the co-design of interventions is to create a food environment that is healthy, sustainably sourced, accessible, affordable, and culturally appropriate. To this end, several aspects are envisioned for the future of the city-region: local farmers feed Budapest, direct sales of small-scale products increase, and these local, sustainable products become more popular among urban consumers. During the visioning and strategic planning, it was also recognized that there is a need to support urban agriculture so that people can be somewhat self-sufficient, complemented by educational gardening programmes that provide long-term assistance to city residents. The institutional food environment, for instance schools, hospitals and public canteens, must offer healthy and sustainably sourced food, and should strive for waste-free meals. Overall, food saving and reducing waste along the different parts of the supply chain is a priority, as is the strong local community desire to support food citizenship and how people think collectively about their role in the environment.

Scene setting and planning

The co-design process was conducted through three workshops. The first co-design workshop was dedicated to discovering the ideas and main topic themes for RLIs on the neighbourhood level in two districts (VIII. and XIX.) where extensive research was done by LL partners from ESSRG during the previous mapping and gapping process.

As a result of this mapping and gapping, and due to its diverse population and cultural significance, **District VIII** in Budapest, called **Józsefváros**, was selected as a project neighbourhood. Józsefváros has been historically a working-class neighbourhood which is currently gentrifying, with many residents who belong to vulnerable groups from various ethnic

backgrounds facing challenges associated to its demographic composition, health and housing issues.

The second district selected was **District XIX, Kispest**, which was once a small village designed for workers migrating to the capital. As Kispest underwent rapid urbanization during the industrialization period, it grew and became a suburb of Budapest, and today has an active community life with communitarian organisations spreading their love for growing things locally. There are many densely populated housing estates in this neighbourhood where it is more challenging to engage with residents due to a lack of financial and educational resources.

With these neighbourhoods as the focus, the first co-design workshop was held on 6th February 2024 to invite stakeholders with relevant work in districts VIII or XIX. The venue of the workshop (Kesztyűgyár Közöségi Ház) was a community house in the VIII district, maintained by the local district municipality. E-mail invitations were sent to all participants of the visioning and strategy workshops, with additional contact information to request background information about the FoodCLIC project via telephone. Participants were provided an opportunity to send their intervention ideas (or seeds of ideas) to the Budapest LL prior to the workshop, and space was allocated at the beginning of the workshop to introduce existing food initiatives which need further strengthening. Two of these initiatives were presented in more detail at the beginning of the workshop – Farmcity & the Wekerle Food Hub – to discuss potential for development.

The second co-design workshop was held at the City Hall of Budapest on 15th February 2024. The objective was to collect initial ideas and topic themes for interventions at the municipal level, with a focus on bringing together stakeholders who are carrying out activities in the context of different food environments in the city. For this second workshop, participants were selected based on the relevant work at the municipal level, especially those stakeholders who are operating in food environments which were found to be strategically relevant in the previous FoodCLIC workshops.

The third co-design workshop, held on the 12th March 2024 at the City Hall, was aimed at refining key concepts, clarifying contributing partners and identifying responsibilities between them, and developing a detailed action plan for the RLI ideas which resulted from the first and second co-design workshops. All participants were invited whose ideas were selected for further planning, as well as some new participants with potentially relevant roles in assisting the operationalisation of technical aspects for interventions envisioned.

Co-design methodologies

A systems-thinking approach was emphasized during these co-design workshops to keep in mind the co-benefits and linkages between different aspects of the interventions. This helped to encourage a transdisciplinary approach and to develop more synergistic and concrete ideas and proposals for the future. Similar methods were used in the three consecutive co-design workshops: after a short welcome and introduction, members of the Budapest LL presented the

main results and guidelines of the previous visioning and strategy development workshops, complemented by the CLIC framework which laid the foundation the LL's thining about RLIs. Each workshop began with an introductory phase where the previous plans, ideas and initial strategic objectives were shared with participants, who were free to comment, ask questions and further discuss. It was a priority to give people the space to express their own ideas and share them openly with others. We used creative tools like LEGO, coloured post-its, pens, and pencils to create a pleasant and productive atmosphere for people to express their concepts. We also used an action plan template with key information for each intervention idea (activities, objectives, responsibilities, etc.) and filled them in with the participants in small groups and with the help of a facilitator.

In addition to the workshop activities, a city food walk was organized in District XIX, Kispest, on 20th March 2024, in collaboration with one of the selected co-design partners responsible for the Wekerle Food Hub initiative. Participants of all three co-design workshops were invited to take part, with 17 people joining the city walk. The walk offered a wonderful opportunity for participants to learn from the experiences of the Wekerle Transitioning Community, as they have been active in the area and working on sustainable agroecological food production solutions for nearly 20 years. During the walk we visited old and new, failed and functioning sites of community gardens, a packaging-free shop, and a local market and bio bistro operated by the community.

Photo: Bálint Balázs

Photo: Daniel Hedar

Photo: Krisztina Filep

Photo: Dóra Diófási

Photos 1 & 2 (upper row): Co-design workshops at the Kesztyűgyár Community Centre in VIII. District (left) and at the Mayor's Office
 Photos 3 & 4 (lower row): City Food Walk in the Wekerle Transitioning Community neighbourhood in District XIX

Table 1: List of participants in the co-design activities in Budapest

ORGANISATION	SECTOR
JOINT NEIGHBORHOOD WORKSHOP	
Local Municipality of District VIII (Józsefváros)	local government (3)
Védegyelet Egyesület/FarmCity	NGO, buying community (2)
Rév8 Józsefvárosi Rehabilitation and Urban Development Zrt.	local government – urban development (3)
Józsefváros Management Company	local government – city management
Józsefváros Social Services and Child Welfare Centre	local government

Oltalom Charity Association - Heated Streets Program	NGO
Józsefváros Recreation Association	NGO
C8 Civilians for Józsefváros association	NGO
Local Municipality of District XIX. (Kispest)	local government (4)
Transforming Wekerle Community Cooperative	NGO
First Garden Civil Society in Kispest	NGO (3)
Kislépték Egyesület – National Association of Interest Representations for Small-scale producers and service providers	business – farmers and producers (2)
Corvinus University, Budapest	researchers (2)
Institute of Agricultural Economics	researchers
Budapest Mayor's Office	government (4)
ESSRG	researchers (4)
MUNICIPAL LEVEL WORKSHOP	
Department for Climate and Environmental Affairs, Mayor's Office	government (4)
Department for Urban Planning, Mayor's Office	government (3)
Budapest Market Halls Ltd.	government (2)
Budapest Urban Planning Company	government
Budapest Methodological Centre of Social Policy and Its Institutions	government
School Catering Service Business Organization of the capital municipality	government (2)
Municipality of Pest County	government
Cigle Fészek Social Cooperative	NGO
TÉT Platform (Nutrition Platform)	NGO
Hungarian Food Bank Association	NGO
Kislépték Egyesület – National Association of Interest Representations for Small-scale producers and service providers	NGO
Budapest Bike Maffia (Food donation)	NGO
Védegylet Egyesület	NGO

DOMOVOJ projekt	NGO (2)
National Association of Caterers and Food Service Managers	NGO
ESSRG	researchers (4)
Moholy-Nagy University of Art and Design Budapest	researchers
Super Channel Kft	researchers
MUNICIPAL LEVEL WORKSHOP	
Local Municipality of District XIX. (Kispest)	local government (2)
Local Municipality of District VIII (Józsefváros)	local government
Józsefváros Management Company	local government – city management
Department for Social Affairs, Mayor’s Office	government
Department for Climate and Environmental Affairs, Mayor’s Office	Government (4)
Budapest Methodological Centre of Social Policy and Its Institutions	government
Transforming Wekerle Community Cooperative	NGO
First Garden Civil Society in Kispest	NGO (3)
Hungarian Food Bank Association	NGO (2)
Védegylet Egyesület/FarmCity	NGO, buying community
Budapest Bike Maffia (Food donation)	NGO (2)
VIMOSZ - Hungarian Hospitality Employers’ Association	business
Permaculture gardening expert	NGO
ESSRG	researchers (3)

Description of co-design results

The first co-design workshop was very fruitful for conceptualizing and generating consensus support for four intervention ideas: Farmcity, the Fruit & Vegetable Social Cooperative, the Wekerle Food Hub and the Balcony Gardening Program. These interventions were found to be optimal for further planning from the perspective of their feasibility, engagement with dimensions of the CLIC framework and alignment with the work of the Municipality. The second workshop, while also being enlightening, resulted in two ideas: the Community Food Rescue Platform and Budapest Market Halls for Sustainable Urban Food Systems (for more detail see section 2.6.2 below). During this second workshop, two ideas were rejected for further planning as they were not specific

enough, and the core values of these ideas (education and knowledge dissemination) were already reflected in other selected RLIs.

The main achievement of the third co-design workshop was the refinement of concepts and their translation to more detailed action plans, while also clarifying partners who can be potentially responsible for these actions and identifying the roles.

Overall, the process of RLI co-design in Budapest allowed the LL coordinators to delve deeper into the engagement of different stakeholders through analysing possible activities and initiatives which are already running, while also offering an important open space for stakeholders to connect and get to know each other's activities. One of the resulting achievements was the level of harmonisation among ideas, goals and priorities to strengthen networks which are operating within similar food environments.

Lessons Learned

The most challenging aspect of the co-design process was the transition from generating ideas and brainstorming to asking participants to develop detailed action plans, including timelines and financial estimations. As outlined in the portfolio of interventions below, what could be planned during these workshops reflects the initial estimate or projection. However, there was a lack of information available on the options for financing and contracting under the parameters of the FoodCLIC project (for example, what type of contracting and types of costs are eligible under EU rules), which need to be further clarified before final budget considerations for interventions can be confirmed. This caused some difficulties to assess the amount of financial support which each intervention would/could receive during the project activities.

Lastly, it was also challenging to explain the FoodCLIC methodology on which the project is built, as many participants did not understand the reason behind designing RLIs prior to finalising the final food strategy of Budapest. Facilitators were extremely useful in keeping the participants on track, and smoothing out tensions which mainly arose due to the complexity of the FoodCLIC project, for example, when participants criticized the local scale of pilot interventions instead of starting with prioritizing new Municipal policies.

On reflection, the co-design process could have benefited from having a clear overview about the list of organisations which are owned and operated by the Municipality of Budapest and which are relevant in the context of this project, as many participants were not familiar with their work. Consequently, sometimes ideas focused on themes which were already (or which are currently being) addressed, for example the reinvention of institutional food environment through public school canteens and public procurement practices.

Outlook

Looking ahead, the Municipality of Budapest must internally examine the legal and financial feasibility of each intervention idea and negotiate the possible ways to cooperate and implement RLIs with co-design partners. This process will be further complicated by the upcoming municipal elections in June 2024, which will tie up the decision-making board in the coming months until the establishment of a new general assembly. The focus will turn to further conceptualisation of the interventions as well as the execution of baseline surveys to provide means to evaluate and reassess intervention planning at the first action-observation-reflection session.

2.6.1 PORTFOLIO OF REAL-LIFE INTERVENTIONS

The table below provides an overview of the tentative real-life interventions planned during the co-design workshops in Budapest.

INTERVENTION 1 – BUDAPEST MARKET HALLS FOR SUSTAINABLE URBAN FOOD SYSTEMS	
Level	Municipal
Brief Description	Budapest's market halls and markets are important actors in the city's food systems, where consumers, traders and producers are connected to each other. They are therefore ideal places for shaping the attitudes and education of these actors. The Budapest Market Halls (BMH) Ltd. is owned by the Municipality of Budapest, with more than 100 years of tradition. BMH is already active in some outreach programmes, such as market visits for kindergarten groups, thematic days (dairy, honey, etc.), Open Markets Day, and tenants' education, but these activities lack a coherent framework and adequate capacity. The target groups for the programmes are consumers, including kindergarten and school groups, families and the elderly, traders and small-scale producers.
Objectives	To develop a series of programmes for community building around market halls, connecting consumers, traders and producers, and education and communication on sustainable and healthy food consumption.
Activities envisaged	
1.	Baseline survey of target groups, development of program plans tailored to target groups (M1-M3)
2.	Development of educational materials and training plans (M3-M6)
3.	Design of community spaces (M3-M6)

4.	Reaching target groups through continuous communication and launching programmes (communication from M2, programmes from M4)
Responsibilities	It is envisaged that the intervention will be operated by BMH Ltd. However, given the specific rules of municipal operation, the legal and financial options still need to be explored.
Resources	<p>The implementation of the programme series will require human resources for coordination, educational and training materials, the creation of community spaces in the markets and communication platforms.</p> <p>The coordinating person would be employed – depending on the legal and financial possibilities – by BMH Ltd. or the Municipality. The baseline survey will be provided by an external contributor. Educational materials will be collected based on existing practices, and civil society organizations dealing with this topic will also be involved. Communication will take place via the existing social media and websites, developing and strengthening them.</p>
Monitoring & Evaluation	<p>Success can be measured with the following indicators:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The number of visitors to the market, including those belonging to each target group, is increasing. • The proportion of local products and organic products sold by traders is increasing. • The number of visitors to the events. • The number of groups of children visiting the market.
Criteria: How does this intervention meet key project and local criteria?	
Engaging food deprived & vulnerable communities	Among the visitors of some markets, the retirement-age group is overrepresented. These programmes can influence their shopping and consumption habits to become more conscious, while also attracting young people to markets more often to get acquainted with local producers.
CLIC dimensions	<p>Co-benefits: The positive impact on consumer choices (eating healthier food, consuming more fruit and vegetables, choosing local products, etc.) contributes to improving the overall health of consumers, strengthening the economy of local retailers and peri-urban producers, and improving the environment by choosing goods from more sustainable production.</p> <p>Linkages: The programmes help strengthen the link between urban consumers and traders and rural and peri-urban producers.</p> <p>Inclusion: With the programmes we involve different groups of inhabitants (children, families, elderly people) and bring markets</p>

	<p>and producers closer to them. In addition, with the knowledge provided to them, we bring their food-related household decisions closer to sustainability aspects.</p> <p>Connectivities: Strengthening the in-person interactions between consumers, traders and producers helps to understand the behaviour of each party and the reasons behind their decisions.</p>
Food environments	Retail food environment – more sustainable through training and shaping the attitudes of traders operating in the markets, by taking sustainability into account in their purchasing and business decisions (purchasing local or organic products, handling food waste, etc.)
Alignment with vision/strategic plan	An important element of Budapest's vision for sustainable food systems are market halls as the most suitable places for the integration of residents, traders and producers.
Other important information	The timeframes given for activities are rough estimations.

INTERVENTION 2 – FARMCITY SHOP – EXTENDING THE BUYING COMMUNITY TO DISADVANTAGED SOCIAL GROUPS IN DISTRICT VIII

Level	Neighbourhood level
Brief Description	An initiative built on an innovative and inclusive business model, offering local, seasonal and healthy products to extend the operation of the buying community towards the vulnerable residents of the district. This initiative has been active in previous years, however the original shop closed due to financial difficulties. The new Farmcity shop would be redeveloped as a community space and an educational/community kitchen to build community and attract new clients. Through a solidarity model, producers donate some products and customers buy sponsorship tickets to support vulnerable residents of the district, coordinated by local stakeholder organisations.
Objectives	The intervention provides an opportunity to raise environmental awareness. On the one hand, the business model and shop will ensure that people can buy local, seasonal and quality food, and on the other hand, the community space and kitchen will allow a local community to organise and develop around these values in the district, for a sustainable and healthy food environment in the long term.

Activities envisaged	
1.	Capacity building: kitchen and public space development (M1-M6)
2.	Design and launch community programmes (M3-M7)
3.	Design of sponsorship ticket system and collection of product donations from the farmers, producers (M3)
4.	The distribution of fruit and vegetable boxes, made up of donations from producers and the income of sponsor tickets for people in need with the help of the partner organisations. (from M4)
Responsibilities	It is envisaged that the intervention will be operated by Farmcity buying group. Local organisations providing social care (e.g., Shelter for Families) and NGOs are also involved in reaching families in need. However, given the specific rules of municipal operation, the legal and financial options still need to be explored.
Resources	The construction of the community rooms will require skilled workers and building materials, preferably locally sourced. Volunteers can also be involved in the construction work to strengthen the community. Local NGOs and social organizations and the producers themselves can cooperate in the development and operation of community programmes. To operate the donation system, logistical resources (transportation, storage) are needed, which the buying community can provide with the cooperation of local organizations.
Monitoring & Evaluation	Success can be measured with the following indicators: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the number of cooperating farmers • the number of buyers, members of the shopping community • the number and value of sponsorship tickets purchased • the amount of donations from producers • number of people in need reached by donations • number of community programmes and participants
Criteria: How does this intervention meet key project and local criteria?	
Engaging food deprived & vulnerable communities	Community events and the donation system would ensure that the opportunity to access healthy products reaches residents and, through dedicated collaboration with local partners, disadvantaged groups.
CLIC dimensions	The sale of sponsorship tickets would introduce a new and innovative business model.

Food environments	<p>Co-benefits: The positive impact on consumer choices (eating healthier food, consuming more fruit and vegetables, choosing local products etc.) contributes to improving the overall health of consumers, to strengthening the economy of local, peri-urban farmers and producers, and to improving the environment by choosing goods from more sustainable production.</p> <p>Linkages: The intervention helps to strengthen the link between urban consumers and rural and peri-urban producers.</p> <p>Inclusion: With the programmes we involve residents in need and bring farmers and producers closer to them. In addition, with the knowledge provided to them, we bring their household decisions related to food closer to sustainability aspects.</p> <p>Connectivities: Strengthening lively relationships between consumers and farmers helps them to better understand the behaviour of each party and the reasons behind their decisions.</p>
Alignment with vision/strategic plan	The measure will strengthen both the producers supplying the buying community (agri-food environment) and the alternative food community itself (alternative, community-based food environment).
Other important information	The timeframes for activities are rough estimations.

INTERVENTION 3 – FRUIT & VEGETABLE SOCIAL COOPERATIVE IN DISTRICT VIII

Level	Neighbourhood level
Brief Description	<p>The core of the concept is establishing and running a social cooperative which would operate a stand selling fruit and vegetables in the local Market Hall, and a vegetable garden where vegetables would be grown as part of community work. The local community would participate in the gardening, especially the disadvantaged groups (unemployed, disadvantaged families), as well as groups from the district kindergarten and schools and the district's elderly, who would receive coupons and discounts in exchange for their work at the Cooperative. The Cooperative would sell vegetables and fruits from farms around Budapest, mainly small producers, produced with sustainable farming practices (e.g., organic or regenerative production methods) at the market stand, as well as goods produced in the Cooperative's own garden. Both in the vegetable garden and in the market, the Cooperative would carry out attitude-forming activities (urban gardening, healthy and sustainable nutrition) with the involvement of volunteers.</p>

Objectives	The aim of the intervention is to improve access to healthy and sustainable food for the population living in the district, primarily among disadvantaged groups and young people. It also aims to empower local communities and transfer knowledge on sustainable and healthy eating, changing bad habits and attitudes towards food waste.
Activities envisaged	
1.	Establishing the conditions for operation (setting up a cooperative, obtaining permits, concluding cooperation agreements) (M1-M6)
2.	Setting up the market stand and community place, the logistics system, the discount scheme and the vegetable garden (M4-M8)
3.	Reaching the target groups through after school support programmes, job-search offices, family support organizations and pensioner clubs, and a communication campaign (from M6)
4.	Development of an educational package, launching educational activities in the garden and in the market hall with the involvement of volunteers (from M4)
Responsibilities	It is envisaged that the Social Cooperative will be operated by the local district government or by the municipality. Given the specific rules of municipal operation, the legal and financial options still need to be explored.
Resources	Human resources are needed to set up the working structure of the Social Cooperative, but it has to be considered whether this should be done at district or metropolitan level. The stand will be set up in a market hall maintained by the Municipality of Budapest, while the vegetable garden will be set up on land owned by the Municipality of Budapest or the district municipality. The design of the garden would be partly financed from the project budget and partly from other sources, with the help of volunteers. The use of district media (newspapers, social media) and the involvement of local NGOs will help in communication and reaching the target groups. The involvement of relevant NGOs and volunteers is also needed to develop and launch educational programmes.
Monitoring & Evaluation	Success can be measured with the following indicators: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the amount of fruit and vegetables produced in the garden • number of people involved in community work in the garden

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • number of jobs created in the cooperative • the amount saved by the discount scheme • number of people using the scheme • number of participants in programmes, including target groups (children, elderly, disadvantaged families)
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Criteria: How does this intervention meet key project and local criteria?

Engaging food deprived & vulnerable communities	The Cooperative helps disadvantaged groups by hiring salespeople through the local job search office, and the discount system can also be used by members of local disadvantaged groups.
Engaging innovative business models	The Social Cooperative and the discount system would introduce a new and innovative business model.
CLIC dimensions	<p>Co-benefits: The positive impact on consumer choices (eating healthier food, consuming more fruit and vegetables, choosing local products etc.) contributes to improving the overall health of consumers, strengthening the economy of local retailers and peri-urban producers, and improving the environment by choosing goods from more sustainable production. The vegetable garden will improve the microclimatic conditions and biodiversity of the local area.</p> <p>Inclusion: With the programmes we involve different groups of inhabitants (children, families, elderly people). In addition, with the knowledge provided to them, we bring their household decisions related to food closer to sustainability aspects.</p>
Food environments	By expanding urban agricultural opportunities, we increase the diversity of the agri-food environment. The sale of the products of peri-urban producers helps to make the retail food environment more sustainable.
Alignment with vision/strategic plan	An important element of Budapest's vision for sustainable food systems are the local communities and the transformation of their food related habits.
Other important information	The timeframes for activities are rough estimations.

INTERVENTION 4 – WEKERLE FOOD HUB IN DISTRICT XIX

Level	Neighbourhood level
Brief Description	The intervention further develops a multi-leg model programme already operating on a cooperative basis as a community space, café and kitchen. By creating and coordinating a new community training kitchen and classroom, it aims to enable people in the

	district to gain theoretical and practical knowledge about sustainable food production and consumption. New training tools will be developed involving specialists (consultants, communication specialists) and community members who can assist in the transfer of knowledge in an expanded social network.
Objectives	The aim of the intervention is therefore to develop a multifunctional community space and a series of programmes focusing on community building, education and communication on sustainable consumption.
Activities envisaged	
1.	Basic survey of target groups, development of program plans tailored to target groups (M1-M3)
2.	Launching of programmes: garden visits, seedling fairs and exchanges, composting programmes, cooking classes for specific target audiences (kindergarten, schools, retirement homes, after-school programmes) (from M4)
3.	Capacity building: kitchen and community garden development (M5-M7)
4.	Spreading the program (2025-26) – finding new partners (schools), involving vulnerable groups, young people
5.	Baseline survey of target groups, development of program plans tailored to target groups (M1-M3)
Responsibilities	It is envisaged that the intervention will be operated by Transforming Wekerle Community Cooperative. However, given the specific rules of municipal operation, the legal and financial options still need to be explored.
Resources	<p>The implementation of the programme series will require human resources for coordination both in the garden and in the kitchen program. The involvement of relevant NGOs, influencers and volunteers is also needed to develop and launch educational programmes.</p> <p>To increase the accessibility of the kitchen and the garden, improvements will be needed, which we will finance from the project budget and external sources. The use of district media (newspapers, social media) and the involvement of local NGOs will help in communication and reaching the target groups.</p> <p>To ensure the sustainability of the program, the search for external financial sources will continue.</p>

Monitoring & Evaluation	<p>Success can be measured with the following indicators:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The number of food related workshops • The number of visitors to the events and workshops • The number of groups of children and elderly people visiting the programmes • The amount of food served in the common kitchen • The amount of fruit and vegetables produced in the garden
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Criteria: How does this intervention meet key project and local criteria?

Engaging food deprived & vulnerable communities	The target groups include elderly people and children from disadvantaged families through after-school programmes.
CLIC dimensions	<p>Co-benefits: The positive impact on consumer choices (eating healthier food, consuming more fruit and vegetables, choosing local products etc.) contributes to improving the overall health of consumers, and to improving the environment by choosing goods from more sustainable production.</p> <p>Inclusion: With the programmes we involve different groups of inhabitants (children, families, elderly people). In addition, with the knowledge provided to them, we bring their household decisions related to food closer to sustainability aspects.</p>
Food environments	<p>By expanding urban agricultural opportunities, we increase the diversity of the agri-food environment.</p> <p>Mindset change programmes will strengthen the alternative food community itself (alternative, community-based food environment) and contribute to positive changes in consumer choices.</p>
Alignment with vision/strategic plan	An important element of Budapest's vision for sustainable food systems are the local communities and the transformation of their food related habits.
Other important information	The timeframes for activities are rough estimations.

INTERVENTION 5 – PERMACULTURE BALCONY GARDENING PROGRAMME AT THE KISPEST HOUSING ESTATE IN DISTRICT XIX

Level	Neighbourhood level
Brief Description	Permaculture balcony gardening programme at the Kispest housing estate (Kispest, XIX. district), coordinated mainly by the local Municipality of Kispest. The establishment of a training programme which includes theoretical (educational materials would be published on the website of the local municipality) and practical training regarding permaculture gardening, based on the

	philosophy of organic agriculture. Moreover, the program would also cover the acquisition of a “starter set” (1 loft bed; 1 planter box; 1 seed pack; 1 bee hotel; soil and compost) for participants. Next to the training program, the Municipality would also establish a pilot permaculture garden at Forrásház Gondozási Központ (Forrásház Social Care Centre) for demonstrational purposes to offer an opportunity to experiment with permaculture gardening techniques for pupils receiving social care at the institution.
Objectives	To cause a positive change in the local food environment of at least 50 residents, living in the housing estate located at Kispest, and to strengthen the gardening culture and biodiversity in the community.
Activities envisaged	
1.	Clarifying goals (M1)
2.	Cooperation agreement with partners (M1-M2)
3.	Survey and assessment of needs (M2-M4)
4.	Announcement of the program – call for citizens (M4-M5)
5.	Specific designs, and establishing the demonstrational permaculture unit (M6-M7)
6.	Organising (already existing) educational materials according to specific needs (M5-M7)
7.	Education (theoretic and practical) (M6-M24)
8.	Community building (M4-M24)
9.	Reassessment of the program based on initial feedback from participants (M6-M8)
10.	Consultation services (M6-M24)
11.	Organising incentivising contest of best permaculture balcony (M12-M24)
Responsibilities	Zöld iroda (Green Office); Jogi iroda (Law Office); Municipality of Kispest (XIX. district) coordination of baseline study, development of legal contracts and theoretic and practical training materials; coordination of trainings, knowledge and information dissemination through municipal websites and social media platforms, ensures space and location (social care centre; community gardens), Kispesti Közpark Kft. (urban gardening) – assists in technical implementation Első-Kis-Pesti Kert – assists in sharing experiences, advice

	Other professionals with relevant knowledge – assist in tailoring educational materials to specific needs Municipality of Budapest – assists in the promotion of activities,
Resources	Human resources: trainers, designers, coordinators, communication experts Material resources: materials for permaculture designs, tools for building, seeds, seedlings, loft beds, soil + compost Financial resources: covered by FoodCLIC with additional financing from the local municipality Other resources: online platforms
Monitoring & Evaluation	Success indicators as determined by the local municipality: at least 70% percent of the local inhabitants who participated in the programme maintains a well-functioning balcony garden; growing interest and participation in balcony gardening (i.e., waiting list for the balcony program and local community gardens increases) and locals ask for the continuation of the program.
Criteria: How does this intervention meet key project and local criteria?	
Engaging food deprived & vulnerable communities	Residents in the housing estate often belong to low income or vulnerable communities and programme reach to mentally ill pupils who are receiving care at the local care centre.
CLIC dimensions	Co-benefits: The positive impact on consumer choices (eating healthier food, consuming more fruit and vegetables, choosing locally grown ecological products etc.) contributes to improving the overall health of consumers. The vegetable garden will improve the microclimatic conditions and biodiversity of the local area. Self-sufficiency from vegetables, herbs, seed sovereignty. Knowledge building about permaculture, urban nature and ecosystems. Inclusion: involving low income citizens – vulnerable local inhabitants Connectivities: urban planning
Food environments	urban agriculture, wild agriculture, alternative community-based agriculture
Alignment with vision/strategic plan	The program aligns with the long-term vision with regard to building communities who focus on local food production to increase the number of (partly) self-sustaining locals. Furthermore, it exemplifies how local governments could incentivise local inhabitants for production through active education, lastly the program increases the biodiversity in the area.

Other important information	The timeframes for activities are rough estimations.
INTERVENTION 6 – LAUNCH OF COMMUNITY-BASED FOOD RESCUE PLATFORM	
Level	Municipal
Brief Description	As a first step, the intervention would be aimed at improving the existing website of the Budapest Bike Mafia (BBM), which is already involved in food rescue. The food donors post on the website the type and quantity of the donation, as well as the pick-up location and time, so that a volunteer delivery person can reserve it and deliver it to their selected recipient. To ensure proper food safety, the measure also includes related training for those who offer food donations.
Objectives	The aim is to better organise the process of volunteers donating and delivering food, and to reach more people, mainly (but not exclusively) private individuals, with the possibility to donate food. This will reduce the amount of avoidable food waste in the community.
Activities envisaged	
1.	Data collection regarding the offering and receiving organizations (M1-M3)
2.	IT development based on the survey of the target groups (M3-M5)
3.	Design of educational materials (M2-M3)
4.	Assess the potential of receiving organisations (M1-M6)
5.	Communication campaign from (M3)
Responsibilities	It is envisaged that the intervention will be operated by Budapest Bike Mafia (BBM). However, given the specific rules of municipal operation, the legal and financial options still need to be explored. The Hungarian Food Service Bank and Budapest Methodological Centre of Social Policy and its institutions participate as a cooperative organization.
Resources	A coordinator should be appointed for each of the cooperating organisations. Data collection is needed for the proper specification of the website, which would be carried out in cooperation between BBM, the Hungarian Food Service Bank and Budapest Methodological Centre of Social Policy and Its Institutions. IT development requires a contracted professional partner.

Monitoring & Evaluation	<p>Success can be measured with the following indicators:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The number of food donors • The number of recipients of food donations • The amount of saved food
Criteria: How does this intervention meet key project and local criteria?	
Engaging food deprived & vulnerable communities	Food donations will reach people in need, contributing to their proper nutrition.
CLIC dimensions	<p>Co-benefits: Reducing food waste contributes to reducing the environmental emissions of the food value chain.</p> <p>Inclusion: Food donations will reach people in need, contributing to improving their diets.</p>
Food environments	<p>The program primarily aims to reduce food loss in households, but it can also be extended to the hospitality food environment. On the receiving side, this can help institutional care.</p> <p>The core element of the intervention is the development of a user-friendly website.</p>
Alignment with vision/strategic plan	An important element of Budapest's vision for sustainable food systems is to ensure that proper nutrition is also available to socially disadvantaged residents.
Other important information	The timeframes for activities are rough estimates.

2.7 LISBON

2.7.1 SUMMARY OF THE CO-DESIGN PROCESS IN LISBON METROPOLITAN AREA

Background and aims of the co-design workshops

Prior to the entering the co-design process to select and plan RLIs, the FoodCLIC Living Lab in Lisbon conducted extensive visioning and strategy activities (reported in deliverable D3.1). These activities built on previous establishment of a formalized FPN (Food Link) and the ongoing development of a food strategy for the Lisbon Metropolitan Area. In this context, FoodCLIC activities have contributed to district and neighbourhood-level analyses of systemic barriers to food system transformation, visions for future food systems at different scales, as well and key strategic themes. The previous activities also identified two neighbourhoods where FoodCLIC can make a potential impact with real-life interventions. The two neighbourhoods selected by the LL in Lisbon are Cabeço do Mouro and Adroana.

Cabeço do Mouro belongs to the São Domingos de Rana parish in Outeiro Polima. It is in a residential area and was built under the PER—Special Rehousing Programme. The first residents moved into the houses in 2001. The neighbourhood comprises four shops and eight social housing buildings with 78 dwellings.

Adroana is a small locality with an area of 1,7 km² located in the parish of Alcabideche, in the north of the municipality of Cascais, integrated with the Lisbon metropolitan area (AML). The social Adroana neighbourhood was built in 2004 as part of the PER-Special Resettlement Programme. The first families to inhabit the public housing buildings moved in 2005.

Scene setting and planning

In response to evolving circumstances and a desire to enhance stakeholder engagement, our living lab, especially the municipal district of Cascais, Lisbon as living lab practice partner, has decided to embark on a different approach to the co-design process aimed at transforming the food system within the Lisbon metropolitan area. Originally envisioned as a series of structured workshops, the strategic decision was made to adapt the FoodCLIC methodology to better suit the needs of our stakeholders and the current environment.

After a thorough examination of the stakeholders involved, it has become apparent that these partners extend their collaboration far beyond the confines of the FoodCLIC Project within Cascais Ambiente, forging a robust alliance across various municipal initiatives. Yet, signs of weariness

towards the project have emerged among stakeholders, attributed to its protracted theoretical phase stretching from mapping to intervention implementation. Following extensive deliberations and consensus reached in internal meetings, we determined that the most prudent course of action was a modification of the tools proposed by the consortium for the co-design phase. Instead of a more formal methodology involving hosting three workshops where stakeholders convene to collaboratively design real-life interventions, we have opted to introduce a new format, the lunch/dinner gathering, in order to recognize and respond to the importance of flexibility and the value of informal interaction.

These gatherings are currently being developed to combine the underlying principles and core aims of the methodologies established within FoodCLIC, and create two distinct stages to plan real-life interventions: ideation and co-design.

First, in the ideation phase, a meticulous analysis of the outcomes gleaned from prior workshops will ensue, with a keen eye towards adapting to the local intricacies of Cascais and leveraging available tools and resources. To this end, four specific interventions have been earmarked: Nest Gardens, Social Baskets, Food Literacy, and Cookery training programs in social housing estates. All interventions were proposed by stakeholders who participated in the meetings held at different stages of the project, including stakeholders such as the Territory Enhancement Network, Terras de Cascais, Health Department, and NGOs and civil society, among others. The selection of interventions was based on what was presented during these meetings and tailored to meet the expectations of citizens of Cascais and participating stakeholders. The interventions mentioned and selected here are those that are feasible and tangible in current reality.

At the time of writing, the co-design has not started. The four interventions are still in the proposal stage and might require more time and further consultative steps to tailor the co-design methodology. The process of meeting with the stakeholders for the co-design phase will take place in May 2024. Stakeholders will be actively engaged in successive meetings aimed at refining these interventions through a participatory framework. All interested parties are committed to be intricately involved in the collaborative creation of these interventions.

One of the primary reasons for this timing is the recognition of the multitude of engagements stakeholders are currently managing. It is understood that their time is valuable, and the aim is to ensure that when these workshops are convened, stakeholders have the capacity to fully engage and contribute meaningfully to the discussions. By postponing the workshops, the intention is to avoid overburdening stakeholders with too many simultaneous meetings, allowing them the necessary time and space to prioritize their involvement.

Co-design methodologies

This new approach centres around informal gatherings with key stakeholders in the Cascais Municipality. By shifting the setting from a formal workshop environment to a more relaxed and convivial lunch format, we aim to foster deeper connections, facilitate open dialogue, and encourage creative brainstorming in a comfortable setting.

The decision to transition to gatherings reflects our commitment to inclusivity, adaptability, and stakeholder-centred design. We understand that meaningful collaboration often thrives in environments where individuals feel comfortable sharing their perspectives and ideas freely. By embracing a more informal format, we hope to create a space where diverse voices can be heard, insights can be exchanged, and innovative solutions can be co-created.

During these gatherings, participants will have the opportunity to engage in lively discussions, share insights from their respective areas of expertise, and collectively explore innovative approaches to addressing the challenges facing the food system in the Lisbon metropolitan area. Through this collaborative process, we aim to co-design interventions that are not only effective and sustainable but also reflective of the diverse needs and perspectives of the communities selected.

While the format may have changed, the commitment to driving positive change in the food system remains unwavering. By embracing this new approach to co-design, the Lisbon LL is confident to be able to harness the collective wisdom and creativity of the stakeholders to develop solutions that have a meaningful impact on the future of food in the Lisbon metropolitan area.

In conclusion, our decision to transition from formal workshops to informal gatherings represents an exciting evolution in our co-design methodology. The practice partner remains fully committed to the success of this project and is confident that this decision will ultimately contribute to its overall effectiveness. Updates regarding the rescheduling of these workshops will continue to be provided, and appreciation is extended to everyone's understanding and support in this matter.

Description of Co-Design Results

Given the diverse outcomes gleaned from previous workshops regarding stakeholders' visions and strategies, it's crucial to underscore the necessity of refining these findings to align with the specific realities of the municipality where interventions will be deployed. In light of this, the Lisbon Living Lab's practical partners have chosen to focus on three interventions identified during visioning and strategic planning workshops. These interventions will be implemented both at the municipal level and within the Adroana and Cabeço de Mouro neighbourhoods.

The selected interventions to be advanced are as follows:

1. **Hortas Ninho:** These community-oriented gardens will serve as hubs for cultivating local produce, fostering environmental sustainability, and promoting community engagement.

2. **Food Literacy:** This initiative aims to enhance understanding and knowledge about healthy eating habits, food production, and sustainable consumption practices among residents, empowering them to make informed dietary choices.
3. **Social Food Hampers:** Through the provision of essential food items and resources to vulnerable populations, social baskets will address food insecurity issues while fostering social cohesion and support networks within the community.

These interventions represent a concerted effort to address key challenges identified through stakeholder collaboration and to enact meaningful change within the target communities. By focusing on these areas, we aim to create a more resilient, equitable, and sustainable food system in the Lisbon metropolitan area.

The results will be obtained through meetings/workshops with the target stakeholders involved, focussing on what is important to them. It is crucial to emphasise that there is a clearly defined strategy for determining the responsibilities of each stakeholder in implementing the intervention.

Lessons Learned

The reflections and lessons learnt will be evaluated after the process of analysing the results obtained from the meetings/workshops that will be held with the stakeholders in question.

Outlook

The living lab will adjust workshop dates to start in May 2024. The next steps in implementation of these co-design meetings will refine objectives in order to:

- Ensure the goals align with project priorities.
- Engage with the target stakeholders to keep developing a plan for inclusive participation.
- Summarize Results and compile findings into a concise report to be inserted in this report.
- Integrate recommendations to use insights to inform project planning on the co-design process.
- In addition, it is worth pointing out that having the co-design process embedded in the food policy initiative might imply that multiple issues and ideas for action emerge for the medium and long-term activity of the food policy council.
- Maintain engagement to continue dialogue with stakeholders for ongoing collaboration and for the next steps of implementation and the learning and development reflexive cycles.

2.7.2 PORTFOLIO OF REAL-LIFE INTERVENTIONS

The table below provides an overview of the real-life interventions planned during the co-design workshops in the Living Lab.

INTERVENTION 1 – HORTAS NINHO URBAN FARMING	
Level	Municipal / city-region
Brief Description	<p>Hortas Ninho is an urban agriculture incubator that aims to provide plots of land for the practice of urban agriculture. These plots will be larger than community gardens, measuring up to 2000 m², so that local entrepreneurs can start small-scale but highly efficient urban agriculture, with a special focus on market gardening techniques. This will help meet the increasing demand for local, seasonal and organic products in the municipality of Cascais. The incubator will provide specialized training to empower these entrepreneurs with all the necessary resources to develop a profitable business. This is a significant step towards promoting local, nutritious, and environmentally friendly food in Cascais. The plots will be fully equipped with all the required resources for the practice of urban agriculture, creating new production areas on currently abandoned land. The products produced through urban agriculture will be sold locally, contributing to the municipality's food sovereignty.</p>
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promote organic farming at a local level, proving that it is a viable alternative to the actual production system; • Contribute to the appreciation and cohesion of the territory; • Enhance abandoned land and increase biodiversity; • Create new jobs, training new farmers and reinforcing entrepreneurship; • Bring producers and consumers closer together; • Support local, fair and supportive economy; • Contribute to the Municipality's food sovereignty; • Reduce the ecological footprint of the food system through short circuits.
Activities envisaged	
1.	Infrastructure implementation
2.	Farmers capacity building

3.	Future sustainability of the project through the creation of a local network
Responsibilities	TBD
Resources	Municipal land with agricultural potential; High demand for organic products at a local level (general population); Disadvantaged population with food needs, particularly fresh products; Articulation with the strategy for food sovereignty of the Terras de Cascais Division.
Monitoring & Evaluation	In recent years, the Terras de Cascais division has developed extensive work in organic and regenerative agriculture in the Municipality and is, therefore, the entity with the right resources to monitor and evaluate the project, if necessary, using external support services.
Criteria: How does this intervention meet key project and local criteria?	
Engaging food deprived & vulnerable communities	The project is located in an area where fresh and organic products are not easily accessible at affordable prices for the disadvantaged population.
Engaging innovative business models	The model presented is part of an innovative sector – small-scale, organic and regenerative agriculture. It would at the same time be a pilot project in Portugal, as it would demonstrate how it is possible to produce in a profitable way, within the city, and environmentally balanced.
CLIC dimensions	This solution co-benefits at several levels: at an environmental level, through organic and regenerative production, contributing to improving the environmental quality of these lands through soil regeneration and increased biodiversity. At an economic level, short circuits not only make it possible to shorten distances and reduce GHG emissions, but also contribute to the local economy. At a social level, it will allow the population access to quality and seasonal food, thus improving the health of the population and will also create jobs and promote entrepreneurship.
Food environments (and digital aspects if applicable)	This proposal is structured around a circular economy model, which includes food production, local distribution, and composting. This creates a closed cycle for the local food system.

Alignment with vision/strategic plan	See the food strategy and visioning process
Any other criteria developed with co-design partners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Contributing to the transition towards the new school canteens' management model - Contributing to increase actors' participation and engagement in the Piana del Cibo food policy
Other important information	<p>The project is in complete alignment with the strategy implemented by the Cascais municipality to encourage the production of locally-grown organic food, promote sustainable consumption habits, provide educational resources for sustainability, encourage entrepreneurship, and enhance social inclusion. It comprises of various production sites, including community vegetable gardens, orchards, vineyards, a prison farm, and a "pick-your-own" vegetable garden, along with several other projects relating to food and agriculture. In 2018, the strategy was launched to integrate the various projects already implemented and those yet to come into a comprehensive strategy - the strategy for urban agriculture in Cascais.</p>

INTERVENTION 2 – FOOD LITERACY

Level	Municipal
Brief Description	<p>The food literacy intervention aims to promote healthy eating habits among the youth by increasing their knowledge, awareness and skills in relation to healthy and sustainable food choices. The intervention will enable them to make informed decisions that consider the impact of their food choices on the climate and the environment. The recommended actions aim to empower the community, focusing on young people, to adopt practical and sustainable solutions that minimize the impact of climate change and promote a healthier local food system.</p> <p>The proposed initiatives aim to educate and empower the community, especially young people, about how their food choices impact the environment and climate. Lisbon Living Lab aims to provide alternatives and practical actions to promote a healthier and more sustainable local food system while reducing the adverse effects of climate change. Our project takes a participatory approach, involving citizens so they can become active agents and critical members of the change.</p>

Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Educate youth about the importance of balanced and sustainable eating habits for health and the environment. • Provide information on the relationship between food choices and climate change, including the role of agriculture, food transport, food waste and greenhouse gas emissions in the environment from production to distribution. • Empower the youth community with practical skills to make conscious food choices, considering criteria such as seasonality, local origin and sustainable production methods. • Promote food security, climate resilience, and food diversity awareness for ecosystem sustainability. • Encouraging young people to become agents of change in their communities, promoting healthy and sustainable food choices, and advocating for more equitable and environmentally responsible food policies.
Activities envisaged	
1.	Launch a healthy and sustainable recipe competition/collection for the school community.
2.	Visits to organic farms, agricultural co-operatives and permaculture projects to learn about sustainable agricultural practices and local food systems.
3.	Develop a life-sized board game about food and climate that educates its players
4.	Practical cookery sessions using seasonal and local ingredients, promoting sustainable cooking and reducing food waste.
5.	An event will be organized for the community in partnership with the Town Council and Cascais Ambiente. It will include an experimental cooking session and an educational game. The event will be held at the Municipal Market or Quinta do Pisão and open to the general public. The school community will also be invited, with at least one class of students per parish.
Responsibilities	Cascais Ambiente, in collaboration with various stakeholders participating in the FoodCLIC workshops, will lead this initiative, with the partnership including the Cascais City Council, Cascais Ambiente and civil society groups such as NGOs.

	<p>The intervention will be implemented in conjunction with Cascais City Council departments, namely the Health Promotion and Well-being Division and the Food Quality and Safety Division.</p>
<p>Resources</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collaboration with local schools, NGOs, farmers, health and nutrition experts to promote environmental education. • Educational materials for practical activities, transport for field visits, • fees for guest speakers. • Logistical support is needed for lectures and a cooking session. This includes the facilities for both events.
<p>Monitoring & Evaluation</p>	<p>The intervention will be monitored according to the RE-AIM framework:</p> <p>REACH:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of people involved in actions to promote literacy, attitudes and values and respective proportion in relation to defined target groups (with collection of motivations for participation) <p>EFFECTIVENESS:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adherence to initiatives • Indicators of knowledge acquisition and alignment of attitudes and values that promote healthy and sustainable eating (segmented by relevant groups: gender, age, socioeconomic conditions and areas of residence) • Behavioural indicators: eating behaviour indicators proposed by FoodCLIC <p>ADOPTION:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of promoter stakeholders involved in initiatives over time (number of organizations and people) • Engagement and drop-out reasons <p>IMPLEMENTATION:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of innovation initiatives and processes that occur throughout the project <p>MAINTENANCE:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Indicators of program visibility and notoriety • Indicators of organizational culture adherent to the process (e.g. Continuation after changing political cycles).

Criteria: How does this intervention meet key project and local criteria?	
Engaging food deprived & vulnerable communities	The intervention is aimed at the municipal context and will be conducted locally, focusing on social neighbourhoods. Education professionals will be partnered up and assigned to create social projects with young people in these areas. Specifically, the social neighbourhoods of Adroana and Cabeço de Mouro will be the target areas for this initiative.
CLIC dimensions	The intervention aims to align with the dimensions of CLIC and bring co-benefits to all involved. It seeks to strengthen the connection between young people, health and education professionals, and people in need in social neighbourhoods. Additionally, it will create environmental benefits by increasing food literacy among citizens and promoting sustainable eating habits, such as consuming local and seasonal food. The initiative will also establish connectivities between the local government, including the Department of Health and Education, Terra de Cascais, Department of Solidarity, and civil society, such as non-profit organizations and citizens.
Food environments (and digital aspects if applicable)	Making informed food choices can be challenging for consumers. By educating youth and the community about the difference between healthy and environmentally friendly options, we can promote better health and aid the fight against climate change. Food literacy aims to transform behaviour, promote efficient use of agricultural resources, and raise awareness of the importance of short food supply circuits. This approach can contribute to climate change adaptation and mitigation.
Alignment with vision/strategic plan	Stakeholders prioritised food literacy during the visioning and strategic planning sessions. The four lines of action considered to be priorities highlighted the promotion of food literacy centred on empowering citizens from a "farm to fork" perspective so that they can achieve a healthy and sustainable diet adapted to their context: production, processing, access to and consumption of food and related skills.
Any other criteria developed with co-design partners	In the sessions with neighbourhood residents, priority lines of action were also identified and adapted to the specific context of the neighbourhood. In Adroana, in line with the perspectives of other stakeholders, residents prioritised promoting food literacy.

INTERVENTION 3 – SOCIAL FOOD HAMPERS	
Level	Neighbourhood
Brief Description	<p>The "Social Food Hampers" initiative is an effort to establish short food supply chains that encourage direct communication between producers and consumers. This project aims to provide fresh, organic food to people in vulnerable situations residing in the social neighbourhoods of Adroana and Cabeço de Mouro. The food will be distributed through a membership card system. These hampers, sold by Cascais Ambiente, aim to alleviate food shortages. The food comes from local sources, such as Hortas Ninho/Horta do Pisão/Horta do Brejo/Hortas Associativas, with the support of the local authority, which provides logistical resources such as vans and drivers, and organisations that donate surplus food, such as the Mais Solidário Card from the Resources for Social Inclusion Division.</p> <p>These hampers not only provide recipients with their daily energy and nutritional needs but also contain fresh, organic food not typically found in traditional food aid models.</p> <p>The intervention will provide beneficiaries with membership cards that grant them access to locally sourced, seasonal organic food. Partner organizations will supplement this food with products co-financed by Cascais Ambiente as part of the FoodCLIC project. This approach promotes food security, local sustainability, and food sovereignty while also strengthening the bond between producers and consumers in the community.</p>
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improve the availability of fresh and organic food for vulnerable communities. • Empower social housing communities to achieve food sovereignty through resilient local food systems. • Raise awareness of sustainable eating habits with a low carbon footprint.
Activities envisaged	
1.	Select participants who will become members.
2.	Mediate purchases with local producers.
3.	Organise the hampers for distribution.
4.	Distribute organic and local food.
Responsibilities	The Social Food Hampers initiative will be overseen by Cascais Ambiente, with two divisions in charge: the Climate Action Department and the Terras de Cascais Division. This intervention will be carried out in collaboration with other departments of

	<p>Cascais Town Hall, which are already involved in the National Plan for the Promotion of Healthy Eating (PNPAM) and are working together with the More Solidarity Card in Cascais.</p>
<p>Resources</p>	<p>Physical resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Storage facility • Transport • Ecological packaging materials: boxes and recyclable bags for packaging organic products. Ensure that packaging materials comply with organic certification standards. <p>Human Resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local farmers (specifically those working with Terras de Cascais, Hortas Ninho, etc): establish partnerships with local organic food producers and suppliers. Negotiate contracts or agreements with suppliers regarding prices, quality standards and delivery times. • Distribution team: Hire (?) people to manage the distribution process. • Customer service: it may be necessary to employ Cascais Ambiente customer service representatives (Terras de Cascais). <p>Equipment (technology)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tracking and logistics software: to map and optimise routes, monitor deliveries, etc. • Communication tools: mobile phones, radios, etc. <p>Marketing</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Building the "social hampers" brand: logo, labelling, design of packages and boxes. • Launch a marketing campaign to promote distribution among vulnerable populations and build partnerships with local organizations to increase demand and generate greater interest in the association.
<p>Monitoring & Evaluation</p>	<p>The intervention's indicators will be thoroughly assessed to conduct monitoring and evaluation.</p> <p>Analysing sales and distribution: Quantitative data will be collected, such as the number of hampers distributed, the purchase of food by rural producers, the food produced, and the frequency of distribution. A database will be created to monitor the volume of distribution and the products distributed (qualitative data). Member satisfaction will be analysed through surveys.</p>

	<p>Opportunities will also be identified to adjust supply levels and product types and adapt product offerings to meet the needs of members according to their requirements.</p> <p>Evaluation of producer performance: Organic farmers will be assessed based on several criteria, including product quality, reliability, price, and compliance with organic certification standards. To keep records of interactions with farmers, we will document order fulfilment, product quality inspections, and good communication. To ensure consistent product quality, reliable deliveries, and compliance with organic farming practices, farmers' performance will be periodically evaluated. We will provide feedback to farmers and address any problems or concerns that may arise.</p> <p>Environmental impact assessment: The environmental impact will be measured by calculating the carbon footprint of transport, water use and waste production. Monitoring will be done using sustainability metrics and tools, such as carbon footprint calculators or smart irrigation system trackers. Environmental performance will be assessed to look for opportunities to optimise the ecological footprint of the intervention through initiatives such as route optimisation, the use of environmentally friendly packaging materials and waste reduction strategies.</p> <p>Community involvement activities: The aim is to monitor community participation in the social neighbourhoods of Adroana and Cabeço de Mouro through associations. This will be achieved by creating a list of individuals who wish to participate in the "Social Baskets" program. The effectiveness of this program will be evaluated based on its impact on community cohesion.</p>
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Criteria: How does this intervention meet key project and local criteria?

<p>Engaging food deprived & vulnerable communities</p>	<p>The "Social Food Hampers" program aims to provide exclusive food distribution to all partner members of the interventions in selected neighbourhoods. The program will benefit low-income families, the elderly, people with disabilities and other marginalized groups. Based on the initial mapping conducted, the food hampers beneficiaries will comprehensively represent vulnerable populations. The program organizers will seek participation and feedback from these groups to assess the program's inclusiveness and accessibility as the project progresses.</p>
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CLIC dimensions	The proposed intervention will follow the dimensions of CLIC, with the goal of co-benefiting everyone involved. This initiative aims to foster a stronger linkages between rural producers and urban consumers, including those in need in social neighbourhoods. It will also establish connectivities between public sectors such as Terras de Cascais and the Social Inclusion Department, as well as private sectors, which are yet to be defined.
Food environments (and digital aspects if applicable)	The intervention will improve accessibility to organic food producers by establishing short chains for communication.
Alignment with vision/strategic plan	During the workshop session focused on the vision, the discussions and strategies revolved around a particular intervention. The intervention was inspired by a programme called "Cartão Mais Solidário" (More Solidarity Card) launched in Cascais. This initiative aims to support families facing economic difficulties by granting them access to essential goods such as food, cleaning and hygiene products, small appliances, clothing and medication. The Cascais City Council implemented this programme in collaboration with the municipality's Parish Councils and the private distribution sector represented by "Pingo Doce". The More Solidarity Card programme is in effect for two years, from 2023 to 2024.

2.8 PLAIN OF LUCCA

2.8.1 SUMMARY OF THE CO-DESIGN PROCESS IN PLAIN OF LUCCA

Background and aims of the co-design workshops

The Plain of Lucca, located in Tuscany, central Italy, is set between the Mediterranean coast on one side and hills and mountain ranges on the others. Four out of seven municipalities comprising the city-region are involved in the food policy initiative: Capannori, Porcari, Altopascio and Villa Basilica. The largest of these four municipalities is Capannori with around 46,500 inhabitants (as per 2017). These municipalities are heterogeneous in terms of dimension, geographical features, and demographics, but all include both urban and rural areas (as well as historical small-scale agricultural production). The city-region is characterised by increasing urban sprawl and an ageing population.

The Plain of Lucca LL supports the re-launch of the Intermunicipal Food Policy Network Council. In this regard, the earlier phases of the FoodCLIC project were crucial for several reasons: (a) realigning the four municipalities around a shared vision; (b) confirming their official commitment towards the Intermunicipal Food Policy; (c) acknowledging the need for reactivating participation, including new and more diverse actors to get fresh ideas; (d) identifying shared strategic goals.

As a result of the FoodCLIC work on visioning and strategizing (see FoodCLIC Deliverable 3.1), three thematic lines of action were identified and respective working groups were set up: (i) food education, (ii) local food production and supply chains, and (iii) food poverty and access to food. An important development related to the expected activities of the three working groups is that the school canteens' management system in the municipality of Capannori transitioned towards a new local company model named "Qualità e Servizi". The working groups were therefore encouraged to prepare the way for the future service, including through the construction of a community where different perspectives were represented.

Scene setting and planning

Overall, three rounds of workshops have been planned, with three workshops for each of the three working groups/lines of intervention. The first three of the overall nine workshops have been held in Cappannori. Forthcoming workshops are planned to be hosted by other municipalities involved in the Food Policy Network to underscore the city-region perspective on the process and the inter-municipal nature of the activities.

In the Municipality of Capannori the workshops were held in a municipally owned hostel located in the locality of Vorno, at the rural-urban fringe, on the following dates focusing on the following working groups:

- 27th February 2024: local food production and supply chains
- 29th February 2024: food education
- 5th March 2024: access to food and food poverty

Invitations were sent out by the Municipality of Capannori with a two-fold approach. First, an existing mailing list was used, which included individuals and organisations who had previously attended meetings, events or workshops by the Piana del Cibo or FoodCLIC. Secondly, with the aim of enlarging participation to as many people as possible, a call for participation was published in a local newspaper and shared on social media. An average of 12 people were involved in each workshop (with a maximum of 17 in one occasion), including LL members and the support team (facilitators and working group coordinators).

Images 1-3: Working tables on food education, food supply chains and food poverty. Source: R. Pensa

Co-design methodologies

The meetings were organised with the aim of supporting and building on the recently reactivated Intermunicipal Food Policy of ‘Piana del Cibo’. The strategy of matching co-design workshops in FoodCLIC with the working groups of the Piana del Cibo aimed to address a threefold objective:

1. to accompany the ongoing food policy process in the Piana del Cibo through FoodCLIC material and immaterial resources, making room for in-depth discussions to take place while pushing towards the operationalisation of the ideas that have emerged;
2. to encourage actors in the working groups to take ownership of the co-designed activities and ensure their continuity beyond the project's duration;
3. to align activities in the working groups in view of the transition towards the new school canteens’ model.

For these reasons – and for the reasons unveiled in the earlier mapping and gapping phase of FoodCLIC – all the workshops planned had a municipal or city-region perspective, instead of focusing just on one or two neighbourhoods.

The co-design workshops were organised for each working group – namely (i) food education, (ii) local food production and supply chains, and (iii) food poverty and access to food. The workshops were divided into different sessions and, by the time of writing, only the first session had taken place. Facilitators were identified with the goal of giving the discussion a line towards the definition of RLIs that, on the one hand, could be the result of the needs and visions of the participants and, on the other, be aligned with the ongoing work of the FNP and with the FoodCLIC resources and timeline.

The first part of the workshops were carried out by the LL members, alongside the coordinators of the working groups, and two expert facilitators appointed by the municipality for their longstanding experience in the field. This initial round served to break the ice, discuss the general aims of each table, define shared objectives, and identify missing actors which should be involved in the next workshops. After short introductions by LL members, all participants introduced themselves and

their experience or role regarding the line of interventions discussed. In most cases, participating organisations were represented by more than one member.

In all of the workshops, one member of the 'Qualità and Servizi' company presented their model in relation to the respective theme. One facilitator used visual materials based on earlier mapping of initiatives which could inspire new ideas building on existing assets; the others called for new ideas based on direct experience by participants.

Table 1: List of participants in the co-design activities in Plain of Lucca region

ORGANISATION	SECTOR
CITY-REGION WORKSHOPS	
Municipality of Capannori (city council members;	Public Administration (2)
Municipality of Porcari (city board members)	Public Administration (1)
Municipality of Altopascio (city board members)	Public Administration (1)
ASL Toscana nord-ovest	Public Administration (2)
Piana del Cibo	Public Administration/Civil Society (3)
Mani Tese ONG	Civil Society (1)
Slow Food Lucca	Civil Society (3)
Caritas Lucca	Civil Society (2)
Individual citizens	Civil society (1)
Qualità e Servizi SPA	Public Canteens Manager (3)
I.C. Carlo Piaggia	School (3)
I.C. Don Aldo Mei	School (3)
I.C. Ilio Micheloni	School (3)
Pisa University	Research (4)
Florence University	Research (1)
Agricultural Coop	Business (2)

Description of Co-Design Results

The co-design process proved effective in giving new strength to the intermunicipal Food Policy initiative. It provided new material and immaterial resources, with clear but flexible indications on how these resources should be used to achieve tangible goals in the short to medium term. This allowed to revive participation and actors' engagement, preventing the feeling that it was "just

another project” where we would be doing the same things again from scratch. Since this process was not yet completed at the time of writing (see above), the results highlighted concern the general process undertaken so far, including the workshops and the preparatory activity in the Living Lab.

Lessons Learned

Two expert facilitators were appointed, selected for their specific expertise in the focus of the workshop. In one case, the choice was motivated by the necessity to approach the topic of food poverty and access to food with a progressive mindset, overcoming traditional charitable approaches and food redistribution interventions. In the second case, knowledge and skills in nutrition, school canteens’ monitoring and evaluation and available initiatives were needed as a starting point for facilitating potentially articulated discussions, while preventing to get stuck on the usual obstacles (legal limitations, lack of specific facilities, nutritional guidelines, etc).

As we had experienced the trade-off between broad and open participation and the focused operationalisation of ideas, we scheduled more workshops than asked for to ensure that everyone had enough space and that feasible interventions were defined in time. The decision to hold workshops (also) outside the urban centre of the municipality of Capannori, to include rural settings and other municipalities, was consistent with this logic, even if it required a greater effort.

Outlook

The RLIs will be further elaborated during the second and third rounds of workshops. Meanwhile, LL members had met with the working groups’ coordinators and facilitators to align their expectations after the first round of sessions and to discuss the centrality of the shared scope of the various interventions (namely building a community of practice around the transition toward new school canteens’ management system). Conceptual maps were developed to describe the specific ideas which have emerged so far, and the visual summary of concrete proposals identified as the elements to kick off the next meetings. It was key to identify who, beyond the LL members, would oversee the progression of the RLIs.

Since a set of RLI ideas have emerged, and details on their operationalisation would come forward in the next round of workshops, the first action-reflection cycle might be centred on the actual feasibility of the interventions, expectations, intended and unintended outcomes, besides a better definition of indicators. With a long-term perspective, the possibility of adjusting RLIs according to the context and emergent needs would be crucial. In addition, it is worth pointing out that having the co-design process embedded in the food policy initiative might imply that multiple issues and ideas for action emerge for the medium and long-term activity of the food policy council.

2.5.3 PORTFOLIO OF REAL-LIFE INTERVENTIONS

The table below provides an overview of the real-life interventions planned during the co-design workshops in the Living Lab. The interventions are likely to be updated and adapted as a result of the second and third round of workshops.

INTERVENTION 1 – WORKING TABLE ON FOOD EDUCATION AND SCHOOLS	
Level	Municipal / City-region
Brief Description	Food education programme meant for accompanying the upcoming introduction of the “talking menu” in primary schools and kindergartens. The programme will encompass diverse actors (school children, teachers, local producers, etc.), needs (education, training, compliance with dietary guidelines, waste reduction) and activities (on-site visits, cooking labs, seminars, informative leaflets on the menu, etc.).
Objectives	Creating a shared food education programme to accompany the introduction of the “talking menu” through direct food experiences to increase children’s understanding and appreciation of healthy, nutritious and more sustainable food.
Activities envisaged	
1.	Teachers’ training and education kits
2.	Experiential food labs in schools
3.	Engaging with farms: on site-farm visits and farmers in schools
4.	Educational videos
5.	Supporting school vegetable gardens
6.	Activities directly and indirectly addressing families
Responsibilities	Municipality (various departments); ‘Ufficio Scuola’, schools (staff, including directors and teachers), Qualità e Servizi, further actors to be determined (TBD)
Resources	Material assets; know-how; video-making; nutritionist; cooks and kitchen staff; educators; TBD
Monitoring & Evaluation	A structured set of initiatives implemented, with a broad participation of schools, teachers, children and their families, but also producers and other food system professionals (cooks, kitchen staff, nutritionists), all contributing to bridge the gap

	between school children and sustainable and healthy food consumption.
Criteria: How does this intervention meet key project and local criteria?	
Engaging food deprived & vulnerable communities	Children in primary schools and kindergartens
Engaging innovative business models	Partly: The line of intervention does not engage further innovative business models, apart from the new public procurement and school canteens' management model, which is considered a novelty in the national public procurement landscape.
CLIC dimensions	<p>Linkages: covers urban and rural areas in the city-region</p> <p>Inclusion: involves different actors; children's vulnerability to unhealthy diets</p> <p>Connectivities: requires the active involvement of different sectors and municipal departments</p>
Food environments (and digital aspects if applicable)	Institutional and agri-food environment
Alignment with vision/strategic plan	Yes, see the food strategy and visioning process
Any other criteria developed with co-design partners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contributing to the transition towards the new school canteens' management model • Contributing to increase actors' participation and engagement in the Piana del Cibo food policy
Other important information	<p>Two more workshops planned, to define the details of the intervention.</p> <p>The "talking menu" is meant as a seasonal menu, clearly illustrating the origin of food and its nutritional, health and ecological value. It aims to better communicate with children and their families the value of food procurement choices, oriented towards food that is more locally sourced, fresh/less processed, organic, seasonal, and fair for supply chain operators</p>
INTERVENTION 2 – WORKING TABLE ON FOOD POVERTY AND ACCESS TO FOOD	
Level	City-region / Municipal
Brief Description	Anti-inflation/anti-crisis meal: preparing a complete, sustainable, and healthy meal with community recipes in open cooking labs
Objectives	Expanding/improving conditions for access to healthy and affordable food for all citizens; social inclusion

Activities envisaged	
1.	Definition of anti-inflation recipes, e.g. starting with traditional recipes of the 'poor local cuisine'
2.	Identification of community kitchens and other suitable spaces and assets, dedicated staff, and local producers for surplus food recovery.
3.	Involvement of similar cultural initiatives (e.g. inter-cultural food exchange dinner 'Cena dei mondi')
4.	Promotion of the initiative as a cycle of community events open to all (potentially starting with families, if in collaboration with schools)
Responsibilities	Third sector organisations, municipality, schools, Qualità e servizi, TBD
Resources	Community spaces and assets (kitchens, suitable spaces for food storage, preparation and consumption)
Monitoring & Evaluation	
Criteria: How does this intervention meet key project and local criteria?	
Engaging food deprived & vulnerable communities	Anti-crisis (and anti-stigma) initiative targeting households at risk of poverty
Engaging innovative business models	Not foreseen
CLIC dimensions	Co-benefits: addresses social (inclusion) and economic (affordability) goals Inclusion: aims at involving vulnerable individuals while addressing the stigma attached to food poverty measures
Food environments (and digital aspects if applicable)	Community
Alignment with vision/strategic plan	It fulfils the issue of right to food for all
Any other criteria developed with co-design partners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Contributing to the transition towards the new school canteens' management model Contributing to increase actors' participation and engagement in the Piana del Cibo food policy
Other important information	Two more workshops planned, to define the details of the intervention

INTERVENTION 3 – WORKING TABLE ON LOCAL PRODUCTION AND FOOD SUPPLY CHAINS	
Level	City-region /municipal
Brief Description	This intervention aims at supporting the transition towards the new school canteen management model by re-localising one or more food supply chains for public food procurement in the new scheme
Objectives	Increasing the number of local producers supplying food to school canteens Activating one or more local supply chains to supply local school canteens
Activities envisaged	
1.	Screening of needs and available assets in relation to the requirements of the upcoming seasonal menu (ongoing)
2.	Visits to farmers engaged in sustainable production in the area to talk about the project and assess willingness to partake in the public procurement plan (recruitment)
3.	Identification of other supply chain operators needed to recreate the local supply chain (e.g. food processors, bakers)
4.	Informative actions aimed at local producers and supply chain operators (e.g. sharing experiences of others already involved in similar initiatives)
5.	Focusing on one or two supply chains to pilot alternative procurement and organisational connections to the school canteens
Responsibilities	Municipality; farmers' organisations; Qualità e Servizi; working table coordinators; Slow Food; TBD
Resources	TBD
Monitoring & Evaluation	Local producers and supply chain operators involved in the pilot
Criteria: How does this intervention meet key project and local criteria?	
Engaging food deprived & vulnerable communities	Small and medium food businesses (gaining negotiation power in the supply chain and reducing their dependency from contracts with big retailers)
Engaging innovative business models	Business model that brings together in a temporary business association (ATI) all the small and medium-sized enterprises that are willing to supply school canteens on a local basis; Qualità e Servizi business and management model.

CLIC dimensions	<p>Co-benefits: addresses the social (local actors' participation in the initiative), economic (small farmers' livelihood) and environmental (beyond the compliance to environmental criteria) sustainability of the new school canteen model</p> <p>Linkages: spans across the whole territory of the city-region, including rural and urban areas</p> <p>Connectivities: involves different sectors and municipal departments</p>
Food environments (and digital aspects if applicable)	<p>Institutional food environment (school canteens/public food procurement)</p> <p>Agri-food environment</p> <p>Digital food environment</p>
Alignment with vision/strategic plan	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contributing to the transition towards the new school canteens' management model • Contributing to increase actors' participation and engagement in the Piana del Cibo food policy
Other important information	Two more workshops planned, to define the details of the intervention

INTERVENTION 4 – WORKING TABLE ON FOOD POVERTY AND ACCESS TO FOOD

Level	City-region
Brief Description	Upgrade and upscaling of the “La mi’ bottega” project (lit. “my local shop”). The project currently involves Caritas operators and small local shops scattered throughout the municipality, in delivering the so-called ‘spesa sospesa’ (lit. suspended shopping) to low-income households with limited mobility.
Objectives	Expanding/improving conditions for access to healthy and affordable food by all citizens, with a focus on low-income households (social services beneficiaries)
Activities envisaged	
6.	Outscaling and upscaling of the existing project (recruitment of new shops beyond the Municipality of Capannori, e.g. in Altopascio and Porcari)
7.	Public information board to improve citizens' access to information, e.g. on social services, calls for activities, etc
8.	Extending the project to include other food recovery practices - TBD
9.	Assessment of the overall initiative: evaluation of innovation capacity, community value, and limitations

Responsibilities	La mi' bottega project, Caritas onlus, municipalities
Resources	Existing project and actors involved; material assets (e.g. transport), volunteers/staff; TBD
Monitoring & Evaluation	A broader network expanded beyond the current network
Criteria: How does this intervention meet key project and local criteria?	
Engaging food deprived & vulnerable communities	Recipients of social services with limited mobility
Engaging innovative business models	Network of small businesses and other public and third sector actors collaborating to achieve social inclusion goals
CLIC dimensions	<p>Co-benefits: addresses social (inclusion), environmental (food waste reduction) and economic (network of small shops) goals</p> <p>Linkages: it spans across the whole municipal territory (which is characterised by being divided among 40 different rural-urban settlements) and aims to expand beyond this</p> <p>Inclusion: addresses social services beneficiaries</p> <p>Connectivities: high potential to involve different municipal departments</p>
Food environments (and digital aspects if applicable)	Retail (small proximity shops in rural areas of the municipality)
Alignment with vision/strategic plan	Upscaling and outscaling to include other municipalities and their businesses to achieve broader food access goals
Any other criteria developed with co-design partners	Contributing to increase actors' participation and engagement in the Piana del Cibo food policy
Other important information	Two more workshops planned to define the details of the intervention
INTERVENTION 5 – AWARENESS-RAISING AND KNOWLEDGE EXCHANGE	
Level	City-region
Brief Description	Cross-cutting awareness-raising and knowledge exchange initiatives on sustainable food. Connected to, and cross-cutting with, all other RLIs.
Objectives	Involving and informing the population about the value of food for health, the environment, and the territory and the value of the intermunicipal food policy initiative

Activities envisaged	
1.	Campaigns and communication actions with practitioners and food communities (e.g. farmers' markets)
2.	Creating a shelf of books on food at the public library
3.	Informative set of events with journalists, activists, influencers, and food researchers
Responsibilities	Piana del Cibo – activities will presumably involve all the working tables; municipalities; universities; TBD
Resources	Key contacts in local and national networks of food policies; TBD
Monitoring & Evaluation	A number of initiatives will be implemented; increased participation; increased knowledge and awareness; food policy governance/commitment; TBD
Criteria: How does this intervention meet key project and local criteria?	
Engaging food deprived & vulnerable communities	Only indirectly (amongst the general population) and through awareness raising initiatives
Engaging innovative business models	N/A
CLIC dimensions	<p>Co-benefits: Connecting food, health, the environment, the territory and creating support for the intermunicipal food policy initiative</p> <p>Inclusion: Broadening of the segments of the population in the region that know about and can get involved in the FPN activities</p> <p>Connectivity: Connecting the themes and activists of the different working groups in the FPN</p>
Food environments (and digital aspects if applicable)	Community (and digital) food environment (e.g. Piana del Cibo website and social media)
Alignment with vision/strategic plan	Cross-cutting knowledge and awareness of food systems
Any other criteria developed with co-design partners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contributing to the transition towards the new school canteens' management model • Contributing to increase actors' participation and engagement in the Piana del Cibo food policy
Other important information	Two more workshops planned to define the details of the intervention

3. OVERVIEW OF REAL-LIFE INTERVENTIONS

OVERVIEW OF REAL-LIFE INTERVENTIONS PER CITY REGION	
AARHUS	
1	SUPPORT LOCAL FARMING & CONSUMPTION CULTURE
2	ADDRESS FOOD LITERACY IN SCHOOLS
3	RECONNECT CHILDREN TO FOOD ORIGINS THROUGH LOCAL PRODUCTION
4	LOCAL FOOD COUNCIL
5	BUY BETTER FOOD, EDUCATING FOOD PROFESSIONALS & INSTITUTIONS
6	LESS FOOD WASTE, MORE FOOD SHARING
7	MAKE AARHUS GREENER
AMSTERDAM	
1	INFORMAL FOOD CIRCLES IN CITY-DISTRICT AMSTERDAM NOORD
2	FOOD COLLABORATIONS IN AMSTERDAM ZUIDOOST
3	COMMUNITY FOOD INITIATIVES IN HAARLEM SCHALKWIJK
4	SUSTAINABLE PUBLIC PROCUREMENT
5	COOPERATIVE FOOD PRODUCTION
BARCELONA	
1	NOURISHING LINKS
2	FOOD RETAIL WITH A COMMUNITY KITCHEN
3	COMMUNITARIAN AGROECOLOGY
4	GENERATIONAL RENEWAL OF FARMERS
5	FOOD SYSTEM TRANSFORMATION NETWORKING

BERLIN	
1	POLITICAL ROUNDTABLE
2	BERLIN FOOD POVERTY TRACKER
3	INTERCULTURAL FOOD HUB
4	FOOD-RELATED URBAN PLANNING
BRASOV	
1	EDUCATION IN NUTRITION AND HEALTH
2	SHORT FOOD VALUE CHAINS
3	URBAN AGRIFOOD MARKET
4	FOOD SECURITY
BUDAPEST	
1	BUDAPEST MARKET HALLS FOR SUSTAINABLE URBAN FOOD SYSTEMS
2	FARMCITY SHOP – EXTENDING THE BUYING COMMUNITY TO DISADVANTAGED SOCIAL
3	FRUIT & VEGETABLE SOCIAL COOPERATIVE IN DISTRICT VIII
4	WEKERLE FOOD HUB IN DISTRICT XIX
5	PERMACULTURE BALCONY GARDENING PROGRAMME AT THE KISPEST HOUSING ESTATE IN
6	LAUNCH OF COMMUNITY-BASED FOOD RESCUE PLATFORM
LISBON	
1	HORTAS NINHO URBAN FARMING
2	FOOD LITERACY
3	SOCIAL FOOD HAMPERS
LUCCA	
1	WORKING TABLE ON FOOD EDUCATION AND SCHOOLS
2	WORKING TABLE ON FOOD POVERTY AND ACCESS TO FOOD
3	WORKING TABLE ON LOCAL PRODUCTION AND FOOD SUPPLY CHAINS
4	WORKING TABLE ON FOOD POVERTY AND ACCESS TO FOOD
5	AWARENESS-RAISING AND KNOWLEDGE EXCHANGE

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